

**UNIVERSITY OF LIBRARY STUDIES
AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES**

Franz Zeilner

**OPTIMIZATION OF INFORMATION
PROCESSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM
OF REPUBLIC OF AUSTRIA**

DISSERTATION THESIS

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FACULTY OF INFORMATION SCIENCES
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DISSERTATION THESIS

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in Professional field 3.5. “Social Communications and
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Management of Information Processes”

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Abstract

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Digitalisation is the focus of interest of research in the field of educational science research, it also enables new learning and teaching methods. This dissertation came to the conclusion that personnel development, organisational development, teaching development, information technology development as well as coordination and cooperation development are the central areas in the context of digitalisation and school. This process is multidimensional and institutional; the essential unit of design is the specific school. This requires cooperation and coordination between school authorities and schools as well as with private institutions. Educators are the central actors in implementing the rapid technological change in the context of educational goals, and above all media literacy. Constitutive factors in this are the digital media and the direct actors in teaching. However, these factors must be further differentiated in order to be able to assess the direct or indirect effects of digitalisation. The developmental steps of digitalisation in the Austrian education system shown in the historical longitudinal section also show its significance for teaching practice. Digitalisation is "work in progress" and "history in progress".

Keywords: Education system, digitalisation, digital competence, digital media, digital school development, information technologies, media competence, teaching.

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INTRODUCTION

„Paths are made by walking“

Franz Kafka

The research areas

The present doctoral thesis (dissertation) comprises the following main research areas: Chapter I. Media developments, teaching media and basics of information processes, Chapter II. Digitality and digitalisation in the Austrian education system and Chapter III. Digital media in the classroom

The particular interest in these research areas or in this topic primarily arises from my work as a teacher and professor in higher education (BHMS, 29 years) and at the University of Salzburg (university lecturer and research assistant, 20 years). Here I was able to experience some of the developmental steps of digitalisation myself. The future living and working environment will be characterised by an increasing integration of digital communication and information processes and their intelligent use. For several years now, modern technologies and information technologies have made it possible to exchange and make information available to an enormously increasing extent. One of the tasks of educators is to enable pupils and students to use digital media competently, responsibly and critically. In this respect, there is basically also an interaction between school lessons and private use which can take place passively and actively and can also contribute to the optimisation of essential educational processes. Together and in coordination with their students, educators should, in particular, integrate digital teaching and learning processes into lessons and develop and enhance media competence. As a whole, the learning processes of the pupils should be supplemented or improved by media-supported teaching. Digital learning is only one of numerous other ways of learning. Learning itself is not digital, but digital media and tools are used as a means. A good learning effect requires above all didactically and methodically well prepared lessons. School education must enable pupils, among other things, to find their way in society. They should also be able to recognise and competently assess political, social and

economic problems. Digital media are of increasing importance in this context. National, European, international and global developments entail fundamental social and political changes that also comprise the media. Specific research is based on a broad concept of media shaped by cultural studies, which understands media not only as published channels of communication, but as functions of cultural practices and objects that are used by subjects to gain information about alterity or to convey it to them.

The focus of the present research lies is on investigating the essential development steps of digitalisation in the Austrian school system and digital media. Digitalisation is already a factor that has a lasting impact on the education sector, and requires essential competences. The society of the present and the future needs contemporary education, the active future-oriented shaping and further development of which is essential. This requires competences of the actors; media competence is a "key competence" here. Education at a high level using digital media is, among other things, an essential prerequisite for coping with present and future demands.

The use of digital media in schools for administrative purposes is not explicitly the object of investigation of this thesis.

Investigative approach/research methods

In the field of science, research methods or procedures and analytical techniques are necessary to deal with scientific questions. The present doctoral thesis was edited through a combination of different sources and methods (methodological pluralism). This required different research approaches, extensive and selective literature studies as well as the application of qualitative and quantitative methods. Extensive literature studies were already carried out in the planning phase, and were intensified and specified in the subsequent research phase. This required comprehensive library and internet research. Particular interest was devoted to the research question and the research guiding questions.

With regard to scientific studies investigating relevant questions, it was first decided on the basis of the abstract whether there was interest in a specific study and which questions could be answer. Due to the increasing number of scientific

publications, it was essential to clearly summarise and assess individual studies (meta studies and single studies) on the research topic. Various studies were examined and evaluated for their similarities and differences. In addition, the respective applied methods were outlined in order to enable an evaluation. The systematic examination of scientific studies also demonstrates the state of research on a specific topic and enables the summary of research results. The interpretation of studies has also been carried out in accordance with certain criteria - this concerns meta-studies and individual studies.

Meta studies are a statistical method for combining individual results from a number of selected studies that have the same research question. The objective of a meta-study is to determine a common value, which is expressed in an effect size. The effect size was examined for a small but practically significant effect, medium effect sizes and strong but practically significant effects.

Research goal and existing sources

The research objective of a scientific paper sets out the reason why the research is being carried out. The aim is not necessarily to solve a specific problem, but to obtain good insights into the problem.

This was precisely the intention of the present research. The aim was to investigate what progress has been made in terms of digitalisation in the Austrian school system and what (possible) potential exists for modern, efficient teaching in the context of school instruction. It was necessary to define what this effectiveness relates to. This work was performed through literature studies, but especially through analyses of scientific studies. This also includes the investigation of necessary competences of the actors or technical and pedagogical prerequisites and requires the investigation of developments of teaching in the Austrian school system in the national, European, international and global context, as well as their effects on scientific discourse and teaching practice. Based on the specific research results, essential findings for the education system shall be achieved, and a discourse shall also emerge. It should be possible to develop (further) questions which can then be discussed in the form of an "Education innovation Circle".

Regarding the existing sources, it was clear during the literature research that the totality of available sources on a certain topic and their status are in the field of science referred to as the "existing sources". Sources are therefore all materials from which scientific knowledge can be gained. This also includes scientific literature, which was also used extensively in the research in question. Both primary sources and secondary sources are available on the topic or research subject. A relatively large amount of academic literature, as well as studies are available on the research topic of digital media in the classroom. A careful selection is necessary here and was also carried out in the context of the present work.

Research questions and research guiding questions

Research question

What are the central areas of digital school development in the Austrian school system?

Research guiding questions

- a) Media developments, teaching media and basics on information processes in the context of school teaching
- b) The importance of models (excerpt)
- c) Essential development steps in the context of digitalisation in the Austrian school system.
- d) Basics on media education in the digital and global world
- e) Analysis of studies: Research topics and results

The research steps indicated here were of key importance to the **success criteria, the quality and effectiveness of the research** as well as the final **research result**. The **novelty** of my research comprises the investigation and presentation of the historical development of digitalisation in the Austrian education system in a historical longitudinal section as well as a good synopsis of selected research areas and the obtained results. This also includes the incorporation of meta-studies and individual studies on relevant research areas. The **opportunities for exploiting** my

research results can be found primarily in the fields of science, pedagogy and teaching practice. It was planned to disseminate the results of this dissertation through further publications.

CHAPTER I. MEDIA DEVELOPMENTS, TEACHING MEDIA AND BASICS ON INFORMATION PROCESSES

1.1. Media developments and teaching media: primary, secondary and tertiary media

1.1.1 No uniform distinction between media

If one examines the history of the media or their historical development, a distinction can be made between primary (human media), secondary (print media) and tertiary media (electronic and digital media). However, there is no uniform distinction of media. The distinction or categorisation by Harry Pross is, however, frequently applied in the field of science. Primary media are characterised by direct communication through speech, gestures and facial expressions. Secondary media are characterized by production through technical devices, reception without technical devices such as through written and printed media, wall and blackboard pictures, graphics, etc.¹ (Pürer 2014, p 68 ff).

1.1.2 Primary and human media

The "primary or so-called human media", with a limited coverage, existed until the 15th century. Here, the human being himself was the essential medium. For example, an actor would perform a rehearsed play for his audience, etc. In primary media, the interaction partners communicate directly with each other, they are media of "elementary human contact" through speech, gestures, facial expressions, body language, etc. (Faulstich 1996, p 31 f; cf. also Pürer 2014, p 68 ff). Human media then increasingly lost their importance; new media emerged and replaced or

¹ Later, the term "quaternary media" was also introduced. With the spread of computer-based communication, authors – when using networked computer technology - have used this term. These are "type 4 media". The sender and the receiver need an internet connection for this technology. There is no longer a classic sender-receiver role, but the communication is interactive. Basically, and also in the field of education, a distinction is made between analogue and digital media. The terms "new media" and "interactive media" are also used (Faßler 1997, p 1 ff; cf. also Scharpe 2012, p 2 ff).

overlapped with the human media (Faulstich 1996, p 31 f).

1.1.3 Secondary or print media

These developments already took place from the 15th century onwards. There were now secondary or print media such as the "Gutenberg Galaxy" (Marshall McLuhan 1962), and also the "Alphabetic Monopoly" (Friedrich Kittler 1986). At that time, these were only texts as memories of time; they were so-called recording systems. Kittler basically distinguishes between three phases. He refers to the first two phases as the recording systems 1800 and 1900; he does not denominate the following phase. In the field of scientific research, this period is sometimes referred to as "recording system 2000". In his publication "Grammophon, Film, Typewriter" (1986), Friedrich Kittler explains the embedding of media in our culture as the historical evolution of the inventions mentioned in the title² (Niebisch/Süess 2015, p 1 ff).

The most significant secondary media included books, newspapers, also various prints or types of printing, etc. Leaflets were also already used. Here, production of these was carried out by means of technical devices; however, no technical devices are required for reception. For example, wall and blackboard pictures, written media, print media, graphics, etc. These media are also very essential for education or school lessons (Medien: Didaktik, Methodik, Unterrichtspraxis, p 1 ff; cf. also Faulstich 1996, p 31).

1.1.4 Tertiary or electronic media

a) From the radio to the computer and social media:

From the late 19th century onwards, there was a further transition towards tertiary or electronic media. An example here is "Global village" (McLuhan 1962). Electronic media also had consequences, e.g. TV in the 20th century, etc.

² From the 1890s onwards, the mass press also spread, accompanied by fundamental politicisation. In particular, the freedom of the press was essential for the mass press, at that time. The press spread almost universally in the 19th century. Political newspapers, journals, magazines, etc. were published and distributed (<http://www.medien-gesellschaft.de>>massenpresse-mediengesellschaft, p 1 f).

Photography, sound and image recording were new storage media. A storage medium or data memory is used for storing data; the term storage medium is also used as a synonym for a specific data carrier. Data storage media already existed in the Stone Age; in the present they are viewed mainly in the context of the digital world (Völz 2007, p 1 ff). Since the 1920s, radio fulfilled the role of an information and propaganda medium. In Austria, RAVAG was founded in 1924, and the medium of radio consequently existed. The first radios were "detectors" with poor acoustic quality. Since the 1950s there was also television in Austria, which started in 1955. This was public television in the context of the ORF. In the beginning, there were only two programmes, starting at 5 p.m. and ending at midnight. During the rest of the time, a so-called test picture was shown (Zeilner, 2011).

In Austria, the first private, local TV channels were then also available in the widespread TV cable networks from the 1990s. Private television, which had originally been controversial and contested, was now topical, and a depoliticisation also took place here. As a result, new channels were created and the "Privatfernsehgesetz" came into force on 1 August 2001. This federal law (Privatfernsehgesetz -PrTV-G) regulates the broadcasting of television via terrestrial means as well as radio and television in cable networks and via satellite. The "ORF Gesetz" (BGBl. No. 379/1984) remained unaffected. Addressing the topic of private television also in lessons, here especially in politics lessons, is of crucial importance for pupils and students. Of course, this also applies to public television (Bundesgesetz für die Republik Österreich; Jahrgang 2001, ausgegeben am 3.1 Juli 2001, Teil I. 84. Privatfernsehgesetz -PrTV-G).

b) The 1980s/1990s:

Digital media have also existed since the 1980s. Information in digital media is conveyed via interfaces. Moreover, this does not mean the mere distribution of information; users can also become active. This was and is also relevant for education

and school lessons³ (Kittler 1986, p 1 ff).

There were now personal computers, social media and also new forms of political public media. A digitally based media network also emerged. Digitalisation also made manipulations of the data volume possible, such as modulation, transformation, synchronisation, storage, scanning, scrambling, mapping etc. The computer became the integrating main medium; all media of the modern era implode in the computer. A universal media convergence developed (Kittler 1986, p 8).⁴

However, precursors of the computer have existed since ancient times, that was around 1100 BC the "abacus". Compared to other electrical devices of the modern era, modern computer technology was then developing very rapidly. In particular, the entire 20th century was essential for developments in the context of the computer. As far as personal computers (PCs) were concerned, the first home computers - such as "Altair 8800" - were available from 1974. In 1977, for example, the "Apple II" followed, in 1978 in Germany the "Commodore PET 2001", in 1981 the "IBM-PC" and in 1987 the "Apple Macintosh". From 1985 onwards, computers were networked (e.g. LAN, Internet), in 1989 IBM's OS/2, in 1991 Linux, in 1991/1992 MS-DOS and Windows 3.0/3.1. Major Windows developments also occurred in the period from 1994 to 2000 (Duffner/Lauffer 2002, p 6 ff).

From about the beginning of the 1980s, the technology had already advanced to such an extent that companies, educational sectors and private users were

³ Historically, "digitalisation" can be seen as an epochal signature of the modern era. There are good examples of historical digitisation processes. For example, the spread of the monetary economy since the medieval economic revolution. The spread of clocks and a digital consensus on time. The reorganisation of work through Taylorism and psycho-technique. The spread and networking of electronic calculators. Computers were and are also networked (<http://www.hsozkult.de/event/92123>, p 1 ff; cf. also Tschiggerl et al. 2019).

⁴ Some educators, especially from the higher school sector, already had computers at their disposal in Austria from about the mid-1980s. The beige computer "Commodore C64", which was also called a bread box, was frequently used. It had 64 kilobytes (0.064 megabytes) of RAM. It was possible to write, draw, calculate and programme with this computer, which did not yet have any internal mass storage devices. The computer paper used at that time was the so-called fanfold paper. In its full potential, the Commodore C64 was a programmable all-purpose computer (Salzburger Nachrichten. Das Internet der 80er Jahre/SN.at, 17.01.2018).

benefiting from the use of computers. Of critical importance here was the development of the necessary software and the operating systems MS-DOS and Windows. These developments were also well marketed and made suitable for mass use. From about the mid-1980s onwards, computers were also common in Austrian (secondary) schools. Rapid developments subsequently also led to the founding of numerous companies in the context of information technology, such as Apple, IBM and Microsoft. The 21st century was also characterized by rapid developments in computers and the entire information technology (Geschichte – computer und roboter - technik - planet wissen, p 1 ff; cf. also Müller Peter (2014). Historie: Apple und IBM: Aus Feinden werden Partner. tecchannel.de (Apple und ibm: aus feinden werden partner)).

c) The topic of mass media:

From 1945 or the end of the Second World War until the spread of the internet in the 1980s, radio, television, newspapers, magazines, etc. were of crucial importance for information and (political) opinion-forming processes. Political opinion-forming processes often took place in the triangle of politics, mass media and the population. The important thing is that mass media have a large reach (masses), with a flow of information primarily from the sender to the recipient. This flow of information is characteristic of so-called "push media", which assigned a passive-receptive role to their recipients (D&E Heft 74 2017)⁵.

With the spread of the Internet since the 1980s, this period of media history gradually came to an end. Before the internet, there was the "Arpanet", the "Advanced Research Projects Agency Network". Arpanet was a computer network developed by a small group of researchers under the direction of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and the US Department of Defense on behalf of the US Air Force starting in 1968. Computers from various US universities were networked at that time. The military played a major role as contracting entity and financier. The

⁵ Push media are media or information formats that are delivered without the active intervention of users. Messages flow unidirectionally (in one direction only) from the sender to the recipient. In principle, push media can only be influenced by the recipient in a very general way, for example by switching the receiving device on and/or off (Dittmar Jakob F. 2011, p 1 ff).

structure of the Arpanet made it possible to outline the relationship of these research institutions. This network was so influential that its specific shape made all other structures for connecting computers redundant. At that time, basic principles of computer networks were also developed for and tested in the Arpanet.

The Arpanet is the precursor of today's Internet.⁶

Starting in 1983, the Internet Protocol (IP) opened up a modern or new standard for data transmission in computer networks. The Internet Protocol is a network protocol; it combines the information to be transmitted in IP data packages and regulates the transmission of the data packets to the specific destination. The Internet is a global network; each computer has a unique numeric IP address. This is the "internet protocol address". Due to its function, the Internet Protocol (IP) represents the basis of the Internet (cf. also *Optische Netze - Systeme Planung Aufbau*. 1. Auflage, dibkom GmbH, Straßfurt, p 35).⁷

Since the beginning of the 1990s, the development of the World Wide Web (www) has made it possible for PC users who are online to use or browse the Internet; the development of a net browser was a prerequisite for this. The World Wide Web is a system of electronic hypertext documents that can be accessed via the Internet, i.e. web pages encoded in HTML. They are linked to each other by hyperlinks and are transmitted on the Internet via the https or http protocols. Web pages often contain texts, often with pictures, also videos, audio documents, etc. If selected correctly and prepared well, these can be useful for teaching (Wikipedia,

⁶ Arpanet, a computer network, became part of the internet. The decentralised structure of the Internet is found in key technical and cultural elements such as collaborative development (RFCs), net neutrality, etc. The ARPANET was developed under the leadership of the U.S. Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA) and is based on a concept. It was originally developed by a group of researchers led by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and the U.S. Department of Defense on behalf of the U.S. Air Force (from 1968) (<https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arpanet>, p 1 f).

⁷ By means of IP address and subnet mask, computers within a network can be divided into logical units (subnets). This makes it possible to address computers in larger networks. Logical addressing is the basis for "routing". Public IP addresses must be clearly assignable worldwide. Their allocation is regulated by the Internet Assigned Numbers Authority (IANA). (https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_Protocol, p 1 f).

World Wide Web, p 1).

For today's pupils, the relationship to mass media is basically a very complex network of relationships and influences. Above all, the influence of the parents, the school and the circle of friends plays a vital role, which is why a differentiated view is important. According to the results of a study in the canton of Zurich, pupils use mass media in a very differentiated way and frequently include them in their everyday life. Each medium has its own specific significance in the overall constellation, even though the various media do not mean the same thing to all pupils. Educational instances (socialisation instances) have an essential significance in this context (Die Massenmedien im Leben der Schüler. Ergebnisse ..., p 1 ff).

d) The World Wide Web (www): Start in 1989

Tim Berners-Lee, a British physicist and computer scientist, published a so-called concept paper for a system of distributed documents on the Internet in 1989. The implementation simplified the use of the internet in a revolutionary way. It was no longer necessary to act via complicated inputs, but it was now possible to move from one document to another connected document by "mouse-click". This is how the World Wide Web (www) was created (D&E Heft 74 2017). ⁸

1.1.5 Digital media

a) From the mid-1990s: The full cultural potential

Digitalisation unfolded its essential cultural potential around the mid-1990s. Computers were no longer just individual machines; they now became parts of a network that - as a cultural matrix - surpassed everything that had existed before as a space of knowledge and experience. A comparison with the invention of writing systems or the alphabet is controversial. In addition to comparisons with the invention and spread of writing, comparisons with the invention of printing are also

⁸ The application possibilities of the World Wide Web must be viewed from a variety of angles. Decisive factors here are school levels, types of schools, existing technical requirements, the interest of educators, etc. These are my own experiences as an educator in the sector of vocational secondary and high schools (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

controversially discussed with regard to the fundamental nature of the digital transformation. Already in the 20th century, digital media or electronic media that are digitally encoded were a revolutionary development (Tschiggerl et al 2018, p 88 f).

The electronic media of the 20th century such as television, video, computers etc. also shaped its imagery. Where classical print media mainly depicted reality, they created a new image of reality through reconstruction (Faulstich 2005). People of the present are surrounded by images as never before; and they are overwhelmed by images in electronic media such as television, internet, computer, video etc. Of course, this also impacts the field of education. Science has already turned increasingly to this development under the catchword "Iconic Turn" (Bpb.de, p 1 f).⁹

b) Social networks: Since around 2000

Around the turn of the millennium, further significant technical developments took place. Web 2.0 went far beyond the logic of Web 1.0. Web 2.0 technologies enable diverse forms of communication and participation (D&E Heft 74 2017).

The historical development of social networks is also a story of start-ups and how they changed the market and became established. Already in the 1980s, the first social interaction took place on "bulletin board systems". However, the exchange of messages in an open forum had little in common with social networks of the present day (Werbeagentur Graz, p 1 f).

c) Beginning of the digital age 2002

In the field of science, it is assumed that 2002 was the year in which mankind was already able to store more information in digital than in analogue media. This was the beginning of the digital age with rapid developments of digital media, which are, however, very dynamic. In 2002, the platform "Friendster" achieved a

⁹ Among other things, the question "What is a political image?" is relevant in the context of teaching. One essential aspect here is that the contextualisation is decisive, not the image genre such as poster, cartoon, etc. The context of use is also important in order to be able to qualify an image as a political image. It is about the politicisation of the "visual association". The perception of images follows its own associative logic. It is very essential that images can make something visible that cannot be conveyed so well linguistically. A visual competence enables an innovative approach to questions of political science (Liebhart 2020, p 1 ff).

development that was to have a significant influence on the behaviour of users. In particular, people were supposed to get to know other people (first) on the internet and then get into physical contact with them later. Friendster then changed from a social platform to a "gaming platform". This service was then discontinued in 2018 (Werbeagentur Graz, p 1 f).

Milestones in the development of social platforms also occurred with the founding of other companies. These were, for example, LinkedIn and Myspace in 2003, Orkut and Xing in 2004, Facebook in 2004 and StudiVZ in 2005. The network google+ was founded in 2011. However, this search engine did not succeed in establishing a social platform, and google+ was discontinued in 2019 (Werbeagentur Graz, p 1 f).

1.1.6 Use of digital media

Not only has the intensity of use of many media changed, but the spectrum of "teaching media" used has also expanded considerably over the centuries. Initially, books, that were selectively and then widely used, were important for the school sector. Subsequently, another standard of (acoustical, visual and audio-visual) instructional media developed in the school sector. In the early 1980s, the computer established itself as the central media innovation and as a mass medium. Digital media were already part of the standard, but their existence alone does not enable to use them in an effective and meaningful way. Adjustments on the part of teachers and students are necessary in this respect. ¹⁰

Pupils and students frequently already integrate digital media into their everyday lives, especially for the purpose of communication, information and entertainment. However, the intensity of use depends on the age. Educators should reflect on "How can we succeed in making these already existing knowledge elements utilisable for school learning processes" (Zeilner, 2021). Another essential question that is controversially discussed is, for example, "Do digital media facilitate

¹⁰ Digital media have also already brought about social change in many areas of life; especially communicative practices have been changed. Communication is very essential in people's lives, in education it has a central function (Luhmann 1981, p 26 ff), www.lmz-bw.de, p 1 ff.

learning? The so-called Hattie Study (Hattie, visible Learning) - as well as other studies - provided interesting results, which are also shown in this thesis. It is also important to note that "digital media are not good or bad per se", the people who use them are decisive (Schaumburg 2019. p 1 ff; cf. also Cornelsen.de, Unterricht gestalten, p 1 ff).¹¹

These are the pupils, the students and the educators. The digital transformation led to a multitude of changes. At a commission meeting in 2019 at the University of Göttingen with the title "Teaching media in the context of digital change", for example, it was demonstrated that teaching without media is inconceivable, especially because the (teaching) content to be dealt with in class hardly ever simply exists, but must first be made perceptible. Despite this central role, the media - since the 1990s including the digital media - are still a rather marginal topic in educational research. The "pluralisation of the representation" of educational content, and the "hype" about digital media must, however, be put into perspective, because the evidence for this pluralisation does not particularly indicate a transformation of representational modes in teaching. At any rate, this is subject to discussion (Kommissionstagung 2019: Unterrichtsmedien im Kontext digitalen Wandels, p 1 ff).

1.2. Terminology, definitions and scientific basics of relevant research areas

1.2.1 Terminology, definitions

Concepts or definitions belong to the basic elements of every science. At the same time, however, they are also the subject of scientific discourse. "It is not the definition that determines the application of a term, but the use of the term that

¹¹ This concerns above all the selection and preparation of teaching and learning content as well as the availability of necessary competences. This can basically lead to more efficient teaching and to an increased learning motivation. The use of digital media should be seen as an additional opportunity for teaching and learning. Media competence is necessary for pupils to cope well in the digital world; this has been and is being extensively demonstrated. In addition to other subjects, political education, for example, is very suitable for acquiring and applying digital competences in various areas of competence. However, (potential) negative influences of digital media or computer technology must always be kept in mind (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

determines what is known as its "definition" "or its "meaning". (Popper 1994).

In principle, both also apply to the terms and definitions relevant in the specific research. In particular, in the context of education or school and digitalisation, (digital) media, etc. Furthermore, this also applies to discussions on the understanding of specialist terminology in the national, international, European and global context. However, terminology and definitions from the Anglo-American area or other countries cannot always be translated word for word. Terminologies and definitions have also been subject to fundamental changes over time, which is why they should be viewed in contemporary understanding (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Scientific research or works in the humanities, social and cultural sciences also mean working with and on concepts. In this context, concepts are tools with which reality is broken down and constituted in the research process. The more clearly these concepts are defined, the more transparently and conclusively they are demarcated from counter-concepts and conceptual alternatives, the more exact the result will be. The sciences of the present are characterised by plurality, ambivalence and heterogeneity in the context of research projects. The basis of "fundamental concepts" or the question of which terminology, definitions and basics are essential in this research was decided by the author. This also means a theoretical positioning in the state of research and thus an argumentative derivation in the context of the objective research.¹²

1.2.2 Digitization/Digitality

a) Contemporary understanding of digitization

In its original sense, the term "digitalisation" is a technical term in the special fields of electronics, computer science, communications engineering, etc. and means "the conversion of analogue signals into digital data that can be further processed by a computer". For several years now, the term, together with related terms that are

¹² <http://www.geschichtstheorie.de>, p 1. Several terms are relevant here - but above all digitalisation, digital media, communication and information technologies - for which, however, there is basically no truly objective definition. Every circumscription in this context is selective and therefore at the same time constructive (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

often used synonymously, has become a common term that is ambiguous in its meaning. In comparison with the subject context, the meaning has consequently been expanded and modified (Bidt.digital, Glossar Digitalisierung, p 1 ff).

In contemporary understanding, "digitalisation" has several meanings. It can mean the digital transformation and representation or implementation of information and communication or also the digital modification of instruments, devices, etc., but also the digital revolution or digital turn. The terms "information age" and "computerisation" are also relevant in this context. Digitalisation means the transformation of analogue, i.e. continuously representable values or the gathering of information on physical objects in formats suitable for processing or storage in digital technology systems (Wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de).

In the present, the term digitalisation is used broadly and vaguely for the use of various digital technologies and associated transformation processes in subsystems. In the present research, this subsystem is the education sector or the Austrian school system. It must be noted here that digitalisation is presently not a clearly defined scientific term, but a so-called "umbrella term" (Bidt.digital, Glossar Digitalisierung, p 1 ff).

b) Digitalization in a historical retrospect

In historical retrospect, "digitalisation" initially meant nothing more than that machines were controlled with the help of digital software. Here, computer operations took over the role of humans. However, a completely different situation arises when software-controlled machines are linked via the internet. Devices begin to communicate and (permanently) report back data. If machines and devices are networked, i.e. they can communicate with each other, this is called "Industry 4.0". Digitalisation has already led to significant changes not only in the media landscape,

but also in the education sector.¹³ (Borchart 2018, p 14 f).

However, changes in the media landscape can be observed in a historical longitudinal section even before digitalisation or for decades. New communication technologies also led to an increase in media companies and the spectrum of media content offered (Wikipedia, Medien in Österreich, p 1 ff; cf. also D&E Heft 74 2017).

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The use of computers and the internet has also led to significant changes in the use of media. This also affects the education and teaching sector in many countries, including Austria. (Digital) Media are fundamentally a factor that shapes teaching, which is reciprocally related to other teaching factors (content, learning objectives, methods). Research results show that a unidirectional effect of digital media, such as the computer, cannot be assumed.¹⁵

c) Digitalisation in the narrower and wider sense

Professor Stalder of the Zurich University of the Arts (Digital Culture),

¹³ Learning 4.0 is already relevant and will become of increasing relevance. Learning 4.0 is understood as a subsumption of developments in the professional world that shape the learning culture. It is self-organised microlearning, for the acquisition and implementation of learning content and for the direct use of new technologies to design one's own learning environment or the networks used for this purpose. Opportunities for reflection through peer groups are essential here. The author Karl Lang has written a publication on this topic and problem entitled Personnel Management 4.0. The focus on changes, trends, etc. is topical. This also applies above all to a change in the learning culture (Lang 2018, p 1 ff).

¹⁴ New media such as radio (in Austria since 1924), television (since the 1950s) developed into a mass medium in the 1960s. While video (since the 1980s) or interactive games and edutainment software (multimedia: at the beginning of the 1990s) have each only led to varying extensions of offers, a fundamental change in the media system can be observed since the spread of internet technology (https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/medien_in_österreich, p 1 ff; cf. also D&E Heft 74 2017).

¹⁵ It must be pointed out to pupils and students that technical innovations, especially the current rapid development of communication and information technologies, have profound social consequences that also affect the education system and the school curriculum. In the context of the growing importance of new or digital media, the qualifications that schools should impart to their graduates are discussed in the field of science (https://refubium-fu-berlin.de/handle/03_kapitel3, p 37 ff).

distinguishes between digitalisation in the narrower and broader sense. According to this view, "digitalisation" in the narrower sense is the process of transforming an analogue medium into a digital medium (e.g. scanned book). In the broader sense, digitalisation is a change in processes which are organised with such media. This means that things that were previously organised with analogue media are now organised with digital media. In this focus, digitalisation can be understood similarly to literacy (Stalder 2021, p 3 ff).

d) Digitality

In contemporary understanding, "digitality" means the connections between people, between people and objects and between objects, which are based on digitally encoded media and technologies. In contrast to "digitalisation" or "digital transformation", which are to be understood primarily as technological developments, "digitality" refers much more strongly to social and cultural practices. This concerns the social and cultural reflection of a change that produces new communication norms, identity models, social structures, etc. (Hennig et al 2019, p 1 ff).

In other words, "digitality" is what emerges when the process of digitalisation has reached a certain depth and breadth, creating a new space of opportunity shaped by digital media (Stalder 2021, p 4).

With the establishment of social networks and other forms of Web 2.0, the possibilities of political communication and political decision-making have changed a lot. The monopoly of media services such as providing people with news, culture, science and much more, as well as their interpretation, is no longer in classic media's hands. This also affects the school education sector and should also be addressed in this context. As a whole, the so-called "Riepl's Law" seems to be confirmed in the media sector (D&E Heft 74 2017).

This law ("Law of Indispensability"), which was established by Wolfgang Riepl in 1913, states that older means of news transmission, such as newspapers, will

never be completely replaced by new media, such as radio, etc. ¹⁶ (Wolfgang Riepl: Das Nachrichtenwesen des Altertums mit besonderer Rücksicht auf die Römer. Leipzig, Berlin 1913. Faksimile Nachdruck 1972).

Riepl speaks of a "basic law of the development of communications". This means that the simplest means, forms and methods, once they have been established and found useful, can never be completely and permanently displaced and put out of use again, even by the most perfect and highly developed ones (Riepl 1913, p 1 ff).

1.2.3 Ethics: in the context of digitization and digital media

a) Ethics

Ethics is a branch of philosophy that deals with the prerequisites and evaluation of human action. Ethics is the methodical reflection on morality (Lexikon Philosophie - Hundert Grundbegriffe, Reclam, 2011, p 80).

Ethics is the teaching or theory of human action according to the distinction between good and evil. The subject of ethics is morality. In the present day, an empirical, descriptive ethics is distinguished from normative ethics, which formulates a moral obligation and claims to be generally binding. A third direction is meta-ethics, which makes no substantive statements but analyses the terms of ethical argumentation (Wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de, Ethik p 1).

In the context of science, ethics also has the function of examining norms and values in the understanding of morality. However, norms and values are in principle

¹⁶ In communication science, three law-like statements can be made on the subject of media: 1. Law of necessity: media come into being (and as permanent institutions only) when social need has arisen. 2. Law of non-displacement ("Unverdrängbarkeitsgesetz": media do not die. 3. acceleration law: media appear on the stage of social communication at progressively shorter intervals (Riepl 1913/1972).

discussed controversially (Wiater 2011, p 60 f).¹⁷

b) Ethics as a general educational goal

As a matter of principle, law and ethics or morality are fundamentally closely connected, and this applies mainly to everyday language. This applies in particular to the field of criminal law, where the protection of certain goods that are fundamentally associated with values in people's minds is concerned. Their observance is considered morally imperative, and their protection is expected from the state. The term "morality" stands for the norms and values, rules and commandments that apply in a society. In practical philosophy, the term "ethics" is used for the study of moral issues and their justifications. Educators in particular are required to have basic professional and didactic knowledge and skills with regard to ethical questions. This also includes ethical questions of media use. They should be able to reflect on ethical questions and conflicts and contribute to their solution or attempted solution. The adequate and scientifically oriented handling of ethical problems is already a general educational goal in Austria (BGBL II No. 250/2021 - RIS document).¹⁸

c) Digital ethics (media ethics)

The digital transformation of many areas of life also leads to the fact that the topic of ethics in education is becoming increasingly important. The education sector

¹⁷ Norms and values are basically also subject to change. This can be explained in particular by the rapid increase in knowledge, its dissemination in the context of digitalisation and globalisation, and the associated possibilities for intervention and use. However, the implications and consequences of these developments are becoming increasingly unpredictable. A continuous and intensive public discourse on substantial ethical problems is necessary in this context. This encompasses several areas of ethics and in the present work "media ethics" (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

¹⁸ This has already been taken into account in many teacher training programmes in Austria. Ethics education is very important for pupils and students to address problems and contribute to the discourse. The topic of new technologies and digitalisation also opens up many questions. The fundamentally high innovation dynamics of digitalisation require knowledge and adaptation. New technologies open up many opportunities to work more effectively, more efficiently and simpler (especially with regard to the expenditure of time), but they also involve risks. This should be clearly pointed out to pupils and students. This also leads to important questions in the context of ethics. For example, "What ethical and moral principles are essential for people to live together in the digital world" (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

is currently dominated by two narratives. This is the narrative of digital equipment for schools, e.g. tablets for all schools, and the narrative of new digital forms of teaching and learning. The idea of ethical digital literacy is subject to discussion. Above all, this should also enable pupils and students to acquire a reflective attitude. Ethics, which is not to be equated with morality, is a scientific discipline. Digital ethics is now an essential part of this discipline (Grimm 2020, p 113).

Digital ethics encompasses the areas of impact of digital media and computer-controlled infrastructure on the individual and society. In a digital society, digital ethics reflects fundamental values and beliefs. Of critical importance here are arguments why certain values and norms should apply in the digitalised world and especially on the Internet. Orientations for action and a scientific discourse are required in this context. To date, there are actually no standards for moral action, and there is controversial debate on this topic. However, with the definition of ten (10) commandments of digital ethics an attempt has, among other things, been made to point out rules of conduct. These are: "1. Tell and show as little as possible about yourself. 2. Do not accept that you are being observed and that your data is being collected. 3. Do not believe everything you hear. 3. Don't believe everything you see online and get information from different sources. 4. Don't allow anyone to be hurt and bullied. 5. Respect the dignity of others and remember that there are rules on the web. 6. Don't trust everyone you interact with online. 7. Protect yourself and others from drastic content. 8. Don't measure your worth by likes and posts. 9. Don't judge yourself and your body by numbers and statistics. 10. Rest your mind every now and

then and give yourself a break.¹⁹

There are already numerous teaching materials on the topic of (media) ethics. There are, for example, also predetermined rules of conduct on how to behave on the "net". Just as in "real" life, it is also necessary to observe certain rules of conduct in the digital world. The term "netiquette" covers rules for behaviour on the internet and in digital communication. Netiquette regulates behaviour in computer networks, especially on the Internet. These are rules for communicating, interacting, dealing with each other in communities, in discussion forums, chats, etc. What is relevant in this context is the entire e-mail traffic. This is aimed at behaviour in virtual space, and concerns both dealing with other users and protecting one's own interests. Legal and ethical areas are affected by this. However, online behaviour should always be monitored - also in the context of media ethics or digital ethics (Wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de, Netiquette Definition, p 1).

Digital ethics is an extension of applied media ethics, which refers to classic media and social media such as Facebook, etc. The importance of digital ethics is enlarged due to the increasing digitalisation of areas of people's lives. The subject of digital ethics covers all areas of life and action that are shaped by digital technologies

¹⁹ <http://www.digitale-ethik.de/beratung10-gebote>, p 1 f; cf. also FH-Magazin future 06. Whether and to what extent these ten commandments are relevant for educators, pupils and students is under discussion. However, a high standard of care is necessary because digital media in the world of today offer many opportunities for networking and creative development. A variety of individual and social challenges will consequently emerge. "Always online" is a current topic; real communication is at least minimised here, even though social contact is very important for people. It should also be discussed, for example, that a lot of information about users is collected and often processed by algorithms for advertising purposes, etc. Sometimes this is also used for manipulation, fraud, etc. This is not always the case. Sometimes also for manipulation, fraud, blackmail, etc. Hate postings, fake news etc. are a real situation and should be addressed in class (Zeilner, 1991-2015). For teaching, especially for lower secondary schools, the Landesmedienzentrum Baden-Württemberg, for example, offers a collection of materials on the topic of "media ethics". Of topical importance are the teaching module 1 (Sek I) Basics of media ethics, the teaching module 2 (Sek I) Media ethics in (digital) everyday life, teaching impulse (Sek I) Du sollst nicht posten? 10 Gebote der digitalen Ethik, Zusatzmaterial (Sek I) "Ethik macht klick" - Werte Navi fürs digitale Leben, editorial by Dr Petra Grimm Medieethik - Befähigung zu einer reflektierten Haltung (<https://www.lmz-bw.de>>das gute digitale leben-unterrichtsmaterial zu medienethik, p 1 f).

and their manifestations. The internet, big data, artificial intelligence, etc. are relevant for the field of education. The promotion of information literacy should be the main focus of digital education, especially because social media are increasingly relevant for opinion-forming. Never before has so much information been available, especially through the internet, but this can also pose a risk to IT security and also requires knowledge in the education sector (Grimm 2020, p 113 f).

1.2.4 Information, Information process and information technologies

a) Information

In information theory, information means the knowledge that a (sender) transmits to a recipient via an information channel. In many cases, the information channel is a (digital) medium. The information leads to an increase in knowledge for the recipient. There is no uniform definition of information; the term has often been defined in different ways. For example, in basic librarianship, which is also very essential in education, information is referred to as the content transmitted by the various media (Saur 2016, p 6).

b) Information processes

Even though information processes are basically of considerable relevance, they must be examined in the context under consideration. Information processes are basically procedures intended for the acquisition, usage, storage, processing and forwarding of information (Wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de., Informationsprozess. Definition).

In the context of education, information processes as well as media education are an important topic. This also includes knowledge about the possibilities of information and information processes. Competences concerning the creative handling of knowledge and the mastering of information processes are essential for the actors. The Austrian federal government proclaimed 2019 the "Year of Digitalisation", which also means that a major, far-reaching upheaval is actively taking shape. The education system or school is also in transition to a fundamentally networked future in many areas. In particular, media, possibilities of communication,

etc. are further developing rapidly. "Digital competences" are already another basic competence. This requires educators, pupils and students to have knowledge in areas that are particularly relevant here, such as information, communication, media, teaching media, etc. (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

c) Information technologies

Information technologies are all technical means that serve the automatic or machine-assisted generation, storage, processing and/or transmission of information. In addition, all components necessary for this, including the programmes and the technical requirements for communication. Information technology (IT) is basically divided into hardware and software, and both areas are subject to further development (Wirtschaftslexikon24.com, Informationstechnik, p 1).

Basic knowledge of information technologies used is necessary in the context of education or school, especially for educators. Information technology (IT) is already a key technology of the 21st century. Computers, smartphones, etc. used in the context of education have up-to-date electronic and software components. For pupils and students, basics of information technologies are also important, and can be learned in the context of media education, etc. Information technology is also a branch of education or study in higher technical schools (HTL) in Austria and also a possible field of study within the framework of Bachelor's and Master's degree programmes. In this research, information technologies are of particular importance in the context of the digitalisation of schools and the use of digital media in teaching (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

1.2.5 Internet

a) "Internet" and "net"

The Internet (prefix: Inter and network) is a worldwide network of computer networks, the autonomous systems. It enables the use of Internet services such as WWW, e-mail, etc. Here, every computer can connect to every other computer. The exchange of data between the computers connected via the Internet takes place via the technically standardised Internet protocols. The RFCs of the Internet Engineering

Task Force (IETF) describe the technology of the Internet. From the general English technical term for an "internetwork" or "internet", the word "internet", which is also included in the Duden dictionary, spread as a proper name.²⁰

With the social penetration of the internet, the terms "internet" and "network" became common. In computer science, however, "net" does not necessarily refer to the internet, as there are also other network infrastructures.

In the context of teaching, the term "Internet" is basically used. The topic of the Internet and the public sphere is also relevant here, and this also affects legal norms such as copyright law, etc. The legal norms which apply in the public sphere differ from those applicable in the non-public or private sphere. This requires educators, pupils and students to deal with norms relevant to the use of media. Examples of the public sphere in the school sector are the internet (including the internet pages of a specific school), school newspapers, school events in which people from outside the school also participate. For teachers, the topic of public reproduction of content in school is also essential and legally relevant²¹ (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

In any case, the internet transcends the public sphere; the concept here is also a component of the self-understanding of modern democratic societies. From a phenomenological perspective, the internet has constituted itself as a public space; it enables a general appearance of content before other possibilities. In a digital society, public spaces are not only physical, but virtual spaces. The position of the human being as a historical subject is changed by enabling them to fundamentally determine their own place in the medialized world (Leguizamon 2009, p 101 ff).

The internet has changed many areas of life; it is already part of everyday life

²⁰ In the Duden, Internet as a noun, neuter = worldwide network of computers and computer networks in which special services (such as e-mail, World Wide Web, telephony) are offered. (<https://www.duden.de/suchen/dudenonline/internet>, S 1 ff); <https://dewikipedia.org/wiki/internet>, p 1

²¹ In the pre-digital age, the public sphere was often understood as the shared physical presence of people in one place. The public sphere legitimises social action through participation and so-called eye-witnessing. Schlögl calls this the "face-to-face society". Through digitalisation, however, the concept of the public sphere has changed significantly (Schlögl 2008, p 155 ff).

in many cases. The internet has also changed teaching. These changes in detail are also of interest to researchers. The Allensbach Study, for example, has already produced very interesting results, clearly demonstrating how the internet is changing areas of life and politics.²²

b) Possible advantages and disadvantages of using the internet

User behaviour, especially in everyday life, is also becoming increasingly intensive. However, it should also be noted that being "online" for a long time can lead to difficulties in real life. Here, in particular, the distinction between the "real" and the "virtual" world with potential dangers. Negative changes in people's behaviour must be recognised in time, as countermeasures might have to be taken in this respect. Face-to-face communication remains indispensable. Physical social contacts are absolutely necessary in people's lives, especially to ensure psychosocial health (Politische Bildung und Neue Medien 2015, p 5).²³

During my own teaching activities in higher education, I have been able to identify both disadvantages and advantages of Internet use by students. The advantages include, for example, the immediate availability of information for teaching, current publications (e.g. papers etc.) in the context of the subject such as history and political education (Zeilner, 2020), to a limited extent also (foreign language) online services, the creation of one's own content, especially with theoretically worldwide communication possibilities. Chat forums, for example, are very up-to-date, as is communication by e-mail. The disadvantages of using the

²² Media use has also changed and continues to change, especially through digital media. Digital media determine everyday life; Generation Z basically no longer knows life "offline" or without being available everywhere and to everyone immediately and everywhere. The digital revolution of the media world with all its facets has changed media usage behaviour considerably, to which the internet has also contributed significantly (<https://www.smart-pr.de/news/3192-mediennutzung>>Mediennutzung im Wandel: 2009 vs 2019/Smart/PR, p 1 ff); <https://www.welt.de/deutschland>, Allensbach Studie

²³ The first indications are, for example, the neglect of social contacts, the deterioration of school performance, etc. Counteracting this means (again) more of the real world for those affected, for example experiencing nature, exercise and sports, etc. The topic of "grounding" is more topical than ever (Zeilner Unterrichtsvorbereitung Geschichte und politische Bildung 2014; cf. also landoberoesterreich.gv.at/32184.htm).

internet in an educational context certainly include the flood of information, the sometimes difficult evaluation of content (quality, fake news, etc.), legal questions of internet use, etc. Educators, pupils and students use the internet not only in the context of teaching but also in the "private sphere", which can also be relevant for the acquisition of knowledge. The topic of Internet use in the school sector must be viewed in a very differentiated way, as there are major differences with regard to the possibilities of use, the prior knowledge of learners, etc. (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

c) The evaluation of information from the internet

A certain level of due diligence is necessary for teachers, pupils and students when evaluating information on the internet. An evaluation that determines the quality of an article, paper, etc. is certainly necessary in the context of teaching. Scientists publish their research results, for example, in a "paper" or scientific article, which is basically associated with a certain quality. Such articles are also published in specialist journals and verified by experts or scientists in the field before publication. An important criterion is also whether extreme views are represented in an article or not. For example, democratic values or their violation are an indicator of this. In addition, the comprehensibility of the information, for example, correct citing, arguments, justifications, etc., are of crucial importance. In addition to papers, other contributions, pictures, videos, etc. are also suitable for teaching. Provided that the students' level of proficiency is appropriate, the emergence or continuation of a discourse would- be one of the possible teaching objectives. The selection and preparation of contents and the preparation of the students before using them in class is an important task of the teacher (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

1.2.6 Communication

Communication is a process of transferring information. Communication (in Latin: "communicatio" = "communication") is the exchange or transmission of information, which can take place in different ways (verbal, non-verbal and paraverbal) and in different ways (by speaking, by writing). In the present day, computer-aided communication in particular is also very essential (Merten 1999, p 76

ff; cf. also article Social Bookmarks).

Communication is a process of transmitting messages between a sender and one or more recipients. In a narrower sense, communication is the exchange of messages or information between specific individuals. Here, language as well as body language (non-verbal communication), such as facial expressions, gestures, eye contact, etc. are used as communication channels. In the field of scientific analysis, the communicating persons are often referred to as communicator and recipient. Semiotics" is an abstract approach for the analysis of communication and sign processes.²⁴

Communication in the context of digital media and school lessons or online communication in the classroom affects, in particular, also the media use and media competence. Communicating with digital media is a basic skill in the age of globalisation. It is therefore the school's responsibility to promote digital forms of communication and to support pupils in acquiring the corresponding media competence.²⁵

1.2.7 Medium or media

a) Definition and meaning

In Latin, "medium" means the middle or centre. In the field of current sciences or communication, a medium is basically a mediator, a set of instruments for mediation. It is understood here, as it is in everyday language, as a means of communication. In media studies, different concepts and objectives have developed

²⁴ Semiotics (sign theory) deals with sign systems of all kinds. For example, language, pictorial writing, gestures, etc. (<https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semiotics>, p 1); <https://wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de>, p 1 ff

²⁵ Students should learn to communicate using different digital communication tools and to select them according to the situation. The KMK competence area "Communicating and Cooperating" also specifies that learners use digital tools for collaboration. For example, that they work together on documents, merge data, etc. with the help of digital tools. There are also interesting thematic dossiers for specific subjects here (<https://www.lehrer-online.de/dossier/Online-Kommunikation> im Unterricht, p 1 ff).

in the context of media²⁶ (Brockmeier 2010, p 15 ff; see also Lambert 2009, p 122 ff).

However, media are by no means understood as arbitrary communication phenomena and/or communication aids, but rather as social institutions that have established themselves over the long term following generally widespread acceptance. It can be plausible and beneficial to think of media as institutions and to work with new institutionalist theoretical approaches in communication studies (Zpart.nomos.de, Medien als Institutionen und ihre Auswirkungen auf Organisationen, p 1 ff).

Media are necessary for the acquisition of knowledge; in the present, digital media already serve this purpose to a considerable extent. However, the term (digital) media is not uniformly defined. The transmission of information is always essential; it is encoded on the basis of a sign system (language, images, music, numbers, etc.) (Kerres 2013, p 54).

b) No uniform definition for medium

There is no uniform definition for medium. However, there are several definitions, which are basically also subject to the liking of a user (Mock 2006, p 183 ff).

The fact that there is as yet no uniform definition for the term "medium" is also emphasised, for example, by Markus Lernen in his publication "Digitale Medien in der Lehrerbildung". It is a cultural-anthropological, communication science, psychological, cultural science, theatre science, pedagogical, philosophical, sociological, economic and semiotic perspective (Lernen 2008, p 214).

What is clear, however, is that a medium makes communication possible in the first place. One may differentiate between several dimensions of the concept of media. There are media as a form of communication, the physical concept of media (media as a means of perception), the semiotic concept of media (media as a means of communication) and the technical concept of media (media as a means of

²⁶ According to Dietrich Kerlen, "medium" denotes the middle (Latin), i.e. something that exists "in medio", in the middle of two objects that relate to each other. Therefore, a medium is a formative content carrier between producer and recipient (Kerlen 2003, p 9).

dissemination) (Mock 2006, p 183 ff).

c) Broad and technical concept of media

Broad concept of media:

The distinction between the broad and the technical concept of media, which is common in media theory, is also relevant for specific research. The broad concept of media also includes the human being himself; he is a personal medium. In addition, his language, gestures, facial expressions, posture, etc. are also included. MacLuhan's assumption in the context of the broad concept of media is that a medium is a comprehensive, revealing instance in which people behave. Media are mediators between people and their environment. Communication includes a media component (Stiehler 2005, p 305).

Technical concept of media:

The technical concept of media can be explained on the basis of three aspects:

1. The technical aspect: this is the instrumental component and the specific statement or information by means of the medium. In the context of education, educators as well as all other users must master the technology of the field.

2. The semantic aspect: these are the contents and their media design. Educators and students, as well as all other users, must be able to understand the content conveyed.

3. The pragmatic aspect: this means the exchange and dissemination of information, the intentions of the designers and the interests of the users. Students and educators, like all other users, need to be able to use media well for their own communication (Foc.geomedienlabor.de, sidebar: AB02-1).

d) Medium and media culture

The concept of the medium also developed into a specific concept of cultural studies around the mid-1980s and defined the concept of media culture. In modern communication and media research, the academic research increasingly focusses on

the mediatisation of culture. What is essential here is to assess how culture is permeated and shaped by media. An interrelationship of cultural change and media and communication change is assumed (Hepp 2013, p 27 ff).

If the diverse forms of human medialisation are not only perceived as subjective expressions, but also as elements of a supra-individual discourse about human beings, they become scientifically tangible as constitutive elements of media cultures. Here, media cultures are in simple terms understood as a functional totality of medium, media production, media use and allocation of meaning. They are culturally specific, historically changeable and the product of a discursive process. Viewed in a historical longitudinal section, they are renegotiated again and again. Changes in media culture are often based on significant cultural paradigm shifts. One example is digitalisation (Tschiggerl et al 2018, p 88).

e) The functions of media

Information, opinion forming and decision-making:

The media have for a long time had important functions in democratically constituted societies. First and foremost, they provide information, but they should also create a public sphere that is as plural as possible and thus contribute to the opinion forming and decision-making. It is the task of media policy to create the framework conditions, which must, however, not exert any influence on the content.²⁷

Media: The fourth power in the state:

The media fulfil essential or fundamental functions in democratic states. First and foremost, they are supposed to inform the people, contribute to the formation of opinion through criticism and discussion and thereby promote (political) participation. For many years, the media have commonly been referred to as the fourth power in the state. This is an informal term for the public media, such as the press, broadcasting, etc. "Fourth power" here means that there is a fourth, a virtual pillar in a system of separation of powers. However, this topic has to be properly

²⁷ In some countries, for example in Germany, media policy is mainly limited to broadcasting policy. Basically, there are many content-related issues in this area, which have become much more since the spread of the internet (<https://www.hsozkult.de/journal/id/zeitschriftenausgaben>, p 1).

prepared and explained to pupils and students because equating it with the three classic powers of the state is fundamentally problematic (M.bpb.de, Medien - die "vierte Gewalt?", p 1 f).

f) Medium: Definition in the Media Act

According to Section 1 of the Media Act, a medium is "any means of disseminating information or performances with intellectual content in speech, writing, sound or images to a larger group of persons by means of mass production or mass distribution" (Section 1 Mediengesetz).

g) Digital media

"Digital media are information carriers based on binary coding, i.e. their original character set can only represent two discrete states". More complex information is represented by a combination of these two characters. "Digital media" are often "electronic media".²⁸

The term "digital media" is used synonymously with the terms "digital media" and "new media". Ratzke, for example, defines "new media" as all processes and media (means) that enable information with the help of new (renewed) (information) technologies. This includes information acquisition, information processing, information transmission, information storage and information retrieval (Ratzke 1982, p 14).

From the point of view of media education, "new media" basically include all microelectronic or digital media in addition to the computer. In everyday language, "new media" is understood to mean digital and computer-based media (Speck-Hamdan et al 1998, p 13).²⁹

²⁸ Digital media are sometimes also referred to as computer media. It is understood to mean electronic media that are digitally encoded. The term "digital media" is also used synonymously for "new media". The contrast to this is "analogue media" ([https://joernlengsfeld.com/definition Digitale Medien](https://joernlengsfeld.com/definition-Digitale-Medien), p 1).

²⁹ In teaching practice or in the school sector, new media are primarily understood to mean the computer and the Internet or the World Wide Web (www). The so-called traditional or old media are still available. These are textbooks, overhead projectors and overhead transparencies, the blackboard, videos, etc. (Zeilner, 2011).

Such media have been relevant in education and in the classroom for some time. For example, educators with tablet computers and online access have many possibilities for teaching. This can also be seen as a new age of education. In principle, digital media can act as a learning accelerator if used correctly. Digital media are also means to positively influence learning processes (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Digital media should primarily be seen as a means of positively influencing learning processes, here in particular to increase the efficiency or effectiveness of teaching. This concerns both the learning of the students and the teaching of the educators (Muth 1976, p 234).

Teaching media are means for shaping learning processes and for communication; digital media are already of great importance in this context. They are also of considerable relevance in everyday life, this is especially noteworthy for media literacy because fundamentally different preconditions are to be assumed; this also concerns the specific school (Köck 2005, p 361 ff).³⁰

The use of (digital) teaching media is basically very specific. In addition to the prerequisites already mentioned, the topic of the lesson, the goals of the lesson, the interests of the pupils, etc. are also important. In addition, the selection and preparation of the teaching media by the teachers is important. This also involves a certain amount of preparation time as well as skills and motivation³¹ (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Digital media also enable new approaches to learning. This is essential in didactic and methodological considerations, especially for media literacy. Digital

³⁰ In the field of education, the concept of media should be defined very broadly; the characteristics of (digital) media are also essential in this context. The foundation for media literacy should already be laid in elementary education (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

³¹(Digital) Media can play a decisive role both as a teaching tool and as a teaching subject. In other words, this is "learning with digital media" and "learning about digital media". As teaching aids, they contribute in particular to the optimal organisation of lessons. The different possibilities of use and subject-didactic selection criteria are noteworthy here. For educators, this means the necessity of a combined technological, pedagogical and subject knowledge. Teacher training programmes at universities and teacher training colleges in Austria already take this into account (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

media are not only tools, but also "digital actors". This must be clearly pointed out to pupils and students in the context of teaching (Bpb.de, Medienpädagogik, p 1).

New learning approaches require well-trained and motivated educators. Learning with and for digitalisation or in the context of digital media means primarily explaining knowledge acquired independently, discussing it in a team, practising it and also implementing it or paying attention to results. This is a completely new "mindset" and requires an overall plan for implementation in the education system that encompasses all aspects of education. Traditional teaching can be improved and complemented by digital media. In the education sector, digitalisation opens up new opportunities for both learners and teachers. However, this must be viewed in a very differentiated way.³² (Hellmuth 2016, p 1 ff).

Pupils and students are now more intensively involved in the lessons, which are basically also made more illustrative. In addition, creative skills of the learners are also promoted. The development of own (digital) media products is an important example here. Digital media that are suitable for teaching and can be obtained rather easily, quickly and conveniently, are of fundamental importance for educators. Cooperation between the actors, best practice examples, etc. is certainly beneficial in this context (Bovet/Huwendick 2008, p 170).

It can be assumed, however, that educators are only little aware of how pupils use digital media - especially in the form of social media - in different contexts. The interactivity of games, for example, allows users to directly participate in political events and also to (re)interpret them. Students can also produce and publish political (historical, etc.) content for a large audience, e.g. on YouTube, etc., on their own responsibility. This also opens up an interesting field of research (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

³² An example from teaching practice is "Erinnern.at", where the repertoire has been expanded to include digital learning materials such as learning apps, videos, online toolboxes, etc. The repertoire can be used for individual or group learning. Here, pupils can learn individually or in groups. Digital media offer many possibilities for political education, for "historical" and "modern political education" (www.erinnern.at).

h) Teaching media

- The context of teaching

In the context of teaching, media are referred to as "instructional media"; here they are a means of communication (medium) used in teaching for didactic purposes. Here, they are - just like methods - instruments to achieve teaching goals. In principle, they help to evoke parallel learning processes of pupils and can act as multipliers (Martial/Bennack 2004, p 1 ff).

The most important teaching media are pictures, texts (texts in didactic form, e.g. textbooks, texts to be prepared by oneself), e-books, worksheets, blackboard, flipchart, etc., film, television and sound media, newspapers, magazines, computers and the Internet. Digital media are of particular relevance in this research. Texts should be designed in a learner-friendly way, in order to improve the understanding of a topic and to promote retention. The computer basically provides pupils, students etc. basically with a powerful medium.³³

Texts should be designed in a learner-friendly way, which improves the understanding of a topic and promotes memory retention. With the computer, pupils, students etc. basically have a powerful medium at their disposal.

Above all, the computer also enables various forms of interaction in the context of teaching. For use in everyday school life, the application forms of learning software, digital lexicons and the Internet are particularly topical (Kühne Steve/Gütter Liliane Anna/Handke Janette/Schrader Christine, Medien in der Schule).

³³ Digital media are media in electronic or digital form and are based on information and communication technologies. The extent to which they will replace analogue media such as books, television, radio, the legendary blackboard, newspapers, etc. is under discussion. The digital media that are very important for education are the e-book, social media, smartphones and tablets, computer games, digital radio, digital video/video portals, etc.; http://www.lsvmv.de/news_2016/medien_im_unterricht.pdf, p 1 ff (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Table 1: “Forms of use of computer & internet in everyday school life”

Brockhaus digital
Compiling of knowledge
Linking to tasks on which students receive feedback
Various implementations (images, sound, text, animation)
Similar to lexicons in book form but digital
Often accessible information available (images, sounds)
Project realization with remote partners
Information search
Compiling of knowledge, presentation in the net
Retrieval of learning programmes

(Source: Kühne et al.)

- Digital teaching media:

In the context of schools, (digital) media should accompany or support learning processes. This also means not only consuming media education/media didactics and communication, but being active as a shaper in the educational and media landscape (Medienbegleitung.com, p 1ff).

Media didactics is a helpful basis for activities as well as for co-decisions. The potentials of digital media in lessons or in learning and teaching processes shall be identified with its help. Among other things, the existing media spectrum as well as problems and issues related to the psychology of learning and perception are essential, as are relevant information technologies (IT). A well-functioning permanent exchange of information between the actors in the context of production and application of digital teaching media is essential in this context. The resulting findings and best practice examples should be used as a decision-making aid. In addition, a further scientific discourse could emerge in the form of a "science

circle".³⁴ (Hüther 2005, p 239; vgl. auch de Witt 2006).

For educators, basics in the context of digital media in the classroom are also fundamentally important. Examples thereof are:

1. Pupils are personalities: Due to the social and cultural diversity of students, it is necessary to make education more individual.
2. Learning process: It is beneficial for pupils and teachers if the individual learning progress can be tracked precisely.
3. Modular teaching: supported by the possibility of targeted selection of learning modules and teaching material.
4. Flexible choice of location for learning: Digital media connect learning in and out of the classroom and help to compensate for disadvantages in terms of the access to education.
5. Collaborative learning: online platforms allow students to work together on homework and share ideas from home. Experts call this "collaborative learning".
6. Lessons should be practice-oriented and stimulating: Digital media help to make lessons in many subjects more lively, practical and interesting.
7. Presenting complex contexts in an easily understandable way: Realistic digital simulations in the classroom help to better convey complex content that could previously only be dealt with in abstract terms (Benq.eu, Education, p 1 ff).

Digital competence areas:

"The curriculum for basic digital education combines digital and computer literacy with media literacy and socio-political competences"

³⁴ According to Heike Schaumburg et al, digital media can influence important functions in the classroom. These are the functions of motivating, presenting, activating and deepening, individualising and differentiating as well as communicating and cooperating (Schaumburg et al 2019, p 174)..

Figure 1: Digital competence areas

Source: Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort

In addition to the stated examples of basics in the teaching context, basics on visual and audio-visual media in the classroom are of vital importance educators, because they are already fundamentally relevant. Visual media are "texts that either consist purely of still images or in which still images represent a constitutive string of characters. Audio-visual media are media that address the visual and auditory senses (eyes and ears) simultaneously. They are synchronous technical means of communication that engage the visual and auditory senses of humans through sound and image. AV media can be both analogue (e.g. a VHS videotape) and digital (e.g. an MPEG-encoded video). In certain contexts, multimedia online services are also classified as audio-visual media. Historically, they emerged from the media convergence of image projection and sound storage towards the end of the 1920s³⁵ (Bentele et al 2013, p 21 f).

³⁵ In the field of education or in the context of school, visual and also audiovisual media have been used for a long time. It started with school radio, then there was also school television; in the present visual and audiovisual media are very current (Hagemann 1978, p 26).

Educators have many possibilities to use visual and audio-visual media in the classroom. Interest, IT knowledge, the organisational effort, above all the (technical) equipment of the school, type of school, school level etc. basically rank among the key factors for their use in lessons. Ultimately, the teachers decide autonomously; they must also integrate these media in the context of the lessons in a well-considered way. Even though the selection and preparation is very important here, the effects and effectiveness in lessons are controversially discussed³⁶ (Strittmatter 2000, p 1 ff).

Educators have many opportunities to use audio-visual media in lessons, the selection and preparation of which is always essential. In many cases, audio-visual media were and are used as "enrichment", i.e. to brighten up and enliven the lessons. Educators retreated behind the audio-visual medium, but they had the chance to master it (Hagemann 1978, p 3).

In historical retrospect, the emergence of mass media brought about a change in emphasis in the use of audio-visual media. In the context of media education, the (digital) media themselves now became teaching content. The topic of "media effects", for example, was of considerable importance to learners in this context (Hagemann 1978, p 61).

Criteria for the use of audio-visual media in teaching according to Wolfgang Protzner:

- Originality: This means that information should be changed as little as possible so that pupils have authentic access to the facts or materials. This is very important because of the possibilities of manipulation in the context of (digital) media.

- The target group-appropriateness: This means that it should be ensured that the "abilities of the users of the media are neither over- nor under-challenged". The individual level of proficiency or knowledge is important here.

³⁶ In the context of education and schools, audiovisual media have been very current for a long time; they are particularly useful tools for educators. They enable a simultaneous linguistic and visual presentation of facts. Facts can be presented in their entire complexity or in a simplified form. Basically, audiovisual presentations are more interesting, they stimulate the interest of pupils and students and thus also their attention (Strittmatter 2000, p 85)..

- Topicality: This means that only the latest or most up-to-date information on a topic or issue is selected. In principle, this enables an optimal gain of knowledge (Protzner 1977, p 92 ff).

Protzner's criteria are a good guideline. Selection, preparation and implementation are very important, which I can justify through my own teaching experience of many years. Some students at secondary schools and BMHS were already "digital natives" (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

i) Changes through development steps

Changes can also be seen in particular in the development steps from Innovation/Learning 1.0 to the current Innovation/Learning 4.0. In the context of competence research, it is essential for Learning 4.0 that it is based on self-development or personal responsibility, stable relationship networks, goal-oriented collaboration and intensive reflection. It basically leads to the acquisition of knowledge and the enhancement of competences through certain learning methods. Learning in practice and in exchange with other people is particularly essential here (Lang 2018, p 1 ff).

With regard to personal responsibility, learning is increasingly integrated into the work context in order to achieve more sustainability. Self-development is important here, i.e. people must take responsibility for maintaining and expanding the necessary competences and make use of educational opportunities on their own initiative. This should already be taken into account in school education, as it affects the transition from school to working life and the future of students ³⁷ (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 10).

³⁷ Innovation 4.0 is essential for the education sector and for the world of employment; here, cooperation with the company's human resources development department is indispensable. People should be able to decide or co-decide what they want to learn and when. Entrepreneurial thinking and action is also important here. In the overall context, Learning 4.0 means a gradual dissolution of the boundaries between the field of work and the learning environment. Above all, learning will predominantly take place informally at the workplace alone or together with other employees or other persons, i.e. in the form of face-to-face seminars. In addition, digital media are or will become very important for learning (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 10).

j) (Digital) media in the context of teaching

- Didactical structure:

Didactics deals with the effectiveness of teaching and places an emphasis on teaching and learning processes. Digital media influence this process; they are already standard in many modern school lessons. Application orientation, flexible design of teaching and learning processes, etc. are very relevant in this context. Digital media can in principle bring benefits, but this does not come about through their use alone. Arrangements drawing on media didactics are required; they can lead to positive results in the context of teaching. Fundamental questions here are, for example, "How is the message or subject matter conveyed?" "Is it done through frontal teaching?", "In the form of group work?", etc. (Wb-web.de, Mediendidaktik, p 1 f).

- Possibilities for action:

With regard to the possibilities for action, an essential question is: "What can teachers and/or learners do with the (digital) medium? Basically, teachers should accompany pupils in the competent use of their media, raise their awareness of risk aspects, provide them with possibilities for action and encourage them to use media creatively for their own purposes. For example, possibilities of changing the media on offe, such as media selection, slowing down videos, stopping them, etc. are also indispensable in teaching practice. (Fsm.de, Medien in der Schule - Materialien und Beispiele, p 1 ff).

- Symbol systems:

When educators and pupils communicate with each other, they become senders and recipients. The sender wants to communicate something, for example factual information. Here the question is: "How is the message encoded?". In the context of teaching, for example, through spoken language, a text, through images or illustrations, through a combination of several symbol systems, etc. Language, writing or body signals "transport" the message to the receiver, a signal is sent. The receiver has to decode the signal. The recipient can react to the message that has been sent and become a sender himself only after he has "cracked" the code and

interpreted the message.³⁸

- Digital media and motivation

Digital media or digital technologies have changed and are changing people's lives to a considerable extent. In the present day, there are hardly any educational and work processes without the use of digital technologies. In particular, digital and IT skills are necessary for teachers, pupils and students to participate in many areas of society. This fact has already been recognised in teacher training and in the context of teacher training programmes at universities and teacher training colleges in Austria. Above all, the motivation of pupils and students can be improved with the "right" approach, (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

However, the topic of digital media and motivation must be viewed in a very differentiated way. This raises, in particular, the question "Do digital media improve teaching and increase motivation to learn?" There are already interesting scientific studies on this, such as the one by the Technical University of Munich. Almost eighty (80) studies on this topic were examined and evaluated. The main outcome is that there is an improvement in performance compared to classes that are taught conventionally and without digital media. However, it is clearly demonstrated that digital media per se (or alone) do not guarantee learning success (Digitale-schule Blog, Lernerfolg durch digitale Medien, p1 ff).

Markus Deimann (TU-Ilmenau) also obtains valuable results in his research "Motivational Conditions in Learning with New Media". Motivation is of increasing importance here for successful teaching and learning processes. However, motivational conditions in learning with "new media" or "digital media", including the underlying theoretical considerations, are not sufficiently taken into consideration - in the context of education. Deimann referred to the research programme outlined

³⁸ Communication can take place by different means. These include verbal communication (speech, the spoken/written word), paraverbal communication (type of articulation, the range of the voice, e.g. vocal spectrum, volume, speed of speech, etc.), non-verbal communication, gestures (movements outside the face, e.g. shrugging the shoulders, etc.), facial expressions (movements in the face, e.g. laughing, blinking the eyes, etc.), as well as posture and movements in space ((https://www.br.de/facher/deutsch/Kommunikation_und_SPRACHE. Sender-receiver model - BR, p 1 ff).

by Brünken and Leutner (2000) as an example. He first focussed on selected "old" media, in order to (re)gain awareness of existing findings and to be able to integrate them into discussions about motivational conditions in learning with digital media. New media offer above all the possibility of interactivity. This correlates with effects on motivation, which can be clarified through correct feedback. Feedback to learners should be as neutral and informative as possible, social standards of comparison should be avoided. According to the author, well-chosen and prepared multimedia learning offers are very well suited to promote interest and motivation to learn (Deimann 2002, p 61 ff).

k) The views of Bovet, Huwendick and Hüther

According to Gislinde Bovet and Volker Huwendick, teaching media are "all those aids (...) that are used as a substitute for experience or as a substitute for reality in the classroom (Bovet/Huwendick 2008, p 170).

Hüther additionally integrates the improvement aspect in the definition of media in the context of education or in the pedagogical context by considering media "as the totality of technical aids (...) that serve in a didactically planned way to improve teaching and learning situations" (Hüther 2005, p 234).

1.2.8 Medialisation / Mediatisation

Medialisation describes a certain form of media effects that are supra-individual, long-term and indirect (Kepplinger 2008). Medialisation means the appropriation through media or the exploitation of media, e.g. "medialisation of teaching" or "medialisation of politics", etc. It is a theoretical approach in communication studies that explains changes in social spheres by the fact that communication is increasingly oriented towards the time horizons, selection rules and role specifications of the media (Wikipedia, Wiki, p 1; see also Unifr.ch, Dohle_Vowe_Wodke.pdf, p 1 ff).

This means "medialisation of communicative action" with necessary adaptation measures and the increase in importance of media (Marcinkowski/Steiner 2010).

1.2.9 Media education / Media competence

a) Media education

"Media education aims at a self-determined and responsible use of media. Media literacy enables the well-founded reflection and creative design of media (Bundesverband-medienbildung.at, p 1 ff).

In the field of educational sciences, media education is in principle understood as a lifelong educational process that takes place in different contexts or fields of socialisation. Apart from the context of school lessons, especially in the family, the circle of friends, etc. where an active and reflective engagement with (digital) media can promote media interest and media literacy. "Media literacy" is an essential educational goal, "media education" the (lifelong) development process for this competence (Tulodziecki 2012, p 1 ff).

Media literacy is essential for the entire lifetime. The proper use of (digital) media is especially essential in the context of school teaching. According to important educators, however, textbooks will not disappear as a result. Digital media are particularly suited for concise information; a differentiated view of content must be prepared very well (Hellmuth 2016, p 1 ff).

Media literacy is essential during school life and beyond, i.e. for the entire future life. Media have a significant role in and outside the school environment, and this continues for the time after school life. Achieving media literacy in the classroom is therefore of great importance ³⁹ (Klafki 1991, p 49 ff).

Our society has already developed into a "media society", which is why "media education" in particular is essential for the education sector. Pupils or students are to be promoted in order to be able to cope with the current demands confidently and with the necessary skills. This relates in particular to all skills in the context of information technologies. This means, among other things, a sensible, reflected and responsible use of (digital) media. In addition, a well-considered and

³⁹ The importance of media literacy should be indicated to students. Especially in history and political education, the fact that politics and media are in a permanent field of tension should be pointed out to students (Hellmuth/Klepp 2010, p M3; cf. also Hellmuth 2009 Media and Power).

prepared selection of media. Media competence is a "conditio sine qua non" in this context ⁴⁰ (D&E Heft 74 2017).

Media competence in the context of media education is a substantial goal of modern teaching. A powerful internet connection, a school network, technical equipment, technical infrastructure, etc. are required in addition to media-literate teachers. Good planning and the involvement of all the necessary actors are required in order to ensure that the technology or information technology can be adapted to the specific requirements of a school. This also requires cooperation and coordination (D&E Heft 74 2017).

Knowledge of operating systems or web-based browsers is also beneficial for educators. Web-based means that the use is independent of the operating system of the end device (e.g. PC, tablet, etc.) and offers advantages for pupils who have end devices with different operating systems. Basics in the context of media didactics are very important for educators in modern school teaching ⁴¹ (Schulbistum.de, Basics Mediendidaktik, p 1 ff).

Media didactics is another essential field for achieving goals in the context of media education. Media-literate pupils should be able to use media in a self-efficacious, critical and reflective way and to assess the associated opportunities and risks. Basics on behavioural rules and legal principles are already necessary in this context. An important legal basis is the "Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung". Achieving media competence is an essential goal of media education (Bmbwf.gv.at, Prinz, p 1 ff; cf. also "Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung").

Media literacy makes it possible to reflect on different interests and also leads

⁴⁰ Media training must be taught as part of an integrated whole subject. Basics here are the areas of analysis, information, communication, media society, presentation, production, reflection, personal rights, copyright, licensing law, data protection etc. In addition, information technology basics are essential (D&E Heft 74 2017).

⁴¹ Due to their potential multi-functionality, digital media can fundamentally individualise, promote self-organised learning, encourage teamwork, etc. There are different areas of application in this context. For history and politics lessons, for example, the simulation and interaction of social or economic processes, political planning games, WebQuests, etc. are topical (<https://www.schulbistum.de>basics mediendidaktik>, p 1 ff).

to an awareness that (political) judgement is often formed via the media. In addition, it promotes the shaping of media content and opportunities for (political) participation.⁴²

If one follows the research results on the topic of media education in schools, it can be seen that they are controversial. However, the majority of them (still) show the existence of shortcomings, and this also applies to the school sector in Austria. I could see this myself as an educator in the BMHS sector and also through discussions with educators - also in other types of schools (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

b) Media education in Austria

Media education is "...dedicated to the established media cultures and reflects the continuously changing media worlds. Media education is understood as personality formation, as a process and as the result of the mediation process of the world and self through media". ⁴³ (bmbwf).

Media literacy, a "key competence", is necessary for the selection of media, the critical evaluation of content and information as well as for communication in media. In the present, media literacy is also necessary to fully exploit the potential of the Internet (bmbwf).

Media education is also essential for critically questioning, responsible and constructive media use. Media education can also contribute to the recognition of negative media content. Here, the topic of opinion formation and (possible) manipulation in social networks etc. as well as sensitisation in this regard is of vital

⁴² On the topic of school media education or media competence, the Pädagogische Hochschule Wien, for example, has introduced a university course entitled "Digital Media Education in Primary Education". The target group consists of teachers who have completed their teacher training at the primary level or have completed their training at the elementary level. This course imparts school media education in the context of scientific-theoretical concepts, conveys the socio-cultural relevance, etc. and gives suggestions such as for the (further) development of one's own media competences ([https:// phwien. ac.at>hoerschullehrgaenge](https://phwien.ac.at/hoerschullehrgaenge), p 1); [https:// www. bmbwf.gv.at>prinz](https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/prinz), p 1 ff; cf. also "Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung"

⁴³ The essential areas which media education comprises are critical and creative thinking as well as the resulting action. Media literacy refers to the ability to use digital media, to understand their contents and to critically question them (bmbwf).

importance. This means knowledge or basics for the actors (Medienbildung, Bildungsserver Wien)

c) Media literacy

Media literacy has been an essential goal in the context of media education content and actions for decades, especially since the emergence of action-oriented media education. The acquisition of media competence is significant in particular for the future professional life of pupils and students. Being able to deal competently with media content is also the basis for social participation and socialisation. It is of prime importance to question the origin, intention, etc. of news instead of simply accepting news as it is. This also includes political communication and the need for basic digital education⁴⁴ (Süss 2013, p 125).

Basic digital education already exists in the Austrian school system. One buzzword in this context, for example, is "network policy education". This also means political communication in the context of digital media with interesting and essential areas, such as democracy as a cooperative project, etc. Technical developments and different technologies are of current relevance in certain areas in the context of school teaching. Receiving and evaluating media content and results quickly and efficiently is essential in education. This also enables passive and also active (political) participation (Lpb.sachsen-anhalt.de, Politische Kommunikation im Kontext neuer Medien, p 1 f).

Educators should be able to create learning conditions for students that promote the development and advancement of their media literacy (Herzig 1997, p 39).

In any case, media literacy has been an essential goal in the context of media education since the 1970s. In the Anglo-American world, the term "media literacy" is already very current. Media education is predominantly understood as education for politically responsible citizens (Süss et al 2013, p 125).

⁴⁴ In teacher training in Germany, the term "media pedagogical competence" has become established in addition to or instead of the term "media competence". In this case through model experiments in the context of "new media and teacher training" (Tulodzieki et al 2012, p 271 ff).

In the field of science, there are various media literacy models, in which media literacy is precisely defined and the essential skills and competences are outlined. The models by Aufenanger and Baacke are among the best known. These models are also presented below (Süss et al 2013, p 122 ff).

1.2.10 Models of media literacy using the examples of Aufenanger and Baacke

a) Different media literacy models

In the field of science, the term media literacy is defined in different ways. This has also led to the development of different media literacy models, which, among other things, also point the skills and competences that are to be taught. For example, the model of the educationalist and media educator Stefan Aufenanger is of interest in this context. Aufenanger divides media competence into six dimensions: "Cognitive Dimension", "Action Dimension", "Moral Dimension", "Social Dimension", "Affective Dimension" and "Aesthetic Dimension", which in Aufenanger's opinion should all be seen as equally important (Aufenanger 2003, p 147 ff).

In addition to Aufenanger's model, Baacke's model is also very widespread in German-speaking countries. According to Baacke, media competence means "the ability to use all kinds of media for people's repertoire of communication and action in a way that actively appropriates the world" (Prof. Dieter Baacke).

Media literacy is an essential goal; the term has existed since the 1970s. Baacke's definition for the German-speaking world - as a model of communicative competence - is based on a model by Habermas. Media literacy is part of communicative competence ⁴⁵ (Süss et al 2013, p 122 ff).

b) The Baacke Model: Four Dimensions of Media Literacy

1st dimension: "Media criticism"

⁴⁵ In addition to the term media competence, the term "media literacy" is also in use. Media literacy has now also become relevant in areas of the European Union (EU). For example, through media literacy projects, EU citizens should participate more actively in EU processes (Süss et al 2013, p 125).

The ability to deal critically with media content (media criticism) requires media competence. This also means an analytical way of thinking and an analytical understanding of social processes; in addition, being reflexive, in this context also a clarification of the analysis and a reflection on social responsibility or ethical action.

2nd dimension: "Media studies"

In addition to the dimension of media criticism described above, information about media and media systems is also essential. In media studies, Baacke distinguishes between "knowledge about processes and structures" (informative), i.e. for example how journalists etc. work, and "knowledge about technical handling" (instrumental-qualificational).

3rd dimension: "Use of media"

In Baacke's view, media use requires to master media action both receptively as a user (use competence) and interactively as a provider.

4th dimension: "Media design"

Media design is an essential area of media literacy. This should be done in two ways - firstly innovatively, i.e. in the sense of changes and further developments of the media system, and secondly creatively, i.e. reaching beyond the limits of the communication routine⁴⁶ (Baacke 1997, p 1 ff).

1.2.11 Multimedia

The term multimedia refers to content and works that consist of several, often digital, media. For example, audio, video, text, photography, graphics, etc. However,

⁴⁶ Regarding this model by Baacke, dimensions one and two refer to the area of knowledge, dimensions three and four to active application. According to Baacke, the teaching of media competence is very essential in the field of media education. This enables media to be used passively and actively. This is much more than "just" operating media and is a learning process (Baacke 1997, p 98 f).

there is no uniform definition of "multimedia". The existence of different interaction possibilities is very essential here, and good knowledge is necessary for their use (Wikipedia.org, Multimedia, p 1 ff).

Although there is no uniform definition of multimedia, Klimsa's definition, for example, is very up-to-date. Here, "multimedia" means numerous hardware and software technologies such as audio, video, text, graphics, etc. In addition, interactivity, multitasking, parallelism, etc. also play an essential role. This is an aspect of integration and presentation of the multimedia concept, which is only concretised by the application of multimedia technology. The context of use and the functionality of multimedia are also decisive.⁴⁷ (Issing/Klimsa 2002, S 3 f).

In the context of education or teaching, pedagogical aspects are essential, in particular the assumption that the use of different media simplifies the knowledge absorption of content for learners because information is absorbed with different sensory organs. This also leads, for example, to the scientific question of the causal relationship between the learning effect and the amount of media, which is, however, controversially discussed. According to Bernd Weidenmann, this is a "naive sum theory" that lacks any empirical proof. This is open to discussion (Besthelp.at, Multimedia, p 1 ff).

1.2.12 Wikipedia

Wikipedia already plays an essential role in school lessons, and integrating this encyclopaedia into lessons is often a real situation for teachers which can enrich the lessons. For pupils and students, Wikipedia is already an encyclopaedic resource and thus an essential key to accessing knowledge; of course, this also applies to educators. However, its use in lessons in general and in political and history lessons is controversially discussed (Bpb.de, Wikipedia im Schulunterricht, p 1 f).

However, there is high demand for information and useful guidelines in the

⁴⁷ In this context, the existence of different opportunities for action plays an essential role. A rapid development took place due to the technical progress of digitalisation and the increasing performance of computers. (Issing/Klimsa 2002, p 3 f; cf. also <https://www.besthelp.at/lexicon/multimedia>, p 1 ff).

context of education. "Wikipedia im Bildungsbereich", a multidisciplinary portal covering both subjects and education, collects existing and yet to be developed resources and is also a forum for discussion and exchange. For educators, Wikipedia has become a constant everyday companion in two ways. Research on the net by educators often leads first to Wikipedia articles as a basis for information, and pupils' homework, presentations, etc. are often strongly related to Wikipedia.⁴⁸

1.2.13 World Wide Web (WWW)

The World Wide Web (www) was developed by Tim Berners-Lee in 1989 at CERN in Switzerland. It is a patent-free hypertext system that was published in 1991. In the 1990s it became the "killer application" of the Internet. The emergence of web browsers for graphical user interfaces (GUI) then accelerated digitalisation very significantly. The term "Web 2.0" is current, subsuming those aspects of the WWW that are characterised above all by their participatory, collaborative and open qualities (Agis-www.informatik.uni-hamburg.de, p 1 ff).

In the field of education, the WWW has been used for quite some time. The contents (texts, pictures, etc.) are stored by companies or private individuals as web pages on server computers. These web pages can then - as is generally possible - be retrieved by pupils and students with a browser programme (Internet Explorer, Mozilla, Opera) and will appear on their computer screen. Pupils and students can also be active on the WWW, i.e. they can create their own content and become creative. The idea of the Internet was and is also that people should build their own websites where they can pass on their knowledge to others. This idea was first raised at universities and found many followers (Helles-koepfchen.de, article 569, p 1).

⁴⁸ In school lessons, interest in learning can be promoted through audio-visual media or images. The use of historical and/or political images in co-curricular subjects is topical for educators and students, they basically enrich the lessons. Images are much more than illustrations of texts. The central messages of political campaigns are also conveyed on the image level (not only on the text level) (Liebhart 2020, p 1 ff); https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia_in_der_Schule, p 1 ff

Conclusions and recommendations from Chapter I

The selection and investigation of basic terms, definitions and scientific foundations in the research at hand was made by the author. For the time being, it was intended as a step to improve the "sharpness" or the "exactness" of the research in particular, this was already shown to be essential in the context of investigating the research literature and in areas of application. If one follows Popper's (1994) view, it is not the definition that determines the application of a term, but the use of the term determines what is called its "definition" or its "meaning". In principle, however, terms and definitions can have several meanings, and they cannot always be translated word by word from Anglo-American into German. Terms and definitions are also fundamentally subject to change over the course of time, which is why they must be viewed in contemporary understanding. The particularly central terms in the context of this research are "digitalisation" and "(digital) media", here in the context of education and schools, as well as "information technologies" and "communication". For the time being, "digitalisation" meant that machines were controlled with the help of digital software. The networking of software-controlled machines via the internet then created a completely different situation. Devices now communicate and also report back data. This also led to significant changes in the media landscape and also affects the education sector.

Concerning the term "medium", it can be stated that a medium is a necessary condition for all areas of communication, but that there is no uniform definition of it. According to Markus Lerner, a distinction can be made between cultural-anthropological, communication-scientific, psychological, cultural-scientific, theatre-scientific, pedagogical, philosophical, sociological, economic or semiotic perspective of media. Instructional media, however, represent a clear specification in the media context. According to Bovet and Huwendick, teaching media are "all those aids (...) that are used as a substitute for experience or as a substitute for reality in the classroom". Hüther additionally integrates the improvement aspect in the definition of media in the context of education by considering media "as the totality of technical aids (...) that serve in a didactically planned way to improve teaching and learning situations". In addition to the specification in the educational context, one can also

distinguish between several dimensions of the concept of media. These are media as a form of communication, the physical concept of media (media as a means of perception), the semiotic concept of media (media as a means of communication) and the technical concept of media (media as a means of dissemination).

Concerning the "digital media", which are of fundamental importance in the context of the present thesis, it can be stated that these have been available in Austria since the 1980s. Information could now be conveyed via "interfaces"; in addition to the distribution of information, users could now also become active themselves. This was also a significant development for the education sector. From about the mid-1980s, some teachers in Austria already had computers at school and also "home computers" at their disposal. The Commodore C64, for example, was a very up-to-date computer at that time. Around this time, the Internet began to gain importance. The Internet Protocol (IP) opened up a new standard for data transmission in computer networks. Since the beginning of the 1990s, it has been possible to use the World Wide Web (www). Consequently, the World Wide Web also gained increasing importance for the school sector. A significant cultural potential already existed from about the mid-1990s. Further technical developments took place from around the turn of the millennium (2001); moreover, the social networks that were essential for the school sector were also developed at that time. This was now the beginning of the "digital age", which also encompasses the education sector and here in particular requires information technologies, media education, media competence and adaptation measures on the part of the actors. This required from educators to have a good understanding of (among other things) the functions and developments in the context of digital media and teaching. The subject of "media education" is highly topical; it includes critical and creative thinking as well as the resulting action as essential areas. Media education is also understood here as personality development, and as a process and result of a mediation process. The achievement of "media literacy" - the ability to use digital media, to understand their contents and to critically scrutinise them – is of crucial importance in this context. Media literacy refers to analogue and digital media and is a key competence in the educational context. According to Baacke, media literacy, as part of communicative competence,

is a central element in the field of media education. Communicating one's own views and opinions is very essential for teachers and learners. It is a learning process and plays a decisive role in the field of education. The deciding factors include school levels, types of schools, existing technical prerequisites, training, interest and motivation of educators, etc. Implementation in practice - cooperation, coordination, best practice examples, etc. - is very important in this context. In any case, it requires good, interested and motivated educators with the willingness for training and further education. This is a necessary precondition for good teaching; it also enables, among other things, various forms of interaction in the context of teaching. Digital media should primarily be regarded as a means to positively influence learning processes, here especially to increase the efficiency of teaching. The use of digital media has already brought about significant changes. In principle, pupils and students are now more intensively involved in lessons. Lessons can basically also be organised more illustratively and thus promote the creative abilities of the learners. The development of own media products is an important example here. Digital media that are suitable for teaching and relatively easy, quick and uncomplicated to obtain are essential for educators. As far as digital learning methods are concerned, the selection of the practically innumerable offers is essential. Apps, massive open online courses (MOOCs), e-learning tools, etc. are very important here. Modern learning formats can basically influence the process of learning in a motivating and attractive way; they also enable learning via different sensory channels. In addition, "gamification" is also topical, whereby a transfer of game-typical elements and processes into a non-game context (learning environment) can take place. In the context of the education system, (digital) media should accompany or support learning processes. This also means not only consuming media education/media didactics and communication, but also being active as a shaper in the educational and media landscape. Here, a well-functioning permanent exchange of information between the actors in the context of production and use of digital teaching media is of crucial importance. Protzner takes the view here that the selection, preparation and implementation etc. are very important. In the context of teaching, this also means a self-determined and responsible dealing with media and enables the thorough reflection and creative

design of media. This requires "media competence", which is an essential educational goal; "media education" is the (lifelong) development process for this competence. From the point of view of the responsible Federal Ministry, media education "...addresses the established media cultures and reflects the constantly changing media worlds. Media education is understood as personality development, as a process and as the result of the mediation process through media". Media education includes critical and creative thinking as well as the resulting action as essential areas. Media literacy refers to the ability to use digital media, to understand their contents and to critically question them.

The term "media literacy" is defined in different ways, which is why different media literacy models have emerged. After examining several media literacy models, also in the context of the literature research, the models of Aufenanger and Baacke, in particular, can be seen as very common in the German-speaking world. Aufenanger differentiates between six dimensions: "Cognitive Dimension, Action Dimension, Moral Dimension, Social Dimension, Affective Dimension and Aesthetic Dimension", all of which are to be seen as equally important. According to Baacke, "media competence" requires different skills. Baacke's definition is based on Habermas's competence model for communicative action as part of communicative competence. Regarding this model by Baacke, the first and second dimensions refer to the knowledge area, while the third and fourth dimension concern the active application. According to Baacke, teaching media competence is the most important task in the field of media education; it is a learning task for all people. The encyclopaedia "Wikipedia" is also essential for educators, pupils and students; it is an encyclopaedic resource and thus essential in accessing knowledge. The World Wide Web (WWW) is also already of significance for educators, pupils and students, they can also be active here, e.g. create their own content. The idea of the internet was and is also that people should build their own websites on which they can pass on their knowledge to others. This idea was first raised at universities and is now relevant for school teaching, especially in the context of "digitalisation". Especially due to its complexity, this requires a good orientation, and in particular a definition of one's own position. The complexity and speed of change processes in the global and digital

world in general, especially in the context of digitalisation in the educational sector, requires adaptation measures on the part of teachers, pupils and students. It can be noted, among other things, that digitalisation - as a process - in the context of education was rather slow at the beginning. In this process, digital media are increasingly taking the place of analogue media, even though they have not yet completely replaced them. The relationship between digital media and analogue media must be considered in a differentiated way in the context of school lessons, and is also discussed very controversially. However, it is necessary to discuss and develop teaching media and "school digital" constructively and discursively. Changes in this respect are related to innovations and their implementation. The twentieth century was significant for developments in the context of digital media, especially concerning the computer and computer technology. As rapid developments in computer technology have taken place and continue to take place in the twenty-first century, the education and training of educators is very important in this context.

CHAPTER II. DIGITALITY AND DIGITALISATION IN AUSTRIA'S EDUCATION SYSTEM

2.1. Research on digitalisation (excerpt)

2.1.1. Digitalisation in the context of schools

The topic of digitalisation in the education system and in the context of schools in Austria has been very topical for quite some time. In the context of science and research, digitalisation also has the fundamental potential to change the research landscape. In the context of the digitalisation in many aspects of life, access to knowledge and information has been and will be significantly changed. The education and school sector – and especially the digital school development - is an essential aspect of life and research (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Staff development is, among other things, a key element in the context of digital school development. Educators and their participation are very important in this context. The necessary measures to support the integration of digital media in a way that promotes learning are referred to as pedagogical support, which is decisive for the digitalisation of school and teaching. However, shortcomings in the field of digitalisation in the education system or school are often identified in public discussions. This applies to the German education system, for example, but can also be observed in the Austrian education system. Support services for educators and the specific school itself are very important; this requires good support solutions with a far-sighted vision of the future. The emphasis should not only be placed on development opportunities but also on possible accompaniment with empirical research. The cooperation and coordination of the actors, especially the school authorities and the school is of fundamental importance⁴⁹ (Kaspar et al 2020, p 17).

School authorities must provide an up-to-date technical infrastructure in schools and suitable support solutions. In general, a distinction between the technical

⁴⁹ School authorities can support the digitisation of schools in three main areas. These are technical support, further training for teachers and joint concepts (Lorenz et al. 2020, in FRIEDRICH JAHRESHEFT XXXVIII 2020, p 32).

and pedagogical component of support has to be made in this context. These components must be conceived jointly and implemented in a coordinated manner (Lorenz et al. 2020, in FRIEDRICH ANNUAL XXXVIII 2020, p 32).

The term "technical support" refers to measures to ensure the technical functionality of digital media. The term "pedagogical support", on the other hand, includes interventions to support teaching and learning processes. The "first-level support" provided within the school is to be considered at the process level. In contrast, the externally provided "second-level support" can be seen as a prerequisite at the input level. This part is implemented by the school authorities or companies commissioned by them. However, pedagogical support - which is relevant for teaching processes - is only well organised in a few schools (Lorenz et al. 2020, in FRIEDRICH JAHRESHEFT XXXVIII 2020, p 32).

The subject of digitalisation in schools is topical in many respects and raises many questions. One essential question in this context is "How can the advancing digitalisation in schools be professionally supported and what role do the school authorities have in this?" A study on this question is also of particular interest. This study is based on media centres and interviews with fourteen (14) school authorities from different federal states in Germany who were interviewed for the study "Investigation of technical and pedagogical support at lower secondary schools in Germany". The research focus of the study was the perspective of the school boards (Lorenz et al. 2020, in FRIEDRICH JAHRESHEFT XXXVIII 2020, p 32).

This study examines the technical and pedagogical support and the relevant framework conditions. The results of the teacher survey indicate major shortcomings in various areas. This applies in particular to the provision of information technology (IT) which is adapted to the pedagogical requirements. Adequate IT equipment is a necessary or fundamental condition. In addition, the development and further development as well as specific responsibilities for tasks. From the teachers' point of view, designated contact persons as IT coordinators or teachers with a media background within the school as well as externally provided technical support are, in addition to adequate IT equipment, essential for school media work. The benefit of suitable further training offers for teachers was also demonstrated in the context of

this study (Study: Investigation of technical and pedagogical support at lower secondary schools in Germany 2017, p 9).

Independent of this study, statements from school authorities pointed out the necessity of professional support for successful digitalisation in schools. Among other things, cooperation between the actors, especially between the school authorities and the school, is of particular importance. Digitalisation must always have a conceptual basis. Personnel and financial resources are required due to the complex interrelationships and fundamentally existing comprehensive structures in the context of digitalisation in schools. Qualification measures at the level of the school authorities and the schools are also necessary. This study also leads to the fundamental conclusion that a well thought-out concept planned in the medium or long term, or a concept with foresight must take into account the resources and competences of all actors. Coordinated and cooperative further development is equally essential here (Lorenz et al. 2020, in FRIEDRICH JAHRESHEFT XXXVIII 2020, p 32).

Digitalisation imposes new tasks and adaptation measures not only on school authorities and schools, but also on the entire education system in the public and private sector. This also requires the integration of services from external companies, especially in the field of information technology (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Austria's education system must fundamentally change in order to keep up with rapid developments. This can occur on many levels; the understanding of large structures and interrelations, critical faculties, interpretation, etc. is therefore necessary (News.wko.at, Digitalisation of Education, p 1 ff).

These are major challenges for actors in the Austrian education system in the context of digitalisation. A fundamental question in this regard is "Is this education system able to prepare future generations for the challenges of a digitalised world? To this end, Austria has already taken essential steps such as the elaboration of an eight (8) point plan etc. (Digitalisierung.agenda-austria.at, p 1 ff).

On the basis of specific targets, the integration of computers and the Internet is also promoted. It is essential for educators to take into account the media

characteristics. Here, different types of programmes also determine different possibilities of use, which is why therefore one cannot speak of one or "the" effect of digital media or the computer on teaching. In addition to the medium itself, the educators, their motivation and adaptation measures - ideally together with their students - are of great importance. Media education as well as a willingness to coordinate and cooperate is necessary for all actors, also as far as the implementation of digital media in the classroom is concerned (Refubium-fu-berlin.de, chapter 3, p 37 ff).

2.1.2 Researching "digitality" or "digitalisation" in the school sector

Regarding the research of digitality or digitalisation in the school sector, it must first of all be noted that digitalisation is very resource-intensive. This applies above all to the acquisition costs of hardware and software, but also to the time capacities of the teachers. Sustainable school development in the digitalised world is a central focus of research. Quality and sustainability are regarded as essential success factors. In her article in the Friedrich Jahresheft 2020, Eickelmann shows, among other things, that previous research revealed three successful development perspectives that are presented below:

"Perspective 1: Integration of digitalisation processes and school development processes at the individual school level. Here, schools are particularly successful if they combine the innovation processes related to digitalisation at the individual school level with the pedagogical objectives and the specific situations and challenges. Here, developments are combined with other school challenges as well as innovations, and synergies are used in a targeted manner. The criticism here is that if processes are started independently of each other, this results in additional, sometimes contradictory, but in any case in disassociated work. The use of different working teams in schools that do not overlap to some extent is seen as ineffective. It is considered a challenge for schools to develop universal educational concepts and materials only in small steps. In this respect, schools are challenged to take action in their own interest and independent of support services. It is essential to make use of the scope for action at the level of the individual school.

"Perspective 2: Ensuring continuous personnel development". The dynamics of digitalisation is also reflected in the continuous training and further education of successful schools and school systems. However, continuing education and training in Austria still needs to be improved in this sector. However, there are also institutions that serve as role models for educators, such as some teacher training colleges, etc. Eickelmann takes the view that schools can make a big difference with small measures. Examples include mutual coaching systems, the embedding of brief presentations of settings and the application at pedagogical conferences, etc. As a result of all these measures, the schools will be able to optimally use their potentials and resources. This can also be based on the school-related parameters and the technical requirements or in the context of information technologies, etc. The potential of digitalisation can also be beneficial for other school development processes and professionalization processes (Eickelmann 2020, p 40 f).

"Perspective 3: Development and maintenance of sustainable cooperation structures. Co-operation not only within the school but also from outside the school can be efficiently applied as a resource for school development processes in the context of digitalisation. Cooperation in subject groups is, for example, particularly effective within the school. Networks, school observations, etc. are important across schools. It is necessary to optimally plan and establish cooperation structures, and this should also be done with a vision for the future. Many changes will occur due to - partially not yet foreseeable - developments, especially in the technical field or in the context of technology and ethics, that will require adaptation efforts on the part of the actors. The increasing importance of artificial intelligence (AI) and the related unpredictable developments will also become relevant in the field of education. This requires research in the context of several scientific fields, and in particular also cooperation, coordination and the ability of actors to work in teams with a vision of the future and responsibility for people. This should also be addressed by educators in the classroom (Eickelmann 2020, p 41).

The developments pointed out by the Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung on the topic of digitality may also be of interest to educators. In the context of heterogeneous interactions where language meets society, with a focus on school

education and the topic of "digitality", the following developments can be observed:

Firstly: in some cases, discourses in school educational media are subject to change. Above all, new and partially also different educational content is being offered by actors who did not or do not produce textbooks, but who are currently developing digital (teaching) materials of fundamentally good didactic, technical and aesthetic quality.

Secondly: education is changed by how digital educational media are used. This prioritises certain discourses and practices. For example, individual competition is presented as desirable when winning is the main focus. In contrast, collective knowledge generation is preferred when collaborative writing tools are used. This is basically nothing new in the education sector.

Thirdly, discourses on digitality provide the framework for how and by whom education is structured and shaped (Bundeszentrale für PB. Digitale Bildungsmedien im Diskurs. Wertesysteme, Wirkkraft und alternative Konzepte).

The development levels outlined here and their contents are under discussion. ⁵⁰ In the context of researching "digitality" or "digitalisation" in the school sector, it is also essential to examine the relevance of previous (analogue) educational content. This requires analyses, planning and implementation. Digitalisation in the education system has been a current topic in Austria for years and has already led to planning and implementation, but above all to discussions (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

⁵⁰ The related issue of whether pupils who have little literary practice should be brought to a high level of competence in book reading is controversial. Here it is also essential whether and to what extent the parental home, circle of friends, etc. influence this. In principle, social background is also decisive here. This must be taken into account in any case, because unequal educational opportunities subsequently exist. This also applies specifically to educational opportunities for the development of media competence, which reinforces social inequality. The topic of digitalisation of schools and teaching is of interest to researchers; the development of models is, for example, of fundamental importance here (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

2.2. The meaning of models

2.2.1 Models on digitalisation strategies (excerpt)

There are many different approaches and paths in the field of digitalisation of schools and teaching, which are basically validated by the specific situation. They occur in particular in the context of school development processes. However, the development of strategies as well as a shared understanding of what is meant by "digitalisation" or "digital transformation" are always necessary - in contemporary understanding. Knowledge of models can also be beneficial, even though these are often targeted at specific aspects of digitalisation such as information technologies, etc. The basics of digitalisation strategies and selected models shall be presented before investigating the digitalisation in the Austrian education system, (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

However, the goals and perspectives of these models principally differ considerably. A reflective review by the actors is always necessary in this context. In the following, examples of digitalisation strategies are discussed which can also lead to substantial questions (Iqesonline.net, Modelle zur Digitalisierung von Schule und Unterricht-IQES..., p 1 f).

The following models are intended to provide an overview of different approaches. In general, the association between digitalisation and school development is of central importance. Information and computer technology is essential here and the basic knowledge in this regard is basically a prerequisite for success already in the planning stage. The willingness of all actors to cooperate and coordinate is also crucial. The possibility to use individual areas of different models or to combine them should also be considered (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

a) The SAMR model

This model enables to design tasks with digital media. Schools can use this model as a common language to facilitate learning experiences with digital media. Educators can reflect here on how to optimally use digital media. Either as a direct replacement for working tools without functional change, or as an extension, modification or renewal by designing new tasks that were previously unimaginable.

b) The 4K model

The 4K model means competences in the VUCA world of the 21st century. It is an important component for school and lesson development. In contrast to the SAMR model, where educators, their use and the use of learning technologies are essential, the 4K model focuses on the question of competence acquisition in the context of new global challenges with a clear focus on pupils.

c) The IQES- model (Switzerland)

The IQES model of a good and healthy school promotes or supports a lesson-centred school development that empowers the educators for their tasks and focuses on the successful independent learning of the students. This model is a practical orientation framework whose individual elements can be optimally adapted to specific requirements. It is designed to focus the teachers' energies and limited resources on their core task, i.e. the effective and sustainable promotion of students' learning processes and outcomes. This means self-directed and cooperative learning as an essential relief factor for teachers. The eight elements or fields of action of QM include self-directed learning, development of competencies, good teaching, individual feedback, work in teaching teams, cooperative teaching development, school management and staff development as well as school development and internal evaluation (Iqesonline. net, Schulentwicklung, p 1 ff).

In the context of this model, the topic of "digital education" is essential; it includes an extensive media library with teaching ideas, video tutorials, guides and annotated collections of tools, basic texts, platforms, etc. These are important contributions to contemporary education in a digital world. Based on Bloom's Taxonomy, the IQES Kompetenzrad enables to formulate learning objectives with verbs and to allocate learning and media products to them.

d) The ARCS- model

1. Attention: Gaining the attention of the students or learners is an essential goal of motivation for learning. Attention and interest in the lesson or in the subject matter must be sustained. Curiosity and topics that also concern one's own living environment, media, etc. are crucial in this respect. According to Keller and Kopp

(Keller&Kopp 1987), attention is gained, for example, by way of using new, surprising, contradictory or uncertain events. The curiosity of the students is stimulated by new, paradoxical, inconsistent or complex things. However, an excess of these themes can entail fundamentally negative effects here. In order to ensure that pupils can see learning content as meaningful, learning tasks can also be associated with important needs and motivations. Confidence, appropriate positive feedback and affirmation of successful learning are important in the context of motivational conditions or attention.⁵¹

2. Relevance: Relevance here means conveying the meaning of the subject matter. The engagement with the subject matter must be intrinsically and/or extrinsically motivated for students - it must be relevant for them. The choice of teaching method is also very important here, because it is fundamentally associated with motivating aspects. The relevance of the subject matter comprises two perspectives, i.e. the usability of the subject matter for tasks or performance assessments based on it and for the teaching/learning process. The everyday life or the life world of the learners is an essential point of view in this respect. Relevance is also created by the fact that learners can find themselves in details of the teaching process or in their own living environment.

3. Confidence (confidence in success / expectation of success): Educators should be aware that pupils and students can only be motivated by a positive expectation of success. This basically also promotes the learners' own abilities and skills. The individuality of the students and trust, i.e. an individually adapted level of expectation to increase the chances of success, are crucial in this context (Schaumburg et al 2019, p 178).

4. Satisfaction: Educators should be aware that learners' efforts should be in line with their associated expectations. If the effort expended deviates from the associated expectations of the students, a situation of demotivation basically arises. However, the motivation of learners – which also comprises satisfaction - is of

⁵¹ According to Heckhausen, motivation is "the momentary readiness of an individual to direct and coordinate his sensory, cognitive and motor functions towards the attainment of a future goal state" (Heckhausen 1974, p 194); <https://arbeitsblaetter-news.stangl-taller.at>, p 1 ff..

fundamental importance. Learner satisfaction can be increased, for example, through extrinsic rewards. For example, there are several possibilities of rewards in the context of digital (teaching) media. This includes the achievement of possible points in a specific learning programme, etc. Fundamental knowledge is required for educators in this respect, because the use of extrinsic rewards must be very well planned and implemented, otherwise intrinsically motivated actions in the classroom could be negatively influenced⁵² (Schaumburg et al 2019, p 178).

e) The Dagstuhl Triangle

This model was developed within the framework of the so-called "Dagstuhl Erklärung 2016". In the Dagstuhl Erklärung 2016, experts from different fields of science, such as computer science, media education, economics, and above all didactics and teaching practice, demanded an independent learning area that should be explicitly included in school curricula. This also means interdisciplinary action or subject-specific interconnections in the context of media education and media competence. The model shows three perspectives of digital education as well as manifestations for the school sector (Ges. für Informatik 2016, p 2 ff).

According to the "Dagstuhl Triangle", each manifestation of digitalisation has different aspects that also influence each other. Educators, pupils, students, etc. must be able to deal with systems in a self-determined way, and their possible uses should be clear. Digital systems should be investigated and understood with regard to interactions between actors, opportunities for exerting influence, etc. The Dagstuhl Triangle therefore shows three perspectives that should be considered and questioned in the context of education or school (media education: bildungserver.wien).

These perspectives are:

- "The technological perspective", with the question "How does it work?". This includes "creating technological foundations and background knowledge for co-

⁵² In 2008, the scientist and teaching psychologist Keller added the letter V to the ARCS model. For Keller, the letter V in the context of this model means to knowingly and deliberately implement instructional goals in a well-planned way. These are self-regulation processes of the learners. Here, they can control their own learning processes, and also monitor and focus them well. This is conducive to learning perseverance, concentration, etc. (Schaumburg et al 2019).

creating the digitally interlinked world".

- "The socio-cultural perspective", with the question "What is the effect of this?" This includes the examination of interactions in the context of digital networking with individuals and society.

- "The application-related perspective", with the question "How can I use this?" This includes the selection of relevant systems and their effective use to realize individual and cooperative projects (Medienbildung: bildungserver.wien; cf. also Gesellschaft für Informatik 2016, p 2 f).

Figure 2: The Dagstuhl Triangle

Source: Medienbildung, Bildungserver Wien

f) The model of Brandhofer and Wiesner (2018)

Brandhofer and Wiesner developed an "integrative framework model for learners' digital competence". A fundamental question is what competences teachers and learners should have when using digital media. Different perspectives of digital competence are examined, which are correlated to each another. The model describes central competence models and lists of competences for teachers and learners as well as their position and structure (Researchgate.net, p 1).

This model was intended to make a contribution to Austrian educational

research. As a major result of this research, it was shown that Digi.kompP also has a framework model. The competence catalogues digi.komp4, digi.komp8 and digi.komp12 are a list of can-do statements and do not have an underlying competence model. The concepts DigComp and DigCompEdu are seen as digitalised lists. The concepts are taken up and brought together by the integrative model. The model is intended to contribute to the discussion on learners' digital competences. In addition, the results of this research will also enable a basis for future revisions of standards ("Online Journal for Research and Education", p 12).

In any case, this framework model attempts to structure the subject didactics, subject systematics and theoretical learning aspects in a well-prepared manner. Essential for this research by Brandhofer and Wiesner were, among others, also the "Grundsatzlerlass Medienerziehung" (BMBF 2014), the Examination of the Lists of Digital Competences by digi.komp4, digi.komp8 as well as digi.komp12 and relevant changes in the "Verordnung über Lehrpläne zur digitalen Bildung" (BGBL. II No. 71/2018) (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Figure 3: "Competence model of digital learning"

(Source: Brandhofer & Wiesner, 2018)

g) The motivating effect of instructional media: Deimann's research

Deimann's research is also of interest for the topic of "digital media in the educational context". In his view, the following research results are essential to the question of the "motivating effect of (teaching) media":

- "Digital learning programmes have the potential to enable important networking. I.e. also to combine motivating aspects with each other. In particular due to their interactivity and adaptivity, digital media have a motivating effect; in addition, auditory and visual impressions are essential for learners".

- There is a significant difference between face-to-face and distance learning. Online learning offers can basically motivate learners through their possibilities, especially also through their independence of time and place. Tools are interesting here, for example internet-based communication and cooperation tools".

- Picture media or the use of pictures in lessons improve the motivation to learn and lead to increased joy in learning. In principle, concentration and attention are improved, which can also have a positive influence on learning perseverance" (Deimann 2002, p 66).

2.3. Development steps concerning digitalisation and digital education in the Austrian school system

2.3.1. The Austrian school system

a) Competences of the Federal Government and the Provincial Governments:

In Austria, educational affairs are traditionally a federal task, they are predominantly managed by the Ministry of Education. The education system is regulated by the federal government, and compulsory schools are regulated by the education directorates. In the past, these were the "Landesschulräte" and the "Stadtschulrat für Wien". The responsible Federal Ministry performs substantial tasks such as the training of educators, the maintenance of schools and the university and higher education system. The specific research basically covers all Austrian school types (Bildungsdirektion, Bildungsdirektion Wien, p 1 ff).

The applicable norm in the Austrian Federal Constitution is Article 14 BVG. Articles 10 to 15 of the BVG regulate the distribution of competences between the Federal Government and the Provincial Governments (legislation and execution). Article 14 is essential for the school system. ÜR contains Art. VII BVG, BGBl. No. 215/1962. In Art. Competence regulations which in part deviate from from Art. 14 BVG are set out in Art. II to IX of this BVG (Art.14 BVG; see Annex).

Austrian constitutional law shows that matters of the school system have a rather special status. The school system is of particular importance in the legal

regulations on competences that concern the distribution of competences. The Federal Constitution additionally lays down some content-related determinants of the school system. In addition, various sources of fundamental rights also contain provisions that provide for the rights of individuals in this context (RIS, Art. 10 – 15 B-VG; see also Wieser 2010, p 1 ff).

In the Austrian school system, the "digital school" is already a significant issue and represents a combination of modern, digital infrastructure and forward-looking pedagogy (Bmbwf.gv. at, Digitale Schule, p 1).

b) Tasks and goals:

Section 2 of the "Schulorganisationsgesetz" stipulates that young people should be "guided towards independent judgement and social understanding" and "opened to the political and ideological way of thinking of others".⁵³ (§ 2 Schulorganisationsgesetz).

"The main goal is that young, self-determined people should know their strengths and talents at the end of their school career. They should see their perspectives in a changing society in the digital age and be able to seize the opportunities that arise for them in order to be able to manage their private and professional lives. As active members of society, they should know the importance of democratic co-determination and shaping of society. Pupils should be able to follow the educational path that is suitable for them individually". This is described in the context of impact-oriented steering through specific goals (Bmbwf. gv.at, Das österreichische Schulsystem-bundesministerium für bildung..., p 1 ff).

"In the context of digitalisation, the aim is to map out a comprehensive basic understanding of for using new curriculum content, methodically and educationally accommodating digitalisation in the modern classroom" (Bmbwf. gv.at, Das österreichische Schulsystem-bundesministerium für bildung..., p 1 ff).

c) Major provisions of the Austrian policy and school policy:

⁵³ This applies to all subjects, but political education in particular is an important prerequisite both for individual development and for the further development of society as a whole (Unterrichtsprinzip Politische Bildung, Grunsatzerlass 2015).

In the PISA 2000 study and the Programme for International Student Assessment, "digitalisation and computer use" in the context of school was one of the topics of the Austrian national supplementary survey. Above all, the increasing importance of modern communication and information technologies was demonstrated in this context ("Programme for International Student Assessment" 2000).

The importance of "digital competence models" was also recognised. The mandatory exercise "Digitale Grundbildung in der Sekundarstufe I", the school network "eEducation Austria", the Initiative Schule 4.0 and the Austrian government programme 2020 - 2024 on the topic of (media) education are relevant here, for example. With the "Initiative Schule 4.0", the Federal Ministry responsible at that time developed a comprehensive concept. The focus was on digital basic education, digital competences of educators, digital content and the necessary infrastructure (BMB 2017). The school network "eEducation Austria" was newly founded in the context of the national education report 2015 including the criticism associated with it (Baumgartner et al., 2016, p 107).

2.3.2 "Digital school", "Digitalisation at schools", "Digital education", "Digital learning"

The terms "digital school" and "digitalisation in schools" mean "that digital media are acquired, installed and used in a pedagogical context at school". Digital education" means a plan that regulates the use of digital media (for example, devices, software, etc.) and the teaching of digital content in the individual subjects. In the present research, digitalisation in the Austrian education system is an essential object of investigation. In fact, all subjects are affected by digitalisation, even though some subjects, such as natural sciences, political education (Zeilner, 2020), etc., are of particular relevance (Aixconcept.de, Digitalisierung an Schulen Digitale Schule, p 1 ff).

In addition, "Digital Learning", an initiative of the Austrian Federal Government, is essential for developments and further developments. This initiative

is part of the "8-Point Plan" and is supported by OeAD as an agency of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF). From the school year 2021/2022, all fifth and, on a one-off basis, also the sixth grades are to be equipped with digital devices. These are prerequisites for IT-supported teaching and enable pupils to access digital education on equal terms (Digitaleslernen.oead.at, p 1).

For the time being, however, the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education" at pilot schools and then at all schools was essential for information, data and media competence as well as Office applications and the safe handling of personal data. In the eighth grade, this is also verified by the so-called "digi.check". However, "Digital learning" or "Digital school" requires in particular technical prerequisites, which are also associated with costs (Kurier. at, Schule-2.0, p 1 ff).

These are, for example, broadband connections, but also the corresponding internet bandwidth with provider contracts, etc. In addition, the power supply in the relevant classrooms, W-LAN, the ongoing maintenance and repair of the basic IT infrastructure, etc. In addition to the creation of the infrastructure, the teaching of digital competences or knowledge, skills and abilities are of importance for school as well as further career and life. This can at least be substantiated by the fact that digitalisation lastingly permeates and impacts not only the schools, but also many other areas of life. Media education is an essential requirement order to be able to correctly assess the risks and to learn how to properly handle the relevant technology (Ktn. gv.at, Land Kärnten investiert 903.000 Euro in das Projekt "Digitale Schule", p 1 ff).

The focus of media education lessons and the digital school is on pupils and students. It is essential to learn with joy and motivation in order to be able to cope in a self-determined way with tasks and the future. Based on a humanistic view of mankind, mastering the cultural techniques of reading, writing and basic mathematics is the foundation for school education. All-embracing general knowledge and the mastery of (several) foreign languages are indispensable basics that must be taught in the course of the school career. The acquisition of digital competences is important and means learning with digital media as well as learning about digital media and creating a basic understanding of it. Here, a meta-knowledge about digitalisation is

absolutely necessary - for certain actors - because there are constant developments that permeate and change society. The development of digital, media-related and basic IT competences makes it possible to promote analytical, logical and abstract thinking in a cross-curricular manner (Digitaleschule.gv.at, Vision, p 1 f).

The methodically meaningful use of digital media in the classroom can enable a broader spectrum of learning forms for different "learners". In this way, learning can be better organised and different "learning styles" can be taken into account. If used correctly, digital media can primarily encourage pupils to enjoy learning. In particular, project work, teamwork, etc. can be facilitated through networking. In general, this enables parents or guardians to recognise and support learning and learning successes more easily.⁵⁴

2.3.3 Relevant fields of law (excerpt)

Legal norms in the context of digitalisation and the use of digital media are very important for teachers and learners in the Austrian school system; these are presented below as examples.

a) "Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung 2001"

"Media education" has been anchored in the Austrian education system since 1991. A major step was taken with the "Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung" in 2001, which also established the teaching principle that is still valid today. This basic decree was updated in the context of the increasing importance of the media or significant developmental steps ("Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung" from 2014). The Basic Decree of 2014 is the basis for interdisciplinary media education in Austria throughout the entire school career. It obliges all educators to consider media education in their subject. Media education is a so-called "cross-section subject" (Süss et al 2018, p 63 ff).

⁵⁴ Technological offerings must always be designed and implemented in the service of pedagogy. The learning process focuses on students. In this understanding, digitisation sees itself as a "change driver" and not as an end in itself. New measures in the context of digitalisation should be linked to and support existing, good didactic approaches (<https://digitaleschule.gv.at/vision>, p 1 f).

At that time, the responsible Federal Ministry also provided explanations in this regard. "Since the topics addressed in the media affect all areas of cognition and action, media education is not limited to individual subjects or certain school levels. Rather, every teacher is obliged to take it into account as a teaching principle, as it is anchored in all specific subjects of the individual curricula (...) Media education generally has to take place at all school levels - in accordance with the intellectual development of the pupils" (BMBF 2014, p 5).

From the Federal Ministry's point of view, media education is understood as comprehensive media literacy and to promote media competence. Media education also means media policy education and should lead to the attainment of media competence. Media competence is based on Dieter Baacke's model, which is also shown in the present work. Active participation in the context of certain areas of society by means of (digital) media is essential and requires media literacy (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

b) "Bundesgesetz, mit dem die Finanzierung der Digitalisierung des österreichischen Schulwesens beschlossen wurde (SchDigiG)"

This law comprises a total of 11 paragraphs; § 1 regulates the purpose: "The purpose of this federal law is to be able to carry out the teaching of all pupils from the fifth school level onwards in all types of school (school types and specialisations) with a legally regulated school type designation supported by information and communication technology" (ICT-supported teaching). The aim is to create the pedagogical didactic and technical prerequisites (BGBL. I No.9/2021 vom 7. Jänner 2021).

c) "Grundsatzterlass zur Medienerziehung Wiederverlautbarung der aktualisierten Fassung" ("Erlass des Bundesministeriums für Unterricht, Kunst und Kultur")

This update of the "Grundsatzterlass zur Medienerziehung" took place because of technical innovations to anchor the term "media education", because of "network-based and social media" and newly emerged tasks of the teacher training colleges ("Pädagogische Hochschulen"). Based on the media-literacy definition of the

European Union (EU) (<http://ec.europa.eu>) and the recommendation of the EU Commission of 20.8.2009 C(2009) 6464 final "on media literacy in the digital environment for a more competitive audio-visual and content industry and an inclusive knowledge society" (ec.europa.eu), the active use of communication networks was also taken into account ⁵⁵ ("Erlass des Bundesministeriums für Unterricht, Kunst und Kultur GZ 48.223/0006-B/7/2011, Rundschreiben Nr. 4/2012").

The "Grundsatzterlass zur Medienerziehung" comprises the areas of basic principles, definitions of terms, objectives of media education and implementation. It is already explained under Basic Principles that "media education" aims at comprehensive "media literacy". Media have an influence on everyday life. Technical possibilities in the context of media, communication etc. are of increasing importance in the everyday world. Education and upbringing should support pupils in their relationship to the environment. With the development of high-tech technologies, a new definition of reality has emerged, which is why media education is becoming increasingly important ⁵⁶ ("Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung", see appendix).

Media education is not limited to specific subjects, nor to specific school levels. This can be derived above all from the "Grundsatzterlass Medienerziehung" or the educational principle. In school lessons, pedagogy should include "media education". There were and are also demands for a separate subject of media education, but this also concerns other areas such as political education. However, these demands are controversially discussed and relate to the field of educational policy (Erlass des Bundesministeriums für Unterricht, Kunst und Kultur GZ 48.223/6-B/7/2011, Rundschreiben Nr. 4/2012).

⁵⁵ "The decree entered into force on 31 January 2012. With the entry into force of this decree, the decree GZ 48.223/14-Präs. 10/01 of 20 November 2001 expired" (Erlass des Bundesministeriums für Unterricht, Kunst und Kultur GZ 48.223/0006-B/7/2011, Circular No.4/2012).

⁵⁶ The teaching principle of media education is - like all other teaching principles - a so-called cross-cutting issue. This means that media education should be taken into account in all subjects, the implementation is clearly up to the teachers. However, my experience as an educator in higher education (BMHS) suggests that this willingness to implement is relatively low, as is the case with other teaching principles, e.g. political education (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

With the "Medienpädagogisches Manifest" in 2009, educators addressed the public and representatives of education policy. At that time, they called for media education to be anchored in the curricula. In the context of "Education for Sustainable Development" (ESD), media education should have a particularly high priority (Keine-bildung-ohne-medien.de, page 63).

d) "Bildungsreformgesetz 2017" (BGBl. I Nr. 138/2017-RIS)

With the "Bildungsreformgesetz 2017", the National Council in Austria decided to introduce the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education". This compulsory exercise concerns the lower level of the AHS and (Neue) Mittelschulen /. "We have to create the basis and provide young people with the foundations for knowledge and action so that they can deal well with the changes brought about by digitalisation and embrace it as an opportunity," was a statement of the former Minister of Education Heinz Faßmann. "The new subject is intended to provide children and young people with the necessary skills and prepare them for life in an increasingly digital world" (Ots.at.: "Digitale Grundbildung ab Herbst in AHS und NMS", p 1 f).

Digital literacy encompasses much more than the use of digital devices. The operation of digital devices should be optimally mastered in various contexts; however it should also be possible to take a critical look at digitalisation. All essential factors should be covered by the then new subject, Ots.at.: Digitale Grundbildung ab Herbst in AHS und NMS, p 1 f).

Substantial contents of this new subject include "digital user knowledge of operating systems, digital communication and social media, safe and critical use of the Internet, aspects of media change, and above all problem-solving skills". The school-autonomous implementation of this compulsory exercise provides the schools with some organization possibilities. These include the time frame, school levels and the form of instruction. Schools are free to choose to implement the compulsory exercise as a separate subject, integratively in the subject lessons or as a mixed form.

Several accompanying measures are also planned for this purpose. For example, teachers can determine their "current status" through a "digital competence

assessment" and take targeted further training measures. An individual, digital portfolio can be created as a "proof of competence". Both in-school and external seminars can be accessed via the school development network "eEducation Austria". In addition, prepared application options for "digital basic education" are available via the "digikomp platform". Furthermore, a digital textbook can also be used for the subject area of "basic IT education". This book is also available as a print edition and can be ordered via the textbook campaign.

e) "IKT-Schulverordnung 2021"

The IKT Schulverordnung or the Ordinance on ICT-supported teaching and data security measures in the school system entered into force on 1.9.2021. The Schulunterrichtsgesetz (§ 14a SchUG) already defines ICT-supported instruction, i.e. instruction supported by information and communication technology and the use of digital end devices (laptops, tablets, etc.) (BGBl. II No. 382/2021).

§ 14a of the SchUG stipulates:

„(1) Digitale Endgeräte sind Einrichtungen zur elektronischen oder nachrichtentechnischen Übermittlung, Speicherung und Verarbeitung von Sprache, Text, Stand- und Bewegtbildern sowie Daten, die zur Datenverarbeitung und Datenkommunikation eingesetzt werden können. Insbesondere Notebooks oder Tablets.

(2) IKT-gestützter Unterricht ist Unterrichts- und Erziehungsarbeit unter Einsatz digitaler Endgeräte als Arbeitsmittel sowie von digitalen Lern- und Arbeitsplattformen, allenfalls auch unter Verwendung elektronischer Kommunikation.

(3) Der Bundesminister für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung kann mit Verordnung Vorgaben über die Art und die technischen Erfordernisse für IKT-gestützten Unterricht, digitale Endgeräte und digitale Lern- und Arbeitsplattformen festlegen“ (§ 14a SchUG. Bundesrecht konsolidiert: Gesamte Rechtsvorschrift für Schulunterrichtsgesetz, Fassung vom 09.06.2022).

With the IKT Schulverordnung 2021, an ordinance was issued that regulates

the essential technical and organisational measures for the use of digital forms of learning and work (BGBl. II No. 382/2021).

This created a necessary framework for measures to ensure secure data processing in the school sector, in particular for technical and organisational measures for digital end devices as well as for accountability (BGBl. II No. 382/2021).

f) "Knowledge of IT security: Framework conditions of the BMBWF"

Knowledge about IT security is also essential for teachers and learners and is required, for example, because of software vulnerabilities, viruses, phishing attacks etc. In principle, it is the task of administrators or designated persons to ensure the security of the IT infrastructure in schools. However, this is handled in different ways. Poorly trained teachers, pupils and students can also pose a security risk. The topic of IT security should therefore always be addressed at specific schools and in the classroom. In addition, this topic should be addressed during the course of study and further training for educators. Knowledge about technical risks in the area of computer use and about suitable prevention strategies are necessary for a competent handling of digital media. Raising awareness of safe surfing on the net is important here, including, for example, the creation secure passwords, the protection of personal data, dealing with computer malware, knowledge of cloud services, etc.⁵⁷

Knowledge for the use of private cloud services in IT-supported teaching is of advantage because IT-supported teaching is already of significant importance in the present (Bmbwf.gv.at, Schulrecht, p 1 ff).

The responsible Federal Ministry has already worked on framework conditions

⁵⁷ This also raises questions such as "What are the basics of digital education?", "What competences are necessary?" Above all, digital media must be used in a didactically meaningful way and media competence must be imparted. Courses of study for the teaching profession at universities and teacher training colleges should take this into account in their initial and further training. This has already been partially implemented and thus fundamentally improved digital understanding. Analytical thinking, coding and simple programming, among other things, should make algorithmic processes clearly understandable for the actors here (Zukunft Bildung. Journal des Landesschulrats für Niederösterreich 1/18, p 8). (www.lehrer-online.de/fokusthemen/it-sicherheit-und-datenschutz-in-schule-und-unterricht, p 1 ff)

for the use of private cloud services. These framework conditions are also published on the Ministry's website in the data protection section. In this respect, the three cloud service providers used in teaching to date (Apple, Google, Microsoft) ensured that all relevant services were offered on the basis of standard contractual clauses⁵⁸ (Bmbwf. gv.at, Digitale Schule, p 1).

The responsible Federal Ministry stated at the time, among other things, that in the future it would follow in particular the guideline announced by the European Data Protection Board as well as the documents of the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) that were being elaborated⁵⁹ (Bundesministerium Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung, Geschäftszahl: 2020-0.590.298).

In addition, this ministry in Austria also sought certification according to Art. 42 GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) as a national instrument (Bundesministerium Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung, Geschäftszahl: 2020-0.590.298).

The competent ministry clearly stated that the use of private cloud services in the Austrian school system is up-to-date and necessary. The digital world is already an essential part of school lessons and everyday life, and this has had and continues to have an impact on education systems and school lessons. A combination of modern, digital infrastructure and forward-looking pedagogy is necessary in this context.⁶⁰.

⁵⁸ A cloud is an interconnection of several servers through a data centre that is accessible online. This data centre is provided by a service provider. Users can outsource their stored data there, thus saving storage space on their own devices or storage media. Cloud storage or external storage - managed by third-party providers - is also essential for the education sector. Data is relatively securely protected in an external database (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

⁵⁹ ENISA, or the European Union Cyber Security Agency, was established by the European Union in 2004. Its task is to ensure the necessary high-level network and information security in the European Union. The Management Board of ENISA is also essential here, it consists of representatives of the EU Member States, the EU Commission and other stakeholders (ENISA on the official website of the European Union, europa.eu)..

⁶⁰ The basis for this in Austria is the eight (8) point plan. Here, in the context of agenda setting, "all central areas of the education system that are necessary for a quality, future-oriented school operation" are involved (Bmbwf. gv.at, Digitale Schule, p 1, [https:// www.bmbwf.gv.at/](https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/), p 1).

2.3.4 Further significant development steps in the Austrian school system

a) eEducation Austria (2016): Digital school development

The main task of eEducation Austria is to "steer and accompany the creation of a national community for the development of digital competences and schools in the digital transformation". The Federal and Coordination Centre eEducation Austria started in 2016 on behalf of the former BMB at the PH Oberösterreich. The Pädagogische Hochschule Oberösterreich is the eEducation Austria National Centre of Competence eEducation. Above all, eEducation Austria supports educators and schools in the further development of their digital competences. One support offer in this context is the university course "eEducation", a pilot course with the target group of lower secondary level. Further courses are already being planned nationwide and statewide.⁶¹

As an initiative of the Federal Ministry, "eEducation Austria" pursues the goal of promoting digital and information competences in all schools throughout Austria. This includes primary schools (elementary schools) up to the school-leaving and diploma examinations. Pupils should already acquire the necessary competences to be able to gain a foothold in further education or in specific professional fields. The topic of "Global learning" or "Media-based global learning" is relevant here (Bmbwf.gv.at, Digitale Grundbildung, p 1 ff).

eEducation Austria is a three-pillar concept and comprises the pillars 1. personal digital competences, 2. teaching development and 3. organisational development. Personal digital competence is the foundation for the use of technology in teaching. For orientation, the competence model digi.kompP is available for teachers. The digi.komp4 competence model is essential for pupils in primary

⁶¹ The participants reflect and expand their digital competences in this university course. Learning the theoretical and practical knowledge as well as skills is essential here. In particular, this is also a sustainable didactic further development of teaching (basic digital education and teaching development). In addition, the participants also help to further develop digital education at their school in the context of a project work. This generally takes place in school teams and requires the commitment of the school management. Here, some basics of school and team development as well as project and change management (school development) can be learned or improved (<https://ph-ooe.at/eeducation> 2020, p 1 f).

education, and the digi.komp12 competence model for pupils in secondary education. The digi.komp8 competence model for lower secondary schools was replaced by the curriculum for the subject "digital literacy". In the context of teaching development, digitalisation opens up teaching for different learning scenarios. Digital teaching development here means in particular online communication to promote learning processes and individualisation scenarios. With regard to organisational development, a good technical infrastructure and coordination of the measures taken are of particular importance⁶² (eEducation Austria: Digitale Schulentwicklung).

Regarding the "development of digital competences", educators need to develop their own digital competences. In this respect it is important to deal with the topic of digitalisation and digital media. This also includes the competence to judge whether and how this use is beneficial for learning processes.⁶³ (eEducation Austria: Digitale Schulentwicklung).

Self-direction and open learning scenarios are essential in the context of "lesson development". Here, input phases, which represent a basic pedagogical concept, can be conceived and applied in many ways. For example, from "frontal lecture" to "flipped classroom scenarios". Digital end devices enable better mobility in the classroom, as well as working in different teaching/social forms, the development of learning materials and basically good feedback.⁶⁴ (eEducation Austria: Digitale Schulentwicklung).

The area of "organisational development" means school development in a

⁶² Schools that want to actively address the important topic of "digitalisation" can become members of "eEducation Austria". This means in particular making the school location "digi-fit". Educators of neighbouring eEducation.Expert. Actors of the "National Competence Centre" "eEducation Austria" accompany the school development process with further training measures, individual development advice and suitable (teaching) materials (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/dibi/dgb>, p 1 ff)..

⁶³ To promote personal digital competences for educators, the support services "digi.check", "digi.komp tasks", "further training via the universities of teacher education", "database of lecturers", "eBuddy system" and "eTapas (OER content creation)" are available, for example (eEducation Austria: Digital school development).

⁶⁴ For promotion and support, eEducation Austria offers the "SET-App" and "diggr+App" (eEducation Austria: Digital School Development).

team; eEducation Austria is a networking initiative in this context. Central elements are the exchange of knowledge and collaboration within the college. Topics include the necessary (IT) structures and possibilities at the school location. The establishment of a digitalisation concept for the specific school is of particular importance. To get started in an organisational development process, the "digi.konzept-Assistent" and some other "support tools" are available in the login area, for example (eEducation Austria: Digital School Development).

Activities of "eEducation Austria" promote the didactically meaningful use of digital media in teaching subjects and the improvement of pupils' competences. An important topic concerns application scenarios of digital media. For educators, this means preparing students to be able to use digital technologies competently at school and later at work.⁶⁵

2.3.5 EXCURSUS: Digital school development

Digitalisation already affects many aspects of life, including the education and school sector. Here, digitalisation also means (co-)shaping the digital transformation. Major changes have taken place here, especially with regard to the possibilities of communication. In addition to the education sector, digitalisation has also entailed numerous changes in working and economic life, for which school lessons should already prepare. The digital transformation has already brought about major changes in the education sector, which requires school development processes and, in particular, the development of "media education concepts by stakeholders" (Bmbwf. gv.at, Digitale Bildung).

⁶⁵ In addition to digital technologies and digital teaching and learning materials, analogue technologies are still available and fundamentally important. However, this topic is often the subject of controversial discussion. According to scientific studies, digital teaching and learning aids can lead to positive effects and greater learning success if used correctly. However, the educators and their knowledge, as well as motivation, the teaching context and the teaching goals are very important for this. Digital media should be seen primarily as a supplement to analogue media. However, educators should take into account that digital teaching and learning materials, just like analogue teaching and learning materials, should not overtax pupils cognitively. Individual support is certainly necessary (Zeilner, 1991-2015); (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/dibi/dgb>, p 1 ff).

The topic of digitalisation of teaching and learning is very important for actors in the field of school development. The strategy "Education in the Digital World", an action concept for future development possibilities in the context of education in Germany, can also be seen as a good example thereof. This strategy was published by the Conference of Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs (KMK) in 2016 and updated again in 2017. In the field of schools of general education, the focus is on "competences in the digital world". Pupils should have achieved these competences by the end of their compulsory schooling. The competence areas here are: "Searching for, processing and storing information, communicating and cooperating, producing and presenting, protecting and acting safely, problem solving and acting, as well as analysing and reflecting"⁶⁶ (Kultusministerkonferenz (KMK) 2016).

A pedagogical concept and optimal technical equipment are primarily required in order to acquire the necessary competences. A school development process must be regarded as a multi-dimensional and institutional process. The essential design unit of school development is the level of the specific school, which is, however, integrated into the overall system of education or the school system. These are primarily the competent Federal Ministry and the education directorates. However, the necessary development processes for digital school development are implemented at the specific school. Development areas can be focussed here. In any case, these include the personnel development, organisational development, teaching development, development of the relevant information technology as well as coordination and cooperation development. The examination of relevant research literature clearly shows that digitalisation in the context of schools does not only take place at the level of infrastructure and information technology, but that organisational, personnel and teaching development etc. is also necessary. The development of potential cooperations, also with private institutions, is certainly effective (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

⁶⁶ The competence framework is the basis for activities of the Federal Countries is. The specific schools are supposed enable and promote the acquisition of the competences. An up-to-date pedagogical concept as well as good technical equipment and the necessary competences of the teachers are required for this. In this context, a resulting media education concept is to be regarded as an instrument of school development (Kultusministerkonferenz (KMK) 2016).

On a practical level, there are already numerous cooperations between educational institutions and private companies. Information acquisition, information processing, communication, content creation, data protection, data security, etc. are substantial issues in the context of media literacy which also require a solution-oriented way of thinking. Cooperation between educational institutions and private companies is in principle necessary in this context; it concerns information technologies as well as, primarily also pedagogical or political contents for teaching, such as apps, political situation games etc. These are essential media and communication prerequisites. For example, "schule.at" in cooperation with "Playmit" has produced twenty-six (26) short videos on the sub-areas of the curriculum for "Digital Basic Education" (schule.at, MEIN DIGITALE SCHULPORTAL).

This is a good example of a networking initiative. Other examples of networking initiatives are "Medienbildung Jetzt" and the "Bundesverband Medienbildung". In Austria, the networking initiative "Medienbildung Jetzt" and the "Bundesverband Medienbildung" are an essential media and information competence network where Austrian media educators exchange information. In the course of their professional activity in the context of pedagogy, information technologies, etc., media educators impart media education and media literacy. Media education is a significant contribution to the education of people and the development of the knowledge society.⁶⁷

As already indicated, school development processes can generally be structured in different ways. Analogous to organisational development processes, initiation, implementation and institutionalisation are of outstanding importance. These phases can and often do overlap in practice. The actors at a specific school, i.e. in particular the school management and the teachers, are decisive for success. This

⁶⁷ The topic of media education and society or knowledge society is of current importance. "Life worlds are media worlds, media worlds are life worlds". In everyday life, people are not only confronted with political content, but also with media and the associated information and communication technologies. With regard to the use of media in schools, an essential question is "How do I use media sensibly, when, for what purpose and at what point in the lesson? This should be done in the context of media didactics and should also be considered in the context of digital school development (<https://www.lmz-bw.de>>, p 1 ff). [https:// bundesverband-medienbildung.at](https://bundesverband-medienbildung.at), p 1 ff

already applies to planning and subsequent implementation (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

b) "digi.komp"

Digital competences and education in informatics have already been demanded and promoted in the Austrian school system for many years. The contemporary and future society requires up-to-date education, its active future-oriented organisation and further development. The use of information technologies or digital technologies in the context of pedagogy, both for teaching and learning, has already become a necessity. High-quality education using digital media is an essential prerequisite for students to cope well with current and future demands. However, the reality in some schools shows that the process of introducing or implementing digital education concepts as a standard in education or teaching is often still in its initial stages⁶⁸ (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

With DigComp into Action. Get Inspired Make It Happen. A user guide to the European Digital Competence Framework", the European Commission published a "Report on experiences with the implementation of the DigComp reference framework" already in 2018. Research that took into account other experiences in addition to this publication came up with interesting results which can be summarised as follows:

- "What digitalisation is, can and will trigger is still unclear". Digitalisation is „work in progress“ und „history in progress“.

- In particular, the issue of social cohesion (inclusion) is of great concern to many, but there are also calls for appropriate education, research and development, institution-building and a courageous seizure of the opportunities associated with it. - The DigComp 2.1. reference framework is one of a number of measures to capture digitalisation and the demands and opportunities it brings for citizens. This reference

⁶⁸ The common digi.komp umbrella is also essential for the implementation of the mandatory requirements. It demonstrates skills specifically with the "autonomous, reflected use of information and communication technologies" mentioned in the curriculum. It enables educators to use digital and informatics competences according to plan in subject lessons. The competence model digi.komp comprises the sub-aspects information technology, people and society, informatics systems, applications and concepts (www. bmbwf. gv.at>zrp>dibi>dgb, p 1).

framework is "work in progress", but with relevant impulses for institutions and companies".

- "The effectiveness of these tools and certificates strongly depends on the target group and their context of use".

- "The openness and dynamics of the development suggest a network association of initiatives, companies and institutions that are involved or responsible and active in matters of digitalisation. However, a central support institution that actively promotes communication and cohesion is absolutely necessary."

- "An open eye on one's own mistakes (understood as learning opportunities) or those made by others and the exchange about them, is of major importance" (Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 16).

The Austrian competence model "DigComp 2.2. AT" is based on the European DigComp 2.1. reference framework. In 2018, the entire English DigComp 2.1. was translated into German and additions were made based on the insights gained in the consultation process. DigComp 2.2. AT is multidimensional and comprises six competence areas and twenty-five competences. The "DigComp Taskforce" was founded for the further development of the competence mod (Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 21 ff).

c) The year 2006: "digi.komp – Digital competences, digital education"

The examination of digital competences is not defined as an explicit goal of the present work. Here, for example, the guidelines and goals of the competent Austrian Federal Ministry, universities and teacher training colleges, etc. are essential. In addition, important development steps have already been undertaken by private and informal initiatives (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

Since 2006, the so-called "digi.komp initiative" has been promoted in Austria; implementation was initially on a voluntary basis and was then integrated into curricula mandatorily. These are "digi.komp4": "a model of digital competences and implementation examples for primary schools (the number 4 refers to the 4th grade of primary school). "Digi.komp8": "digital competences and examples of

implementation for secondary level 1" that ends with school level 8. The subject "Compulsory exercise in digital basic education", which has been introduced since 2018/2019, has replaced this subject. "Digi.komp12": "Digital competences and implementation examples for the upper level of grammar schools up to grade 12". However, BMHS and other vocational schools, for example, have already had explicit curricula in the field of informatics for some time. The "Digi.kompP" model is essential for the "training and further education of educators" ("Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort. Digitales Kompetenzmodell für Österreich". DigComp 2.2. AT, p 18).

d) "National education report 2015"

Chapter 3 of the 2015 National Education Report also contains a contribution on the topic of "Promoting media literacy". The competences of educators concerning the use of digital media are addressed here. It is demonstrated that there is a risk of not using digital media optimally enough "Media education" must be brought into play here - in the area of training for educators and in the competent use of these media by pupils. The main focus of the article is on the topics "Strategies for building digital media competence" and "Making increased use of the potential of digital media" ⁶⁹ (Baumgartner et al., in: Nationaler Bildungsbericht 2015, p 95 ff).

e) The years 2015 to 2018: "Grünbücher des österreichischen Bundesrates"

The Bundesrat in Austria began to focus on and discuss the topic of "digitalisation" as early as 2015. As a result, so-called "Green Papers" were published in the context of "expert reports, public participation processes and parliamentary enquiries". So far, these include the Green Papers "Digitaler Wandel und Politik" (2015), "Digitale Courage" (2016), "Digitalisierung und Demokratie" (2017) and "Digitale Zukunft sozial gerecht gestalten" (2018) (Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort. Digital Competence Model for AusDigitales

⁶⁹ "In the 2015 National Education Report, the authors also noted that initiatives - sometimes overlapping school-based projects and networking initiatives - to promote digital media literacy are neither effective nor efficient. This concerned both quantitative and qualitative areas". This view is open to discussion (Baumgartner et al. 2016, p 105 ff).

Kompetenzmodell für Österreich. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 19).

The topic "Shaping a socially fair digital future" comprises the issue of how we can continue to shape our society in a socially responsible way, which is why the focus is on the digital dimension. In the view of the Bundesrat, social responsibility is of outstanding importance. New technologies or digital media also lead to uncertainty among certain people, which is why long-term strategies must be jointly developed. The question of how digitalisation can be used to ensure social security and social cohesion is of fundamental significance. A space must be allowed in which innovations and new technologies can develop for the benefit of the people. The framework conditions must be designed in such a way that social justice is also guaranteed in a digitalised society. In the view of the Federal Council, the online consultation "Digitale Zukunft sozial gerecht gestalten" (Shaping a digital future in a socially just way) showed that the topics of work, education, data security and democracy are particularly important in the context of social justice and digital transformation (Republik Österreich Bundesrat. Digitale Zukunft sozial gerecht gestalten. Im Auftrag des Präsidenten des Bundesrates Reinhard Todt).

f) "Digital Roadmap Austria": The digitalization of the Austrian Federal Government (2016)

A joint digitalisation strategy of the former federal government was launched in 2016 with the "Digital Roadmap Austria; and the activities of all ministries were bundled for the first time in a joint strategy paper of the federal government. The Digital Roadmap Austria provides an up-to-date overview of the current status as well as current and planned measures and activities. In this context, twelve guiding principles are essential for shaping digitalisation in Austria. A "task force", formed by the "Chief Digital Officer" of each ministry, shall advance the work on the new digital strategy for Austria (Kmu-digital.eu, Digital Roadmap Austria, p 1).

The "Digital Roadmap Austria" is a dynamic strategy paper that is continuously adapted to current developments in the context of digitalisation. Of course, this also comprises the education system, which must be adapted and rapidly further developed. The education system must be able to cope with requirements at all levels. In this respect, the use of digital tools must also become a matter of course.

Digital media competence is part of every basic education. In addition, educational innovations must be promoted and adopted in the regulatory system (Services.bka.gv.at, 29_5_beilage, p 1 ff).

The development steps of the "Digital Roadmap Austria" from 2020 to 2024 are:

2020: "Unified platforms and the Digital School portal simplify communication between teachers, learners and guardians. Teachers participate in further training for the use of digital teaching and learning methods".

2021: "In the fifth and sixth grades, pupils learn with mobile devices. Teachers and learners work with competence-oriented digital materials".

2022: "Quality-assured learning apps support pupils in their learning".

2023: "The IT infrastructure at federal schools (e.g. AHS and BMHS) meets the framework conditions for digitally supported teaching across the nation".

2024: "Digital learning is well anchored in all Austrian schools" (Digitaleschule.gv.at, p 1 ff).

The implementation of the developmental steps outlined here requires efforts from all actors. In particular, the competences of the educators (and also the pupils), their interest and motivation are essential (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

g) Digital education: „Digitalization strategy School 4.0 (2017)“

In 2017, the Ministry of Education in Austria, which was competent at the time, took a major step towards promoting digital and IT skills with the "Digitalisation Strategy School 4.0". However, the basis for promoting digital competences in the Austrian education system had already been created through the "digi.komp model". The "DigComp concept" of the European Commission was also relevant, including its definition of "digital competence", which is as follows: "Digital Competence is the set of knowledge, skills, attitudes (including abilities, strategies, values and awareness) that are required when using ICT and digital media to perform tasks; solve problems; communicate; manage information; collaborate; create and share content; and build knowledge effectively, efficiently, appropriately, critically, creatively, autonomously, flexibly, ethically, reflectively for work, leisure,

participation, learning, socialising, consuming and empowerment" (DigComp concept of the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission).

The implementation of the digitalisation strategy "School 4.0" elaborated and presented by the Federal Ministry then started with the school year 2017/2018. It aims at "teaching technical skills" and "media education" throughout the entire school career. It is based on four interrelated pillars, namely:

1) "Digital basic education from primary school onwards": Here, the use of technology is imparted in a playful way and media education is taught. Digital basic education is laid down in the curricula. The focus is on the third and fourth grade. The acquired skills of the pupils are documented in a collective passport. A compulsory exercise in "digital basic education" (two to four lessons per week) has been introduced from the fifth to the eighth grade. Each school can decide whether the implementation takes place integratively in already existing subjects or as a separate subject. In the eighth grade, the competences are checked by means of "digi.check". "By the end of the eighth grade, pupils should have mastered basic computer skills and the use of standard programmes. Moreover, they should be able to critically reflect on content in social networks, information and media".

2) "Digitally competent educators": "Well-trained educators are necessary to teach digital content and to use it effectively in the classroom. The digital training and further education of teachers is clearly focused here". All new teachers will acquire standardised digital competences from autumn 2017 which will be verified by a compulsory portfolio.

The teachers have three years to complete the "modular course" (6 ECTS) from the beginning of their teaching activities. In addition, the educational offers of the "Virtual University College of Teacher Education" ("Virtuelle Pädagogische Hochschule") are also being expanded.

3) "Infrastructure and IT equipment": "Together with the Federal Ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology, the Federal Ministry of Education has planned a broadband initiative for compulsory schools. The medium-term goal of the BMB was to annually equip all pupils in the fifth grade with tablets and all pupils in the

ninth grade with laptops ". In primary schools, the "Mobile Learning Project", in which tablets are used in lessons, becomes relevant.

4) "Digital learning tools": Easy and free access to teaching and learning materials is necessary for educators to be able to convey digital contents. The "Eduthek", a portal for digital teaching and learning materials, includes a variety of content and media offers that are centrally accessible. For example, "teaching and learning materials, apps, games, innovative tools for modern teaching formats", etc. Educators are also shown application scenarios (Ots.at/ presse Aussendung/ OTS_20170123_OT0045, p 1 f).

In the context of this digitalisation strategy, digital education must - as well as in principle - be seen as an absolutely crucial factor for the future of people. In addition to reading, writing and arithmetic, digital skills are now part of the educational standard for pupils and students. Digital education is essential in the educational sector, in the working world and in the leisure sector. The "School 4.0" strategy is to be seen as an essential milestone in the Austrian education system; it builds on an "interdisciplinary concept of informatics education" and is based on pillars. "Informatics education", especially informatics as an exact, analytical science, ICT application competence as a cross-sectional domain and media education are the basics in this respect (Bildungaktuell.at, Digitale-bildung-oesterreich, p 1).

"Computational thinking" is also essential in the context of the compulsory exercise "Digital basic education". The present and the future are digital in many areas of life, which is why pupils and students must be well prepared for this already in the present. This also includes considerable challenges for the education sector. Basics are required in this connection. For many years, "digital competences" and "informatics education" have been educational goals in Austria. The common "digi.komp umbrella" is also essential for the implementation of the mandatory regulations from primary school to secondary level 2. It demonstrates, among other things, which skills are specifically meant by the "autonomous, reflected use of information and communication technologies" mentioned in the curriculum. It enables educators to optimally use competences in the subject lessons. The

competence model digi.komp comprises the sub-aspects of information technology, people and society, IT systems, applications and concepts.⁷⁰

These are fundamental digital and informatics skills for the use of digital media. Modern educational and working processes are hardly conceivable without their use. Digital technologies also require a new way of thinking in the Austrian education system and other approaches to education, which also requires digital and IT competences of the actors. A relevance with the "Programme for International Student Assessment" is clearly present here. Austria does not stand out in international educational comparisons - such as the PISA survey (Programme for International Student Assessment). Austria's pupils are in the middle of the pack when it comes down to performance. However, they are (still) lagging behind the top countries (Digitalisierung. agenda-austria.at, p 1 ff).

Research indicates that there are certain shortcomings with regard to the use of digital media and digital technologies, and partially also problems in the field of elementary education (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

h) "The 2018/2019 period": "Compulsory digital literacy exercise"

The digi.komp8 concept was replaced by the compulsory digital literacy exercise. In the course of the "Mandatory Digital Literacy Exercise", 14-year-old pupils are expected to be digitally literate as a result. In this context, the question of whether digital competences are "normal" and "a matter of course" for adults of all ages is also relevant (Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort. Digital Competence Model for Austria. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 19).

Especially in order to cope well with political participation opportunities offered by the internet in the context of the education system, globalisation, etc., "digital basic education" is an essential prerequisite. For this reason, as already

⁷⁰ In the school sector, data highways and fast data connections are necessary in order to be able to use digital offers and tools. In any case, this is associated with relatively high costs. Above all, educators must be able to recognise and cope with this situation; they are very decisive in the field of education (school). In the context of digitalisation, they should be digitally well trained and competent* (Zukunft Bildung. Journal des Landesschulrates für Niederösterreich 1/18, p 8). (www.bmbwf. gv. at> zrp>dibi>dgb, p 1)

mentioned, a prescribed curriculum for the compulsory exercise of "Digital basic education" at the (Neue) Mittelschulen and AHS lower cycles has been put into effect in the Austrian school system as of the 2018/2019 school year.⁷¹

This basic digital education with the aim of "teaching pupils to deal with media and modern technology in an informed, safe, responsible and reflective manner" is divided into areas of competence. These are digital competence, media competence and political competence (BGBL. II No. 71/2018).

The acquisition of digital competences relates to the selection and application of suitable tools and methods. The basis for the acquisition and expansion of digital competences is the conveying of hardware and software knowledge. Media use, media language and media content should be understood and reflected upon in the context of "media competence". Critical and creative thinking is very essential in this respect. The political competences are of significant importance for political education, as they also enable a better understanding of democracy, freedom of opinion, etc. Digital literacy is of great advantage in this context.⁷²

At lower secondary level, the competences set out in the curriculum are divided into eight categories. There is compulsory content here as an in-depth school-independent material. The curriculum was developed on the basis of DigComp 2.0 and digi.comp8 (DigComp 2.0; digi. comp8).

The eight categories include "1. Social aspects of media change and

⁷¹ The implementation is the responsibility of the schools or it is an autonomous decision of the schools to implement it in special lessons or integrated into other subjects. The assessment here is by "pass" or "fail" (<https://lehrerweb.wien>single>news>, Schule 4.0: Neue Medien und Lerntechnologien in Theorie und Praxis, p 1 ff).

⁷² In this context, pupils should recognise the possibilities as well as the risks and dangers of media. It is the task of the education system or the school to teach all the necessary competences. The competences listed here can also be applied to educational areas which include "Language and Communication", "Mankind and Society", "Nature and Technology", "Creativity and Design" and "Health and Movement". Didactic principles and equal access for all pupils are obligatory. Differentiated topics in political education should be selected and prepared in an age-appropriate manner. Here, a "hands-on tactic" is probably better than a theoretical treatment (<https://lehrerweb.wien>single>news>, Schule 4.0: Neue Medien und Lerntechnologien in Theorie und Praxis, p 1 ff).

digitalisation 2. Information, data and media literacy 3. Operating systems and standard applications 4. Media design 5. Digital communication and social media 6. Security 7. Technical problem solving 8. Computational thinking". These categories are essential for the acquisition of competences in the context of "media education" (Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort. Digital Competence Model for Austria. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 20).

From the start of school in 2022, "digital basic education" is a new compulsory subject. The curriculum for this compulsory subject was announced in July 2022. The programme includes IT competences as well as media and application competences. "Digital literacy" was previously included in the curriculum as a "compulsory exercise", but without grading. The schools had options. This is no longer possible. One hour per week must now be reserved for the subject in each class. The pupils now also receive grades. The new subject is also related to the equipment with end devices, which is why for the time being it is only taught in those school levels that already have such end devices. These are the first, second and third grade of the AHS lower cycle as well as the Neue Mittelschule, here the fifth to seventh grade. Only from the school year 2023/2024 will the fourth grades (eighth grade) be included ⁷³ (futurezone.at, § Netzpolitik. Der Lehrplan fürs Pflichtfach „Digitale Grundbildung“ steht fest, p 1 f).

i) "The year of digitalisation 2019":

The Austrian Federal Government proclaimed 2019 the "Year of Digitalisation" and, in this way, a major and far-reaching upheaval was actively shaped. According to the minister in charge at the time, this was necessary because a modern society requires digitally competent citizens. To promote these digital skills as the fourth basic competence, the former minister supported "fit4internet". In 2019, all citizens had the opportunity to carry out an online check of their own digital competence

⁷³ The following contents are, amongst other things, planned: "The use of search engines on the Internet (1st grade), the collection, filtering, sorting, interpreting and displaying of data (2nd grade), the explanation of the term "social media" or the understanding of the interests of the respective company offering the service (2nd grade) or the protection of devices and content against viruses or malware (3rd grade)" (futurezone.at, § Netzpolitik. Der Lehrplan fürs Pflichtfach „Digitale Grundbildung“ steht fest, p 1 f).

under fit4internet.at. The "Digital Competence Model for Austria-DigComp 2.2 AT" was introduced as a quality standard which was based on the "DigComp Reference Framework of the European Commission". The "Digital Competence Model for Austria" is oriented towards relevant developments (Bundesministerium. Digitales Kompetenzmodell für Österreich. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 4).

"DigComp 2.2 AT", a complex project that includes school, voluntary youth work and adult education, combines education and training. The field of activity is complex and includes focal points of teacher training studies, research and development processes, developments of practical responses, etc. In addition, numerous initiatives as well as networking etc. are essential here (Bundesministerium. Digitales Kompetenzmodell für Österreich. DigComp 2.2. AT, p 5).

j) 2019: "Digital Austria": An initiative for digitalisation

In February 2019, the Austrian Federal Government presented key projects in the areas of society, business and administration under the umbrella brand "Digital Austria". On behalf of the federal government, the then newly founded digitalisation agency "DIA" developed a set of measures specifically for SMEs based on internationally proven best practices. This also included the introduction of digital innovations in schools (Roadmap2050.at, Digital Austria Initiative für erfolgreiche Digitalisierung, p 1 f).

The Digitalisation Agency "DIA", which was established by the federal government in the Austrian Research Promotion Agency "FFG", is essential for the SME initiative. The federal government's "Digital Austria" initiative is substantially supported and implemented by the Digitalisation Agency (DIA).

The focal points of Digital Austria are: "1. The "Digital Austria" strategy. Coordination for the specialised strategies of the areas of responsibilities. 2. Education as an important cross-sectional topic (e.g. digital competences in teacher training, fit 4 Internet, etc.). 3. eGovernment (e.g. platform oestereich.gv.at, etc.). 4. Focus on cyber security (the first step here is the map of initiatives). 5. Cross-sectoral specialist strategies" (Slidetodoc.com, p 1 ff).

As far as Digital Austria is concerned, the "official Austria" has for decades taken into account above all the increasing digital competences of citizens and the equally increasing demands of digitalisation posed by service facilities. For example, "ris.bka.gv.at", the digital legal information system of the Republic of Austria, is essential for school lessons, especially in the context of political and economic education. The law in force is published online at this website. This is also of interest for political education (Digitales Rechtsinformationssystem der Republik Österreich).

k) "The Austrian Government Programme 2020 - 2024" on the topic of (media) education"

Major goals concerning the field of education were also defined the Austrian government programme 2020 to 2024. The topic of education, science, research and digitalisation is one of the six major chapters. The following, among other things, was established on this topic:

- "Digital terminals for every pupil in lower secondary education":

"Pupils from the 5th grade onwards (AHS, secondary school, other compulsory schools) are gradually being equipped with digital end devices. These digital end devices can be used in class as well as outside of school - according to local and personal needs. The award is to be linked to the quality of school-related digitalisation concepts".

A socially cushioned private financing share is provided for the digital end devices.

- "Equip practical schools of the Pädagogische Hochschulen (teacher training colleges) as digital pilot schools":

"This is done in order to enable optimal conditions for the training and further education of teachers and to test and research the pedagogical added value of new technologies.

- "Install the Austrian Education Cloud": "A reliable and secure repository from which any learning content can be accessed easily, quickly and at any place". This is done in conjunction with and following the textbook action

- Develop a Digital School Service Portal: "The service portal should facilitate

the communication between teachers, pupils and parents and simplify administrative and teaching-related work. In this context, it is important to guarantee "data protection standards".

- Extension of the digital competences of educators": "Embedding digital teaching methodology in all teacher training programmes as well as training and further education for all teachers" are key objectives here.

- "Digital competences are anchored as a teaching principle".

- "Nation-wide evaluation of the digital basic education".

- "In-school further training offer will be expanded": "In order to enable teachers to accompany their pupils in the most competent way possible in the acquisition of digital skills" (Open3.at, Bildung, p 1 ff).

Digital competences and informatics education have been laid down in curricula, teaching principles, etc. for quite some time. The Austrian government programme 2020-2024, here on the topic of digitalising Austria's school education, should also guarantee a reliable and practical implementation. digikomp also makes a significant contribution to this. It is essential for all actors to make optimal use of the digital potential in the Austrian school system (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

1) Digital Action Plan for Austria (2020)

After the first major lockdown in Austria in the context of the Corona pandemic or Covid-19, the "Digital Action Plan Austria" was published by the Bundesministerium Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort (BMDW) in June 2020. The focal points were / are "Digital transformation out of the crisis", with goals and measures, "Corona crisis as a bridge towards the goal". Above all, this action plan calls for more digital innovations. "Basic digital education" and training in the so-called "MINT subjects", i.e. "mathematics, information technology, natural sciences and technology" shall be promoted. One of the objectives of the digital action plan is to lead Austria into the future in a crisis-proof and innovative manner. Digitalisation is not seen as an end in itself, but Austria intends to use digitalisation to further

develop competitiveness, innovative capacity, prosperity, climate protection, health and cultural education in a targeted manner. With the "Digital Action Plan Austria", the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Labour has launched a forward-looking initiative based on the government programme. The Digital Action Plan for Austria refers to the "Master Plan" for digitalisation in education (Bundesministerium für Digitalisierung und Wirtschaftsstandort (BMDW). Digitaler Aktionsplan Austria).

m) "European Union Recommendations and Action Plans for Digital Education"

"Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of the EU 2006".

Already in 2006, the European Parliament and the Council of the EU issued a recommendation calling on EU governments to implement the European Reference Framework for Lifelong Learning. This reference framework also includes "digital literacy" as a key competence. In 2009, the European Commission also recommended that EU member states should promote media literacy in the digital world.⁷⁴

- "The EU Action Plan for Digital Education (2018-2020)"

The EU Action Plan for Digital Education (2018-2020) included the priorities: "1) Better use of digital teaching and learning technologies.

2) Development of digital skills and competences.

3) Improving educational and vocational training through better data analysis and data anticipation" (Education.ec.europa.eu, Digital education-action plan, p 1 ff).

This action plan has been superseded by the "EU Action Plan for Digital Education" (2021-2027), which is also discussed below.

- "The EU Action Plan for Digital Education (2021-2027)"

"The Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027) is a renewed European Union (EU) policy initiative that aims at supporting the sustainable and effective adaptation

⁷⁴ In addition to digital competence, other competences include here: "mother tongue, foreign language, mathematical and basic scientific and technological competence, learning to learn, social and civic competence, personal initiative and entrepreneurial competence, cultural awareness and expression" (www.rechnungshof.gv.at, p 127).

of the education and training systems of the Member States of the European Union to the digital age. This Action Plan builds on the first Digital Education Action Plan (2018-2020) and aims to contribute to the Commission's key objective of 'A Europe for the Digital Age' and to 'NextGenerationEU'. It also aims to support the Recovery and Resilience Facility - which aims to create a greener, more digital and more resilient European Union".

Initiatives such as this action plan are particularly necessary because shortcomings related to the use of digital media have been observed. This was e.g. deduced from a survey conducted by the OECD in 2018 as well as from the International Computer and Information Literacy Study 2018 (ICILS). These shortcomings are also related to access to information technologies, where people's income also plays a decisive role. Research by Eurostat 2019 revealed that "a quarter of low-income households did not have access to computers and broadband networks". The "EU Action Plan for Digital Literacy" identified priority areas, among others. For example, "promoting the development of a high-performance digital education ecosystem and development of digital literacy and skills for the digital transformation. This action plan also serves to realise the vision of creating a European education area by 2025". The Digital Education Action Plan is coordinated by the Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture's Digital Education Unit.

2.4. The Development steps "Digitalisation Master Plan" and the 8-point plan

2.4.1 The master plan

Digitalisation means enormous (possible) potential for the education system. However, strategic guidelines and a considerable amount of planning in specific areas of the school system are required here, especially in the school development sector. A "Master Plan for Digitalisation in Education" has been developed in Austria to ensure optimal conditions. The measures that have become necessary due to digitalisation are to be integrated here gradually and comprehensively (Bmbwf. gv.at, Digitale

Bildung, p 1 ff).

Objectives of the master plan:

- The measures that have been taken or are necessary as a result of the strategic and planning guidelines and the changes are to be implemented in an optimal way. This affects students, teachers and (information) technology. The main objectives of this master plan are: "Innovation in methodology and didactics through pedagogically optimal use of digital media in the classroom. Age-appropriate teaching of digital competences and skills in all types of schools and school levels in the context of clear pedagogical guidelines. The creative potential of the pupils as well as the interest in technology and technology development, especially among girls, shall be promoted.

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This master plan also includes three major fields of action, which are "Field of action 1 software" - "Pedagogy, teaching and learning content", "Field of action 2 hardware" - "Infrastructure, modern IT management, modern school administration" and "Field of action 3 teachers" - "Training and further education". Regarding "Field of action 1", new teaching and learning content from the field of digitalisation is to be systematically integrated into the curricula in the course of a revision of existing curricula. In this way, a comprehensive basic understanding of how to deal with new content should be reflected in the curricula, and digitalisation should be taken into account methodically and didactically in all subjects in the sense of modern teaching. Regarding Field of action 2, the infrastructure and the availability of mobile devices should be brought up to a uniform, comparable standard. It should be possible to use digital instruments and tools comprehensively at schools. School administration should also be simplified through up-to-date applications. Regarding "Field of action 3", digitalisation and new possibilities for teaching content should be systematically

⁷⁵ In addition to the field of education, the field of science: "Institutional strategies of universities and higher education institutions (University 4.0)" etc. and the field of research: "Institutional digitisation strategies etc. are also covered" (<https://slidetodoc.com/bmbwf-gv-at-focuses-on-digitisation-and-digital>, p 1 ff).

anchored in the training and further training of teachers."⁷⁶

This master plan for digitalisation pursues specific objectives. These are "methodological and didactical innovation through pedagogically adept use of digital opportunities in the classroom, age-appropriate promotion of digital skills and knowledge as well as critical awareness-raising in all types of schools and school levels in compliance with clear pedagogical guidelines, increasing interest in technology and technology development (especially among girls), reliable imparting of the digital skills, competences and knowledge required for a successful entry to the labour market and promotion of the creative potential associated with digitalisation among pupils as well as strengthening of talents".⁷⁷

The successive implementation of the digital school takes place in accordance with the eight (8) point plan for digital teaching. The next development steps for a nation-wide implementation of digitally supported teaching and learning are specified; this also concerns the implementation of innovative teaching and learning formats⁷⁸ (Digitaleschule.gv.at, Vision, p 1 f; see also 8-point plan).

2.4.2 The 8-point plan

a) Draft law (RIS):

The objectives: "Creation of the pedagogical-technical prerequisites for IT-

⁷⁶ Work on this master plan began in summer 2018. The master plan should be prepared with the involvement of other ministries and experts by the beginning of the summer semester 2019. The implementation of the plan and the projects and measures contained therein was and is aimed for by 2023 (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/zrp/dibi>, p 1 ff).

⁷⁷ "The Master Plan for Digitisation shall permit a comprehensive, structured and reality-based path of implementation and change" (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/zrp/dibi>, p 1 ff).

⁷⁸ The competence models "digi.komp", the introduction to the subject of "digital basic education" at lower secondary level, the age-appropriate approach to programming, etc. are very essential for digital basic education at primary and lower secondary level. Further initiatives of the responsible Federal Ministry are currently implemented in the area of media education, MINT and Industry 4.0 as well as Vocational Education and Training 4.0. Current priorities also include teacher training, digital textbooks and ICT policy, i.e. "Recommendations for the use of digital technology at school locations" (<https://slidetodoc.com/bmbwf-gv-at-focuses-on-digitisation-and-digital>, p 1 ff).

supported teaching":

With the implementation of the eight (8) point plan "Digital School", "digitally supported teaching and innovative teaching and learning formats" are anchored in the education system. In particular, this is a prerequisite for IT-supported teaching for all pupils from the fifth (5th) grade onwards (Bmbwf.gv. at, DigiSchG, p 1 f).

This comprises: "1. The technical equipment of pupils with digital end devices on a uniform technical level, 2. The use of digital end devices within the framework of a location-related overall digitalisation concept, which integrates the use into the special features of each school and 3. Uniform learning and working platforms for pupils at the same school location or in schools with comparable educational and teaching tasks".

A central "Digital School Service Portal" is aimed at improving the communication between teachers, pupils and parents/guardians. This service portal provides essential application basics as a "single point of entry" by means of "single sign-on". This also includes the equipment with the necessary "hardware" and "software".

b) Presentation and concept:

In June 2020, the so-called "8-Point Plan for Digital Education" was presented. In this plan, the focal points of the digitalisation of the Austrian education sector are laid down for the near future. In order to obtain digital end devices for their own school location, schools shall create a "pedagogical digitalisation and utilisation concept". "Pioneer schools" can distinguish themselves by acquiring the "eEducation-Expert/Expert.Plus status". All schools need a corresponding concept for the digital classroom. In addition, educators should be prepared for special requirements through targeted further training; they also acquire important competences in this way.⁷⁹

⁷⁹ The "ACP eduWERK Academy" also offers a training programme based on the 8-point plan. This private company supports schools and educators, e.g. in workshops, etc. as well as in topics from the special series "Fit für den 8-Punkte-Plan" etc. (<https://eduwerk.acp.at/8-punkte-plan>, p 1 ff).

Conclusions and Recommendations from Chapter II

Digitalisation in the education sector:

The subject of digitalisation in the education system in Austria has been very topical for quite some time, and digitalisation is very resource-intensive. This applies primarily to the acquisition costs of hardware and software, but also to the time capacities of the teachers. Research interest focuses on sustainable school development in the digitalised world. Quality and sustainability are regarded as essential success factors, including access to knowledge and information. Pedagogical support is crucial for digitalisation in the educational sector. In public debate, however, shortcomings in relation to digitalisation in the education system are often still pointed out. Support services for educators and the actual school itself are of significant importance, and this requires good support solutions with a vision for the future. The focus of these solutions should not only be on development possibilities but also on a possible accompaniment with empirical research. The cooperation and coordination of the actors - in particular the school authorities and the school - as well as "best practice examples", is very important. On the part of the school authorities, the provision of an up-to-date technical infrastructure in schools and suitable support solutions that enable the integration of digital media in lessons is crucially important. In this context, support must basically be differentiated into a technical and a pedagogical component, which must be conceived and implemented jointly and in a coordinated manner. The term "technical support" refers to measures to ensure the technical functionality of digital media. The "pedagogical support" comprises the measures to support the integration of digital media in teaching and learning processes that is conducive to learning. According to Lorenz and Bos (2017), the "first-level support" provided within the school is essentially positioned at the school process level. The "second-level support" provided externally is a prerequisite at the input level, where the school authorities and (private) companies are essential for the implementation. Professional support is significant for the successful digitalisation of a specific school, especially the cooperation of the actors, above all between the school authorities and the school. However, digitalisation must always have a conceptual basis. Personnel and financial resources are necessary due to the

complex interrelationships and the existing comprehensive structures in the context of digitalisation in schools. Qualification measures are also required at the level of the school authorities and the schools. An understanding of large structures and interrelationships is essential in this context. On the basis of specific objectives, the integration of computers and the Internet is also being promoted by stakeholders in the sphere of education policy. For educators, it is also essential to take into account the media characteristics themselves. Here, different types of programmes also determine various possibilities of use, and therefore it is not possible to speak of one or "the" effect of digital media or the computer on teaching. In addition to the medium itself, the pedagogues, their interest, motivation and adaptation achievements, ideally together with their students, are of significant importance. Media education as well as a willingness to coordinate and cooperate is required here for all actors - especially to gain positive development perspectives. The three development perspectives identified by Eickelmann, "Integration of digitalisation processes with school development processes at the level of the individual schools", "Ensuring continuous staff development" and "Developing and maintaining sustainable cooperation structures" are certainly relevant to success and are subject to discussion. In addition to these development perspectives, the developments of the Federal Agency for Civic Education in Germany outlined, amongst others, on the topic of digitality are also of interest. Here, developments can be identified on three levels, which are also explained well. In the context of researching "digitality" or "digitalisation" in the school sector, it is essential to examine the relevance of previous (analogue and digital) educational content. Education in the digital world should actually also be understood as interdisciplinary teaching, which requires, among other things, examining curricula with regard to their relevance. At present, the knowledge to be attained by pupils, as laid down in curricula, is predominantly still contained in textbooks, even though the "media landscape" has changed considerably due to digitalisation. Whether pupils who grow up around digital media should (again) be brought to a higher level of ability in book reading is a moot point. The pupils' personal interests as well as the influence of the parental home, circle of friends, etc. are essential in this context. In principle, social background, income, etc.

are also decisive here. In any case, this should be taken into account by educators because unequal educational opportunities may principally arise from this. This also applies specifically to educational opportunities for the development of (digital) media competence, which reinforces social inequality.

The investigation of models:

There are many different approaches and paths in the field of digitalisation of schools and teaching, which will basically be validated by the specific situation. They take place in particular in the context of school development processes, especially at the level of a specific school. However, the development of strategies as well as a uniform understanding of what is meant by "digitalisation" or "digital transformation" - in contemporary understanding - is always necessary in this context. Knowledge of models can bring certain benefits, which are, however, often related to specific aspects of digitalisation - such as information technologies etc. Concerning the selected and examined models, it can be stated that they can in any case be regarded as an orientation aid; they provide a good overview of different approaches. However, the objectives and perspectives of these models differ, which is why conclusions drawn from the examination of these models also vary. A reflected review by the actors is always necessary. In practice or at implementation level, parts of the different models can also be combined, which could lead to good results. In any case, the models examined are subject to discussion in the context of digitalisation and the use of digital media in teaching; they should contribute to further debates. The research reflection of the examined models "SAMR Model", "4K Model", "IQES Model", "ARCS Model", "Dagstuhl Triangle", "Model of Brandhofer and Wiesner" and the "Research of Deimann" takes place in the Conclusion section in reply to a research guiding question.

The developmental steps of digitalisation and digital education in the Austrian school system in a historical longitudinal section:

In the present research, digitalisation in the Austrian education system is a fundamental object of investigation. Actually, all subjects are affected by this digitalisation, even though some subjects, such as natural sciences, are of particular relevance. The initiatives of the Austrian federal government are essential for both

developments and further developments. Above all, optimal conditions for IT-supported teaching should be created and pupils should be provided with equal access to digital education. The technical prerequisites in this context are, for example, broadband connections, but also the corresponding internet bandwidth with provider contracts, etc. Moreover, the power supply in the relevant classrooms, W-LAN, the ongoing maintenance and repair of the basic IT infrastructure, etc. are also required. In addition to the creation of the infrastructure, the imparting of digital competences or knowledge, skills and abilities is essential. In order to be able to correctly assess the risks and to learn how to properly handle the relevant technology, media education is a necessary condition. Media education lessons or digital schools place an emphasis on pupils and students; digital competences are therefore very essential in this context. For some actors, a "meta-knowledge" about digitalisation is absolutely necessary, because developments that permeate and change society are constantly taking place. The development of digital, media-related and informatic basic competences makes it possible to promote analytical, logical and abstract thinking in a multidisciplinary way.

Legal norms in the context of digitalisation and the use of digital media in the classroom are also very essential for actors in the Austrian school system - this concerns laws, regulations, decrees, etc. "Media education" has been anchored in the Austrian education system for quite some time. A significant step was taken with the introduction of the "Grundsatzerrlasses Medienerziehung" in 2001, which also established the teaching principle that is valid until today. With the "Grundsatzerrlass Medienerziehung from 2014", this basic decree was updated in the context of the increasing importance of the media and significant development steps. Moreover, this is the basis for interdisciplinary media education (cross-sectional subject) in Austria throughout the entire school career. It obliges all educators to take into account "media education", which is understood as comprehensive "media literacy" to promote "media competence" in their subject, i.e. to implement it in all subject-specifically across all teaching subjects. This shall be derived mainly from the "Grundsatzerrlass Medienerziehung". Media education also means "media policy education" and requires an engagement with the topic of "media communication".

Media literacy is based in particular on Dieter Baacke's model, which is also demonstrated in the present work. A further step was taken with the "Bundesgesetz zur Finanzierung der Digitalisierung des österreichischen Schulwesens" (SchDigiG). This federal law is intended, among other things, to enable ICT-supported teaching or to create pedagogical didactic and technical prerequisites. With the "Bildungsreformgesetz 2017", the National Council then decided on the mandatory exercise "Digital Basic Education", which concerns the curriculum of the AHS lower level and the (Neue) Mittelschulen. Here, basic digital education does not only include the use of digital devices, but extends far beyond that. Fundamental contents of this new subject include digital user knowledge of operating systems, digital communication and social media, safe and critical use of the Internet, aspects of media transformation, and above all problem-solving skills. Through independent implementation of this compulsory exercise by schools, they now have scope for design here. In particular, the schools are free to choose whether to implement "digital basic education" as a separate subject (integrated into the subject lessons) or as a mixed form. Several accompanying measures have been planned to support schools. On 1.9.2021, the "IKT Schulverordnung" and the "Verordnung über IKT-gestützten Unterricht und Datensicherheitsmaßnahmen im Schulwesen" came into force. ICT-supported instruction, i.e. instruction supported by information and communication technology and the use of digital end devices (laptops, tablets, etc.), is already defined in the "Schulunterrichtsgesetz" (§ 14a SchUG). The "IKT Schulverordnung 2021" (BMBWF) regulates the necessary technical and organisational measures for the use of digital forms of learning and work. This created a framework for technical and organisational measures to ensure the data security in the processing of school data, as well as for technical and organisational measures for digital end devices, and for accountability in school data processing. The responsible Federal Ministry also established framework conditions concerning IT security, here also for "cloud services". In addition, a certification according to article 42 of the GDPR was also sought by this ministry as a domestic instrument. The competent ministry clearly states that the use of private cloud services in the Austrian school system is current and necessary.

Further significant development steps in the context of digitalisation and digital media in the Austrian school system are eEducation Austria (2016) (Digital school development), Digital basic education in all school levels: "digi.komp, digi.komp (2006) (Digital competences. Informatics education), the National Education Report 2015, the "Grünbücher" (Green Papers) of the Austrian Federal Council (2015 to 2018), the Digital Roadmap Austria (2016) (The digitalisation strategy of the Austrian Federal Government, Digital Education (2017) (Digitalisation Strategy School 4. 0), the Binding Exercise on Digital Basic Education (2018/2019), the Year of Digitalisation 2019, Digital Austria 2019 (An Initiative for Digitalisation), The Austrian Government Programme 2020 - 2024 on the topic of (media) education and the development steps "Master Plan Digitalisation" and the "Eight Point Plan". The further essential development steps in the context of digitalisation and digital media in the Austrian school system, which are presented here in an overview and chronologically in the Conclusions and Recommendations from Chapter II, are dealt with and reflected upon as the research-guiding question in the overall research reflection (Conclusion) at the end of the present work.

CHAPTER III. DIGITAL MEDIA IN THE CLASSROOM

3.1. Basics on education and learning

3.1.1 Changes in school teaching

Due to its complexity, the topic of digitalisation in the context of education and schools requires a good orientation and, in particular, a determination of the respective school's status. The complexity and speed of change processes in the global and digital world also require adaptation efforts for the actors, especially for educators, pupils and students. In the so-called age of digitalisation, the school curriculum has changed to a significant extent, especially as a result of rapid developments in areas of technology and the increasing importance of information technologies. In the field of education, the "digitalisation of educational processes", including associated management tasks, is becoming increasingly important. "Digital education" primarily requires competences on the part of the actors, furthermore a considered and critical use of internet sources, social media, etc. "Digital natives are in great demand; learning support and knowledge transfer by educators is essential in this context (Zeilner, 1991-2015).⁸⁰

It can be stated, among other things, that digitalisation in the context of education and schools proceeded rather slow at the beginning; it must be seen as a process. In this process, digital media are increasingly taking the place of analogue media, even though they have not yet completely replaced them. The relationship between digital and analogue media must be considered in a differentiated way - in general and in the context of school lessons. This topic is also discussed very controversially; however, it is necessary to discuss and develop teaching media and "school digital" in a constructive and discursive way (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

If one examines previous developments in the context of digital media or

⁸⁰ This also means "learning with digital media and learning about digital media". In addition to well-founded theoretical competences, "learning by doing" is also relevant here. However, support by the educators should always be available. In the context of media democracy and modern political education, for example, the topic of "network policy education" is also essential (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

computer-based media in the school sector, it can basically be stated that digitalisation here is primarily taking place through so-called driving forces or committed actors. Changes in the context of digitalisation in the school sector are related to result-, structure- and process-oriented innovations and their implementation in school practice (Eickelmann 2018, p. 13).

In this context, "support structures" are clearly of relevance. A functioning "IT support", for example, is an essential success factor for the use of digital media. The necessary cooperation between school authorities and schools requires a clear distribution of tasks and also includes a systematic organisation in order to be able to perform all tasks and measures (with generally increasing complexity) from an economic point of view (Lorenz et al. 2020, in FRIEDRICH JAHRESHEFT XXXVIII 2020, p. 33).

3.1.2 The topic of education

Education is a permanent development process in people's lives. There is no uniform definition of education, but very different perceptions about it. However, some parameters can be defined, such as knowledge, intellectuality, cultural refinement etc. Nevertheless, the individual personality is also decisive - in this context also the whole set of abilities and skills. This is a permanent development process which also comprises the concepts that - in a narrower sense - are understood to mean education. Knowledge here means "being aware of something", intellectuality refers to special artistic and scientific knowledge (Latin: intellegere = to understand), cultural refinement here means the desired way of life developed in a social context. In addition, there are the individual predispositions of a person as well as temporal, spatial and social conditions. These are the circumstances in which a

person has to live.⁸¹

A high level of education basically has positive effects on many areas of human life. However, this is very complex and also includes aspects such as health, income, etc. A distinction can be made here between the individual benefit of education and the benefit of society. Education ranks among the most important resources for people. However, digitalisation has changed many things; in particular, it has made "digital education" necessary. However, access to (digital) education is very unequal around the globe. According to Hradil, (social) inequality is a "state in which certain people regularly receive either more or less scarce goods and resources in a society than others". The issue of the "digital divide" is also essential in this context and means the gap between people with and without the possibility to use information and communication technologies - such as the internet.⁸² (Hradil 2005, S 30).

Digitalisation is a current topic in the context of education. Since the Covid19 pandemic and its consequences, this topic has gained even more importance. Education in the digital world requires concepts for action or media education concepts for future developments and competences. Of critical importance here are in particular the following competence areas: "Searching for, processing and storing information, communicating and cooperating, producing and presenting, protecting and acting safely, problem solving and acting as well as analysing and reflecting". Media education concepts are equally significant instruments of school development, even though this is a multi-dimensional school development process and is to be

⁸¹ Education is fundamentally a complex and differently defined term. It is essentially seen as a measure of the conformity between a person's knowledge and view of the world and the reality. The ability to understand contexts and to gain well-founded knowledge is related to the level of education. Of particular importance is the intellectual, creative and moral development, which is derived from reason and freedom, without depending directly on politics and economics. This concerns not only the process, but also the result, etc. (<https://wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de>>Education Definition, p 1) (<https://www.bildungsexperten.net/wissen/was-ist-bildung>, p 1).

⁸² Digital divide is a digital polarisation in the use of and access to the digital, international communication structure. During the corona pandemic, major differences also became apparent in the Austrian school system (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

understood in an institutional way. The unit of design is the level of the individual school; however, it must be noted here that the same is integrated into the overall system of education. According to Schulz-Zander, the process of school development occurs in the context of five dimensions. These comprise organisational development, personnel development, teaching development, cooperation development and technology development (Schulz-Zander 2001, p. 194).

Cooperation between the actors is very essential in this context, and this can also take place within the framework of projects. In addition to the five dimensions or areas of school development, the topic of "digitalisation in the education sector" is of fundamental importance in the national, European, international and global context. Numerous studies have already been performed on this topic. For example, two online workshops on case studies (Denmark: February 2021) and (Romania: April 2021). In the context of this research, expert interviews were conducted with representatives from the education system in these countries. The workshops took place following an online survey on digitalisation in the education sector - with the main aim of determining the experiences and views of trade unions and of education providers.⁸³

The results of this study were presented and discussed at the final conference in October 2021. Moreover, a platform for discussing the possibilities or the opportunities and challenges of the influence of digitalisation on the education sector was created.

It can be said that the Covid 19 pandemic had an impact on the school and education sector. Above all, there has been a sharp increase in the use of digital technologies. The social effects - such as increased workload, lack of occupational health and safety – as well as the costs of digitalisation are major challenges. Significant opportunities of digital education mentioned by the study participants

⁸³ The E-Speed project (European Social Partners in Education Embracing Digitalisation) was launched in November 2020. This project/study was carried out in cooperation with the European Social Partners in Education, the European Trade Union Committee for Education and Science and the European Confederation of Education Employers (Final research report on challenges and opportunities for the educational sector in the digital era. csee-etu.org/en/projects/e-speed/4565-introduction-4).

included "improved access to education and inclusion in education, good opportunities for individual learning and acquisition of learners' skills for self-directed or self-guided learning, and an enhancement of the attractiveness of learning experiences for learners, especially when there is a risk of dropping out of school".

The need for effective and high quality training opportunities for educators and digital tools for teaching and learning in online or mixed online and face-to-face versions was highlighted in this study. According to the study participants, private providers or companies play a decisive role in this context.⁸⁴

3.1.3. The topic of learning

Learning is principally, but especially in the context of educational systems, a process that follows a certain pattern. One essential aspect here is that learning must also be learned. This is especially important for students from educationally disadvantaged backgrounds. The starting points of educators differ considerably, especially because there are well-educated students and students who are educationally disadvantaged. This basically includes some significant topics such as access to education, access to (digital) media, prior knowledge, etc. with effects on learning processes⁸⁵ (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

In simple terms, the scheme of how learning happens is a process where pupils or students absorb environmental experiences, process them and then integrate them into the already existing "knowledge". In ideal circumstances, the integrated new

⁸⁴ In the context of this study, the participants pointed out, among other things, the need for best practice examples, including platforms, the development of recommendations at European level to support the national level in the context of digital education (Final research report on challenges and opportunities for the educational sector in the digital era. csee-etuice.org/en/projects/e-speed/4565-introduction-4).

⁸⁵ According to Schelhowe et al, four learning processes can be defined or distinguished. These are essential in the context of education or teaching. Learning process 1 means that learning takes place through simple access to specific messages or factual knowledge. Learning process 2 means that didactic preparation of information is essential for learning complex facts. Learning process 3 means that socialisation and enculturation of learners takes place or should take place. Learning process 4 means that (digital) media can contribute to identity and personality formation (Kerres 2013, p 584).

material or the new knowledge can later be retrieved and (eventually) also utilised. This is an important task for committed and well-trained educators and requires a considered selection and preparation of the teaching content. This also includes the areas of global learning, quality-oriented learning, etc. (Bovet/Huwendick 2008, p 170).

3.1.4 EXCURSUS: Quality-oriented and global learning

In the digital age, the topic of quality-oriented learning is of fundamental importance. In particular, the potentials of digital media that are conducive to learning should be exploited in this context, even though these are controversially discussed. When used correctly, digital media principally offer plenty of potential to support learning. In many cases, this is also associated with advantages for teaching and school development. One of the essential questions here is with what arguments and how a teaching and school development process can be implemented with the aim that pupils and students increasingly - but not exclusively - learn successfully with digital media in a quality-oriented framework. Here, learning support and knowledge transfer by educators are of great topical relevance (Researchgate.net, p 1 ff).

The digital and global world has many implications for the field of education, especially for teaching practice. "Global learning" is an attempt to respond – in accordance with pedagogical principles – to globalisation and the related increase in complexity. Developments are to be made the object of experience and learning. Education in a networked, global world also requires a new learning culture. New knowledge is generated every day, new insights etc. are gained, of which one no longer has any overview. Education is an essential foundation here, especially for the selection and application of knowledge and for orientation towards the essentials.⁸⁶ (Tiefenbacher 2005, p 1).

⁸⁶ The term "glocalisation", that was coined by the English anthropologist Alan Robinson, is also significant here. This describes global networking in the "extended space dimension". It also means that physical presence is no longer necessary to communicate with people. Digital media can bridge long distances (Tiefenbacher 2005, p 2).

Pupils and students should be able to perceive global issues in their complexity and reflect on them critically. Cultural developments should be perceived as processes that provide opportunities for participating in and co-shaping the "world society" (Bmbwf. gv.at, p 1 ff).

In this context, "Global Citizenship Education" is, among other things, also relevant for knowledge transfer and competence development. In a globalised world, the discourse on education has also changed. Problem areas and challenges must be addressed locally and globally at the same time. Digital media are also essential for this (<https://www.unesco.at/education/global-citizenship-education>, p 1 f).⁸⁷

In the "digital age", global learning is already a fixed component in the Austrian and worldwide education systems. Digital media are already absolutely essential in this context. Like "virtual learning environments", they are also changing subject didactical approaches, contents and methods of teaching. In general, I have been able to observe this during my many years of work as an educator in the secondary school system and as a professor at BMHS (VET schools and colleges). Education in the global and digital world is a current topic, but it requires specific strategies, which are, however, controversially discussed (Zeilner, 1991-2015).⁸⁸

In addition to the topics of quality-oriented and global learning, it is also essential to point out that the learning culture is undergoing a lot of changes. This affects the education sector in many countries and also their working lives. For

⁸⁷ Global Citizenship Education (GCED) provides students with knowledge, skills, values and attitudes that enable them to take an active role in addressing global challenges and working proactively for a fairer world. In the sense of UNESCO goals - here also in the context of "education to become responsible and active global citizens" - an awareness of human rights violations or their observance, of education for sustainable development and the promotion of health through education is to be created. In this context, education is becoming increasingly relevant for understanding complex social, political, cultural and global issues and for solving conflicts of the 21st century, The use of digital media, especially media literacy, etc. are essential in this context (<https://www.unesco.at/education/global-citizenship-education>, p 1 f).

⁸⁸ The beginning of global learning in Austria dates back to the 1990s, it arose mainly from evolutionary-historical education. In the context of the global society, new demands arose in the field of education. In this context, the key issues of our time are a cross-sectional task of education (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/schule/sc/praxis...>, p 1 f).

example, developments in the context of digitalisation not only influence teaching/ learning methods and collaboration methods, they also determine how people will learn in the future. This means new challenges and very likely less learning or training with a fundamentally high number of face-to-face events paving the way for a culture where working and learning merge into each other. Here, "learning platforms" are also of significant importance. Learning settings are basically subject to change; innovative learning methods are essential in particular for people in their working life. These promote above all "microlearning", i.e. learning in small learning units and development steps (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 9).

The term "microlearning" generally refers to the micro aspects in the context of learning, education and training processes. It is a type of learning in small steps, often also using special software on the computer, smartphone, etc. In contrast to classical learning processes, this form of learning displays particular characteristics. It takes only a few seconds to a maximum of fifteen minutes. The learning units are simple and can be quickly grasped; learners, who can basically choose and co-design contents themselves, receive feedback immediately and directly⁸⁹ ([https://de.m.wikipedia.org>wiki>microlearning](https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/microlearning), p 1 ff).

In the present, learning and working are seen as a "coherent process" that can also take place at the workplace or on the move. "Mobility" is very significant here, and is not reduced purely to the local component, but additionally - in the sense of temporal flexibility and mental mobility over a long period of time - refers to (new) areas of knowledge. Due to the extension and further development of digital application areas and the required capacities, the interconnection between workplace and learning environment will become increasingly important in the future. Here above all also Learning 4.0 (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 9).

As far as digital learning methods are concerned, the selection of offers, which

⁸⁹ Microlearning is learning in many small learning units and in short steps, it is also offered via the internet. Learning can be adapted to the rhythm of the learner's life and work. For example, learning in the subway, on a plane, etc. Microlearning is often also a supplement to traditional learning (e.g. training materials), skills and competences can be learned and expanded here. In the context of in-company training, costs can basically also be reduced ([https://de.m.wikipedia.org>wiki> mikrolernen](https://de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/mikrolernen), p 1 ff).

in principle are already hardly manageable, is of fundamental importance. Apps, massive open online courses (MOOCs), e-learning tools, etc. are very important here. Modern learning formats can influence the process of learning in a fundamentally motivating and attractive way; they also enable learning via different sensory channels. In addition, "gamification" is also current, which allows for a transfer of game-typical elements and processes into a non-game context or learning environment.⁹⁰ (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 10 f).

Digital learning methods also require critical media reflection in the context of teaching. A media competence area in the context of education in the digital world should enable students to critically and reflectively analyse and evaluate (digital) media. They should know and be able to evaluate design tools of digital media. They should also be able to analyse the effects of media and reflect on the opportunities, risks, etc. of media use. This affects different areas of life, especially everyday life. Moreover, they should be able to assess the economic and political significance of digital media and the potential of digitalisation. For example, political participation is an important topic in this context. Critical media reflection is already a part of many curricula. Educators have the important task of integrating this topic into their lessons. ⁹¹

Critical media reflection is fundamentally significant in the field of education, and is of increasing importance in the context of digital learning. The priority at this point is to replace printed content by digital media. Only in this way can knowledge transfer function flexibly and relatively simply. Means for digital learning include, for example, virtual classrooms for pupils to be able to learn independent of location. This requires end devices or Internet-enabled computer hardware in a TCP/IP

⁹⁰ Objectives in this context are, for example, increasing motivation, changing behaviour, etc. Acquiring knowledge (playfully), e.g. about political content, etc., is also a good way to acquire knowledge in different contexts (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 10 f).

⁹¹ It is therefore necessary to deal with best practice examples or practice-oriented expert tips, teaching projects, working materials etc. The main objective is to educate pupils and students across all subjects and school types to become critical, responsible media recipients. In the context of digital media, the students should be able to form their own reflected opinion and select media offers from the complex media landscape ([https://www. lehrer-online.de](https://www.lehrer-online.de)>kritische medienreflexion in schule und unterricht-lehrer-online, p 1 ff).

network. These are, for example, desktop computers, laptops, smartphones, tablets, etc. ([https:// m.sgd.de>digitales -lernen](https://m.sgd.de/digitales-lernen), p 1 ff).

As an agency of the ministry in charge, the OeAD supports the initiative of the Austrian Federal Government "Digital Learning". This is also part of the "8-Point Plan for Digital Education" in the Austrian school system with essential goals that also include the equipment with digital end devices. In addition to creating pedagogical and technical conditions, it is essential to enable digital education for learners on equal terms (Digitaleslernen. oead.at p 1).

In the context of digital learning or digital education, for example, the so-called "peer learning" is of topical relevance. Social networks also play an important role in this context. The first result of any learning process is ideally the "gain of knowledge"; "experiential knowledge" is subsequently also important, which should then lead to a sustainable learning effect. In the future, "enterprise-social-network-solutions" will probably become increasingly important, because the participants can basically expect good learning results through a structured exchange between the learners and those people who have already gained experiences in the learned subject area. This is "peer learning" in an optimised form, such as "learning communities" (virtual classrooms) using virtual tools. Here, formal and informal learning processes are combined in the sense of "social learning". Learners create learning content collaboratively (user-generated content) and share insights etc. on a learning platform, but above all knowledge (content sharing). A major advantage in this context is that implemented "cloud solutions" give learners and teachers the opportunity to easily and effectively exchange content with each other and make it available at any time (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 10 f).

The creation and establishment of "communities of practice" is becoming increasingly important. Here, impact correlations and new application methods are tested through personal interaction, and tutors are appointed. "Blended learning" will increase in extent. Here, it is essential to combine face-to-face events and digital learning in a way that makes sense in terms of learning psychology using new

information and communication media ⁹² (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 11).

3.2. Learning management systems for the educational sector

Learning management systems, among other things, are helpful in achieving goals and optimising (possible) potentials in the context of digital media in the classroom. Schulmeister's definition of learning management systems is of current importance for the education sector and teaching. Here, learning platforms or learning management systems - in contrast to mere collections of teaching scripts or hypertext collections on web servers - are called "software systems" that have certain functions. These comprise user administration (login via encryption), course administration (courses, content administration, file administration), assignment of roles and rights including differentiated rights, communication methods (chat or forums) and tools for learning and note-taking (e.g. whiteboard, notebook, calendar, etc.), the presentation of course content, learning objects and media in a network-compatible browser, the storage of relevant data such as the knowledge or learning level of students (Schulmeister 2003, p 1ff).

In some areas of education, educators are already required to know the functions of learning platforms or learning management systems. This requires a thorough engagement with this topic. Learning platforms or learning management systems enable digital communication. They offer functions in the context of documents, for example, to organise them, to work on them, to file them, and so on. In many cases, LMSs can be used to create learning units (e.g. courses), to assign materials (e.g. videos, links, PDFs) to these learning units, to share them with a specific group of pupils or students, etc. In addition, LMSs can also have functionalities for keeping shared calendars, creating and evaluating interactive assignments, setting up tests, communicating with each other in a forum (e.g. via e-

⁹² Here, the online phases serve to deepen the acquisition or or to prepare the transfer of new knowledge. Face-to-face meetings are then intended for the exchange of experiences. In addition, the very similar "scrum workshops" are also of interest in practice. These are supported by specially trained "scrum masters". Collaboration is essential here (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 11 f).

mail, chat, etc.), assigning homework to students, etc.

The interest in and approaches to learning management systems or educational clouds can differ significantly. For users, it is always necessary to consider what is already available at the school and what is needed. In principle, a simple LMS is sufficient for the exchange and administration of documents. However, if teachers are supposed to accompany the learning and working process of the pupils via the learning platform with teaching material and feedback, an LMS with a wide range of functions will be required. There are already numerous providers for the education sector. For educators, the well-considered selection of an LMS, the planning of the school development process, innovative teaching concepts, etc. are always of importance. Learning with digital media requires interest, especially also in information technologies, as well as adaptation measures and competences on the part the actors.⁹³

Learning management systems (LMS) or learning platforms have existed for many years and are web-based. All that different actors (teachers, pupils, students) require in order to use these LMSs, is an internet connection and a normal web browser. They are standard in the university sector, at teacher training colleges, universities of applied sciences, etc. At general education schools (AHS/MS) and vocational schools and colleges (BMHS) they are becoming increasingly important.⁹⁴

⁹³ A good example among the providers in the field of education is "on.Lernen in der digitalen Welt", a magazine published quarterly in print and digitally, is. This magazine addresses stakeholders who want to optimise education in the context of schools. A current topic is, for example, how the potential of digital technologies can be used for school lessons. In addition, how pupils can be enabled to use digital media creatively and competently. This means digitally supported teaching processes that can be of advantage for all types of schools and school levels. Services are, for example, innovative concepts for teaching with digital media, investigation of the potential of digital innovations for school teaching, basic knowledge on digitisation, selection of digital materials, apps, tools, etc. (on.learning in the digital world) (<https://www.friedrich-verlag.de/lms-das-richtige-lern-management-system-finden>, p 1 ff).

⁹⁴ Germany is a shining example in this respect, with its DigitalPakt Schule, which aims to bring the digital infrastructure in schools up to a modern standard. The establishment and further development of pedagogical work and communication platforms is promoted here (<https://www.digitalpaktschule.de>, p 1 ff).

3.3. Legal foundations in the context of digitalisation and digital media

3.3.1 Legal issues as complex challenges

Actors in the context of (digital) education in the school sector are also confronted with legal issues. In particular, the high availability of digital media and their increasing interactivity give rise to legal challenges that can also be very complex. This includes, above all, the areas of data protection, protection of minors and personal rights, copyright and licensing law. Here it is necessary to inform and support pupils, teachers, school administrators and parents. Involvement in (school) multiplier networks as well as lectures by "experts" in relevant areas of law, crime prevention etc. can be useful in this context ("Beschluss der Kultusministerkonferenz vom 8.März 2012", p 8).

Relevant areas of law are also affected by the publication of content relevant for teaching. Here, for example, guidelines and recommendations for schools or school lessons are also essential. The "Internet Policy" should correspond to the interests of the school partners or actors who use the relevant technologies ("Empfehlungen zur Nutzung digitaler Technologie an Schulstandorten", BMBWF-9.000/0025-Präs/15/2018).

However, the possibilities for use vary considerably. The reproduction of own materials prepared for teaching is basically possible without any problems. The publication of materials on a school homepage that is publicly accessible, however, presents a different legal situation. In this case "copyright" is, among other things, affected, which is why sources must be precisely indicated. This applies in particular to sketches and pictures used in lessons. Texts should ideally be formulated by the teachers themselves so that they are appropriate for their pupils or students. In the following, selected fields of law are presented, which, however, can also be subject to changes, which is why, at least in cases of doubt, an assessment by lawyers specialising in this field is necessary ("Empfehlungen zur Nutzung digitaler Technologie an Schulstandorten, BMBWF-9.000/0025-Präs/15/2018").

3.3.2 The topic of media law

a) A cross-sectional matter:

In many areas of life, digitalisation has already made it possible in to distribute intellectual content in word, image and sound via different networks and to receive it by means of different technical devices. Technical innovations develop very quickly in this context; they also influence media law or media activities. In a legal sense or from a legal point of view, media law is not a uniform area of law but a "cross-sectional matter" that includes "criminal law", "civil law" and "public law". In Austria, the legal basis for media law is the "Media Act" (MedienG). Essential are in particular copyright law, data protection law, press and personality law, broadcasting law, internet and domain law, software law, IT intellectual property law, IT contract law, and competition law. In addition, the standards relevant to the use of digital media in the specific education system are, of course, essential.⁹⁵

b) Protection of personality in media law:

Sections 6 ff of the Media Act contain regulations concerning the protection of personality. These are "Defamation, insult, libel and ridicule (section 6 of the Media Act), Violation of the strictly personal sphere (section 7 of the Media Act), Protection against publication of identity in special cases (§ 7a of the Media Act), protection of the presumption of innocence (§ 7b of the Media Act) and protection against unauthorized publication (§ 7c of the Media Act)".

However, protection of personality does not always apply. For example, it does not apply "for persons in the public eye if the public had a predominant interest in the publication" (§ 7a item 1 of the Media Law).

"Provisions on the protection of personality include essential rules that provide for a balancing of interests based on grounds for exclusion" (see §§ 6 ff of the Media Act).

"Each person not only generally affected by facts published a periodical

⁹⁵ The "Mediengesetz" (Media Law) is aimed at "ensuring the freedom of the media in order to secure the right to freedom of expression". It also includes rules on the protection of the journalistic profession (Federal Act of 12 June 1981. MedienG. BGBl. No. 314/1981).

medium product is entitled to the publication of a reply in such a medium free of charge, unless such reply is not true or its publication is excluded for other reasons" (section 9 of the Media Act).

3.3.3 The topic of data protection

In the context of the legal basis of media use and the use of digital media, some areas are of fundamental importance for educators. Since the introduction of the EU General Data Protection Regulation, schools, for example, have to take data protection issues into account and implement innovations. The topic of digitalisation has been current for many years (EU Data Protection Regulation).⁹⁶ (EU-DSGVO).

Many digital offers are already utilized in school lessons; for example, the internet is commonplace for teachers, pupils and students. The topic of data protection in schools is of topical relevance and requires knowledge. Examples of applications in everyday school life are the digital class book, the use of clouds, online learning platforms etc. In compliance with the data protection regulations at schools, data that is (administratively) necessary may usually be processed. However, a precise examination of the specific case is always necessary (Datenschutz. org, Schule, p 1).

Data protection on the Internet is a very current topic in the education sector; it refers to the application of data protection with regard to data transmitted over the Internet. This includes the application of control over the type and amount of information that is released about a person on the Internet. It also includes who has access to this information. Data protection in the context of the Internet is a subcategory of "computer data protection". People who are involved in the topic data protection on the Internet also point out privacy risks. These are (potential) consequences related to the use of the Internet. In the case of infringements, "specialists", such as lawyers specialising in this field, etc., should be consulted (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

⁹⁶ In the school sector, the collection and processing of personal data is necessary. Information that is not absolutely necessary may only be collected with prior consent. The security of the data used must be guaranteed (<https://www.datenschutz.org/schule/>, p 1).

3.3.4 The topic of internet law

a) A variety of different fields of law:

Some knowledge of Internet law is of advantage in particular for educators. Of course, specialists in this field of law, such as lawyers, etc., are required when dealing with specific legal questions or legal problems. As pupils are legally responsible for tortious acts ("deliktsfähig") from the age of 14, certain contents should also be addressed by teachers in class, especially in order to avoid "misconduct".⁹⁷

"Internet law" is also referred to as "online law"; it deals with legal problems related to the use of the internet. It is not a separate area of law, but a cross-section of all fields of law surrounding the internet. It consists of a variety of different areas of law. Examples include general and special civil law (ABGB, KSchG, UGB, Signaturgesetz), copyright law (UrhG, Musterschutzgesetz), competition law (UWG, Markenschutzgesetz 1970), criminal law (StGB, Zugangskontrollgesetz, Verbotsgesetz), data protection law (DSG, Telekommunikationsgesetz 2003, E-Commerce-Gesetz), media law etc. (Wikipedia.org, Internetrecht, p 1 f).

The examples mentioned here are meant to illustrate that in the context of education, legal norms and their knowledge are also essential for the actors. Teaching content can be illustrated by educators in different ways. In addition to textbooks, etc., digital media such as the internet can also serve to impart knowledge. In this context, copyright law, for example, is very important. It protects works of art, literature and science from unauthorised use. The use of corresponding texts, images, etc. is therefore usually only permitted with the prior consent of the author or

⁹⁷ The capacity to commit unlawful acts ("Deliktsfähigkeit") or criminal liability ("Strafmündigkeit") is the ability to recognise that an act is unlawful and to act in accordance with this insight. Adolescents are capable of committing an offence ("deliktsfähig") from the age of 14. The capacity to commit unlawful acts ("Deliktsfähigkeit") does not only depend on age, however; a restriction can also exist, for example, in the case of mentally ill persons. However, the assessment requires a medical opinion (<https://www.oesterreich.gv.at>> Deliktsfähigkeit, p 1).

creator.⁹⁸

b) Internet and criminal law:

Numerous correlations between the Internet and criminal law exist. This concerns, for example, EU criminal law (e.g. EU cybercrime Law and EU legislative acts), Austrian criminal law (e.g. offences of cybercrime), etc. In addition, offences such as defamation, libel and slander are also relevant. Pupils and students should be made aware that untrue allegations, defamation or ridicule not only offend people, but can also cause damage. This includes material and immaterial damage. In addition, hatred on the internet is a current topic, including national socialist and racist content as well as cyber-bullying, incitement to hatred, etc. This should be addressed in the context of school lessons, especially in politics lessons, etc. (Rechtsinformationssystem...; see also Internet4jurists.at, Criminal Law, p 1 f).

3.3.5 EXCURSUS: Violence on the Net. A current topic in the context of pedagogy and criminal law

The criminal relevance of violence on the net

Pupils, students and educators can also be exposed to attacks (violence) when using digital media. Examples include cyber-bullying, threats, sexual harassment, etc. However, they can also be liable to prosecution themselves, for example as accomplices, perpetrators or bystanders. From the age of 14, persons are legally responsible for tortious acts ("deliktsfähig") and are therefore also criminally responsible for their actions (and omissions) (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

The subject of "cyber-bullying", for example, is particularly topical. One important aspect here is that a person is insulted, harassed or shamed online

⁹⁸ It does not matter whether the work was published in a book or on the internet. However, according to the law, teaching at schools and other educational institutions is not public, and some content may therefore be used to illustrate teaching without the author's consent being required. However, there are special regulations on this, such as limitations on scope, etc. Educators are required to deal with this, also with possible changes in the legal situation. In any case, specialists are needed for legal problems (<https://www.news4teachers.de>>urheberrecht im Internet, p 1 f).

over a longer period of time and in front of many people - especially in a social network. Since 1 January 2016, cyber-bullying has been anchored as a separate criminal offence in the Criminal Code: "Fortgesetzte Belästigung im Wege einer Telekommunikation oder eines Computersystems" ("Continued harassment using telecommunications or a computer system", § 107c StGB). § Section 107c StGB stipulates as follows:

- „strafbare Handlungen gegen die Ehre einer Person für eine größere Zahl von Menschen für eine längere Zeit wahrnehmbar begeht (§ 107c Abs. 1 Z 1) oder

- eine Tatsache oder Bildaufnahme des höchstpersönlichen Lebensbereichs einer Person ohne deren Zustimmung für eine größere Zahl von Menschen für längere Zeit wahrnehmbar macht“ (§ 107c Abs. 1 Z 2).

sofern dies

- „im Wege einer Telekommunikation oder eines Computersystems geschieht

- und zwar auf eine die Lebensführung des Opfers unzumutbar zu beeinträchtigen geeignete Weise“ (§ 107c StGB).

In Austria, it is clearly demonstrated that there is a clear commitment to zero tolerance against violence at school. Since 2008, the BMBWF has been implementing the National Strategy for the Prevention of Violence in Schools (BMBWF 2008).

This was an essential step because violence causes great damage, including long-term damage. The many possible forms and mechanisms of violence are described, among others, in the definition of the World Health Organisation (WHO) as follows: "Violence is the intentional use of physical and psychological force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community, that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal-development or deprivation. " (WHO, Definition).

It can be derived from this definition that violence is a targeted use of physical or/and psychological force or power, either threatened or actually applied. The harm can be directed against oneself, against other persons, groups of persons or even

communities. This WHO definition is very broad. The means used "physical violence" or/and "psychological violence" the persons harmed, the type of harm, etc. are also of relevance (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

In addition to "cyber bullying", "hate postings" are also relevant in the context of education or school. This can be done by means of a text, photo or video. Groups of people are attacked here because of their origin, religion, sexual orientation, etc. There can also be direct calls for violence against such a group. The criminally relevant norm is "incitement to hatred" ("Verhetzung", § 23 StGB).

In addition to "incitement to hatred", a "dangerous threat" may also be relevant. This applies when a person is threatened with violence (online). For example, threatening to forward nude videos of a person is relevant here as a dangerous threat (§107 StGB).

If a person is forced or coerced into an act by such a threat or by force, this constitutes "grave or sexual coercion" ("schwere oder geschlechtliche Nötigung"). For example, sending nude photos of oneself or performing other (sexual) acts. This can happen in real life or via webcam. This is "grave or sexual coercion" ("schwere oder geschlechtliche Nötigung" §§ 105, 106, 202 StGB).

In the context of online violence, "persistent stalking" ("Beharrliche Verfolgung") - harassment over a longer period of time via digital media - can also be relevant.⁹⁹ (§ 107a StGB).

Knowledge about possible (criminal) consequences in the context of digital media or the internet is essential for educators, especially also for pupils in the upper grades and students. In principle, young people are only "capable of committing an offence" ("deliktsfähig") from the age of 14 (§ 74 StGB).

⁹⁹ "Beleidigung" ("Insult", § 115 StGB), "Üble Nachrede" ("Libel", § 111 StGB), "Kreditschädigung" ("Discredit", § 152 StGB) or "Verleumdung" ("Defamation", § 297 StGB) can also be punishable under criminal law. Here, threatening, insulting or untrue statements, photos and videos can be made offline as well as online. In addition to the listed norms and examples relevant to criminal law, several others may also be relevant in the context of online violence (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

"Deliktsfähigkeit" ("capacity to commit unlawful acts") in criminal law and in civil law:

"Deliktsfähigkeit" (the capacity to commit unlawful acts) is the ability to recognise that an act is unlawful and to act in accordance with this insight. From the age of 14, are "capable of unlawful acts" ("deliktsfähig"). They cannot be prosecuted, but educational measures are possible. For example, placement in a supervised shared accommodation, etc. (§ 74 StGB).

In the field of civil law, the "Deliktsfähigkeit" (capacity to commit unlawful acts) - like the capacity to contract - is part of the capacity to act. With the limit of the capacity to commit an unlawful act ("Deliktsfähigkeitsgrenze"), which is set at the age of 14, the Austria law aims at shielding young people from the full force of the law. As a rule, young people under the age of 14 cannot be held liable for damages. Compensation for damage caused is the responsibility of the parents if they have not fulfilled their duty of supervision. "Provided that a minor child cannot be attributed a fault earlier (§ 1310), he or she becomes legally responsible for tortious acts according to the provisions of tort law when he or she reaches the age of 14 (176 ABGB Deliktsfähigkeit des Kindes).

The "Verwaltungsstrafgesetz" (Administrative Penal Code) may also have further legal relevance for pupils and students. Section 4 of the VStG stipulates that "Persons not having completed their 14th year of age when committing the offence are not subject to punishment". Section 58 of the VStG (special provision for juveniles) also stipulates in para. 2 that "Juvenile offenders who have not yet completed their 16th year of age at the time the offence was committed may not be sentenced to detention or imprisonment. A sentence of detention of up-to two weeks may be imposed on other juvenile offenders if this is necessary for special reasons; this does not affect the execution of a term of substitute confinement which however also must not exceed two weeks.¹⁰⁰ (§ 4 and § 58 VStG).

¹⁰⁰ "If the offender was 14 years old at the time of the offence, but not yet 18 years old (juvenile), the offence is not attributed to him if he was not mature enough for special reasons to understand the unlawfulness of the offence or to act in accordance with this understanding". According to § 5 No. 2 of the "Jugendgerichtsgesetz 1988", the maximum penalty is ten years, and from the age of 16 fifteen years (Jugendgerichtsgesetz 1988).

3.4. Analysis of scientific studies

3.4.1 Fundamentals for the practice

"Digitalisation" and the "use of digital media" are controversially discussed in the context of science; this applies in particular to computers, the internet, smartphones, etc. Here, the question of digital, analogue or a combination of both is also essential. Basically, it can be stated that it does not make sense to digitalise all lessons, nor should digital media be banned from the classrooms across the board. This topic is very complex and a challenge especially for teachers in the teaching context. Finding the right balance is not so easy, even though it can have positive effects (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

However, there are fundamentally significant differences in the field of existing information technologies and the training of educators at a specific school in the context of digitalisation and the use of digital media. The digital infrastructure and the actors are essential for success. It is assumed that the examination of meta-studies and individual findings can lead to significant insights, which is why the implementation and results of selected studies are shown below (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

3.4.2. The selected studies: metastudies and individual findings

In this paper, meta-studies and individual findings on specific topics were examined and reflected upon. Meta-analyses are a part or subsection of systematic reviews. They serve to statistically summarise individual results from several independent studies in order to increase the significance compared to individual studies. Meta-analyses calculate an overall cross-study result from the individual studies (Wissenwaswirkt. org, Netzwerkmetaanalysen: wie man vergleichen kann, was nie verglichen wurde, p 1).

"Meta-analyses" examine the results of numerous studies and combine them. This makes it possible to specify a common value, e.g. for the effectiveness of the use of media - the "effect size". In the individual studies, the effectiveness of the use of media is determined by scientific tests. The results of the "intervention group" are compared with the results of a control group. Studies that only examine subjectively

perceived competence gains are not taken into account (Schaumburg 2018, p 27 ff).

The meta-analyses examined in this thesis only refer to gains in subject-specific competences; the generic competences are explicitly not taken into account. However, the author assumes that interdisciplinary competences are very essential in the context of digital media in school lessons. Especially computer- and information-related interdisciplinary competences (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

3.4.2.1 Meta studies

a) Meta study: "Invisible Learning" (Hattie-Studie, John Hattie 2009)

Implementation:

The study "Invisible Learning" by John Hattie, an educational scientist, is a so-called meta-meta analysis or an analysis of meta analyses. Numerous meta-studies are examined or compared here. The research interest was the investigation of factors that influence the learning effectiveness of teaching, here also relating to the investigation of the use of different digital media (Visible-learning.org, Hattie-ranking, p 1 ff).

Hattie examined a total of eighty-one (81) meta-analyses concerning the "effects of computer support on students' learning effectiveness", which included a total of four thousand eight hundred and seventy-five (4875) studies. Hattie took a very differentiated view of computer-assisted teaching. Among the prerequisites for positive effects, he saw the need for different teaching strategies, "pre-training" for the use of computers for the actors, for multiple learning opportunities, that learners have control over learning, that peer learning and feedback are optimised (Hattie 2013, p 261). The analysis of meta-analyses referred to the effectiveness with regard to subject-related performances. The review was based on (standardised) performance tests. The effect size (Cohen's d) as a measure of effectiveness is independent of the sample size and independent of the measurement unit in the original study (Hattie: Visible Learning, 2009; 2018).

Results:

Table 2: Hattie Study. Effect size of digital media

CONCEPTS OF DIGITAL LEARNING	EFFECT SIZE	META STUDIES	EXAMINATION TIME
Interactive learning videos	0,52 (medium)	6	1980-1999
Computer-assisted teaching	0,37 (small)	76	1977-2007
Simulations	0,33 (small)	9	1981-2002
Programmed instruction	0,24 (small)	7	1977-2000
Web-based learning	0,18 (very small)	3	2002-2006

Source: http://waxmann.clando.com/img/books/extract/3830987579_lp.pdf

This table shows that the number of meta-studies in the research area "Computer-assisted teaching" is the highest with the number of meta-studies (76). From this it can be deduced that there is a particular research interest here on the topic of improving digital learning. Other concepts studied generated the result or the following order:

Simulations (9), instruction (7), interactive learning videos (6) and web-based learning (3). The Hattie study provided / provides valuable insights concerning the investigation of the "effect size of digital media". One of the findings was that learning supported by digital media has a fundamentally positive effect on learners' (pupils') subject-related performances. This can be assumed for all concepts of digital learning investigated by Hattie. It can be deduced from the table that the effect sizes of digital media are not very large. In this scientific study, Hattie set the value 0.40 as the threshold value, which can be considered as strong and practically significant. The value 0.40 is the medium effect size of all measures examined by Hattie. Values below 0.40 mean a below-average effect, values above 0.40 mean an above-average effect (see Hattie Study. Effektstärke digitaler Medien.¹⁰¹

The effect for web-based learning in the context of Hattie's research showed a

¹⁰¹ Criticism of the Hattie study was voiced, for example, by Mc Elvany et al, who found, among other things, that the concepts of digital learning examined predominantly had a below-average effect in relation to or in comparison with other measures (for improving learning performance). Moreover, only a few concepts of digital learning were examined and years have already passed (research status: 2009) (Mc Elvany et al 2018, p 1 ff; p 29).

very small effect with ($d=0.18$). One of Hattie's assumptions here was that this result was due to the relatively new technology. He assumes that as educators become more experienced, the potential of web-based learning can be enhanced by improving the bandwidth and learning opportunities (Hattie 2013, p 268 f).

The investigation of interactive learning videos or the area of support through technologies or information technologies generated an effect of ($d=0.52$), which is a medium effect. Here it can be assumed that the visualisation of the content brings advantages (Hattie study 2013).

The main achievements of John Hattie are that he "focused on and analysed the use of digital media in teaching. In his meta-study "Visible Learning - Lernen sichtbar machen" (Making Learning Visible), he created a ranking list of various factors influencing learning success at school. He examined meta-analyses in terms of their effect size and ranked them on a scale from very positive effects to negative effects. The average effect of all influencing variables is 0.40. A crucial question in the context of this research performed by Hattie is, among other things, "What really makes a difference in terms of learning success?" The effects of the studies used or included resulted in effect sizes between ($d=0.20$) and ($d=0.60$). The average of all meta-analyses was ($d=0.37$) (Hattie 2013, p 261).

b) Meta-study: Extension of the Hattie study. Heike Schaumburg (2018)

Implementation:

In 2018, Heike Schaumburg extended the Hattie study. Schaumburg's research intention was to investigate whether different results could be expected when examining further concepts of digital learning - including new research results. Concepts of digital learning (flipped classroom, game-based learning) as well as different equipment concepts such as laptops, tablets and interactive whiteboards) were added. This meta-study was intended to achieve "empirical findings on the effectiveness of different concepts of digitally supported learning" (Schaumburg 2018, p 27 ff).

Results:

The main conclusion was that learning effectiveness is influenced by a multitude of factors. A negative effect of digital media could not be found in any meta-analysis. However, the number of effects that can be achieved - regardless of measures or concepts - is often rather small. It is noteworthy that the small effects were found more often in more recent studies than in older studies. Explanations for these results related, among other things, to the complexity of their use in the classroom. The technical requirements (hardware and software) are also essential for exploiting the potential of digital media to support learning. In addition, the (different) learning requirements of the pupils, specific lesson contents, methodological-didactic considerations, etc. must be taken into account. The competences, attitude towards digital media, motivation, willingness to innovate, etc. of the educators are also essential (Schaumburg 2018, p. 27 ff).

This research has shown that the use of digital media in the classroom has an overall positive effect on learners' academic performance, and that there is no generally negative influence on learning effectiveness. Measured in terms of effort and costs, the positive effects are below average compared to other measures. Variable effectiveness of "equipment concepts" was not detected. Educators and teaching methods play a central role. With regard to the types of teaching, the potential of digital media is not as well exploited in "teacher-centred teaching" as in "pupil-centred teaching". In student-centred forms of teaching, learners basically need individual support from teachers and/or fellow students. It is necessary to prepare, accompany and evaluate the use of digital media well (Schaumburg 2018, p. 27 ff).

In the field of educational research, the research findings of Heike Schaumburg on the topic of potentials and risks of digital media in the classroom are, in any case, significant. In Schaumburg's own opinion, research on digital media indicates that educators are very decisive. It is not (only) the media themselves that are important, but how they are integrated into the classroom. Digital media are not good or bad per se; they have to be well selected and prepared. This requires adaptations or competencies on the part of the actors, especially interested, motivated and well-

trained educators (Zeilner, 1991-2015; see Heike Schaumburg, Humboldt University of Berlin, 2019).

c) Meta-study: Use of digital media in mathematics and science teaching at secondary level (ZIB/TUM study)

Implementation:

The so-called "ZIB/TUM Study" is a "meta-study on the learning effectiveness of digital media in secondary mathematics and science teaching". The researchers and authors assumed as a theoretical background that especially "science subjects" such as "biology", "chemistry", "physics" and "mathematics" have a lot of potential for positive effects of digital media. There have already been numerous studies that examined the conditions for positive (learning) effects through digital media in mathematics and science lessons. However, the results of such studies did not provide a unified picture. The authors refer here, for example, to literature by Özyurt, Perry & Steck, etc. They assumed that in previous meta-analyses on the research topic, only certain subjects or types of learning programmes were of research interest. In particular, only studies from certain countries were included in analyses. The ZIB/TUM study is based on a larger data set resulting from research of international literature. In this meta-study, the researchers used a total of seventy-nine (79) individual studies published from 2000 to 2016 following a peer-review process. These studies examined the subjects "mathematics", "physics", "biology" and "chemistry" (ZIB/TUM study).

The study investigated the (possible) effects of digital media on the performance of secondary school students in the "intervention group" compared to the "control group", which did not use digital media. Only studies based on a "pre-post control group design" were included in the analysis. Two independent "raters" coded the data and a "random effects model" was used to calculate the effects (ZIB/TUM study).

Results:

The calculation of the overall effects shows "that the use of digital media in mathematics and science lessons has a positive, moderately strong effect ($g=.62$, $p<.001$; $k=80$)" on learning performance. Positive effects were found for all investigated subjects and for all school levels in secondary education. "A small positive overall effect ($g=.41$, $p<.05$; $k=13$) was demonstrated with regard to the attitude towards the subject" (<https://www.researchgate.net>>; see also DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13319.70561).

Overall, positive effects of digital media in "mathematics and science subjects" were revealed concerning the performance and motivation of secondary school students. In particular, the communication among students is encouraged; teachers have to deal with content, etc. It must be noted that even after analysing this meta-study, "no generally valid statement can be made as to what positive effects can be achieved through digital media in mathematics and science teaching". This is substantiated in particular by the numerous available and different learning programmes. However, the results of this meta-study and the survey among educators have provided specific orientation on how the use of digital media can be a valuable support for teachers and learners. These empirically derived conclusions can be beneficial for the subjects and actors mentioned. Digital media must above all be adapted to the "individual prerequisites of the students" and integrated into the lessons in a way that is "tailored to the specific learning content" (Zeilner, 1991-2015; see Hillmayr et al. 2017, p 26 f).

The selection and preparation or the design of the use in class by the educators is essential for success. It can be assumed that a well-balanced ratio of digital and traditional (analogue) teaching materials generally brings advantages. However, it is not possible to precisely determine this ratio. In science subjects, the use of digital media in the teaching context has fundamentally better effects on the performance and motivation of the students than in other subjects. However, a generally valid statement cannot be made in this regard (Zeilner, 1991-2015).

d) Meta-study: “How effective are digital media in the classroom?” Bardo Herzig (2014).

Implementation:

This study investigated the effectiveness of digital media in the context of teaching. Various individual case studies or meta-studies were analysed. Various possible influencing factors were examined in this research, namely the "digital media" themselves, the "teaching processes" and "the actors involved in teaching" or the "teachers" and "learners". In the course of this study - which was commissioned by the Bertelsmann Stiftung - the status of research was also presented through numerous further literature references (Herzig 2014, p 22 ff).

Results:

The "digital media" themselves, the "teaching processes" and "the actors directly involved in teaching" are constitutive factors for effects of digital media. However, these factors must be further differentiated in order to be able to assess "direct or indirect effects on possible learning outcomes of students". Since the impact of digital media is very context-dependent, general statements can hardly be made. The results of the research refer to the "level of the individual, the teaching processes, the school (the institution) and the perspective of meta-analyses". Pupil groups benefit most from the use of digital media, even though this cannot be generally substantiated with group-specific characteristics. The examination of individual factors, however, enables to determine individual effects, especially on learning success. An important predictor of learning success is the "prior thematic and media-related knowledge". Pupils who already have better prior knowledge can also benefit most from digital media offers/learning offers. This can be justified in particular by the fact that new bodies of knowledge meet with existing prior knowledge and can be built upon or integrated into. However, prior knowledge is generally a significant predictor of learning success and not only in the context of digital media. In addition, media-specific attitudes are also essential, i.e. what attitude do students have towards a digital medium as a learning medium. The difference

between image and text media is also relevant here. Another important influencing variable is the students' self-direction and learning strategies, as well as motivation and interest. However, prior knowledge and self-direction skills are the most important factors explaining inter-individual differences in the context of learning with digital media. This also applies to socio-economic factors, etc.

The decision to use digital media in teaching as an "instrument" or "object" has an impact on different levels. Here, a distinction is also made between the levels of organisational development, personnel development and teaching development (Herzig 2014).

In the field of empiricism, the discussion of (possible) consequences and challenges brought about the result that "the question regarding the effects of digital media in teaching cannot be discussed in isolation with regard to the technical medium, but only in systemic contexts in a meaningful way". There is sufficient empirical evidence for specific effects of digital media to support learning in teaching and learning processes; however, statements can neither be generalised with regard to individual media offers nor with regard to specific groups of pupils nor with regard to specific subjects, nor with regard to different subjects or subject disciplines."

In the field of research, "media-supported teaching-learning scenarios" should continue to be developed and examined with regard to their effects. The examination of specific conditions is very essential here, especially with feedback processes to people working in the field. "School learning processes" and "informal learning processes" must be more strongly correlated to each other (Herzig 2014, p 22 ff).

3.4.2.2 Individual case studies

a) Individual case study (2016): "Internet use and media literacy of young people in Austria" (IFES)

Implementation:

In the context of this study conducted in 2016, a total of 439 people between the ages of 14 and 20 were interviewed throughout Austria. The topic of the study was "Internet and media literacy". The study also includes specific questions on the

topics of "internet use, being affected by cyber-bullying and interest in net-political topics". In addition, "questions concerning suggestions and a better anchoring and teaching of media competence in the Austrian education system". The study examined "how the respondents evaluate "digital skills" in their social environment, what they learn in school with regard to media education and what they increasingly wish for in this context". The study was presented on 24.1.2017.

Results:

An essential result is that most young people assess their skills as very good, but have taught themselves a lot. "Peers" are the "reference group" with the highest competences. Increased media education at school was stated as a wish of many young people interviewed. The desire to improve relevant competences of educators is particularly strong. This also concerns intergenerational learning and peer-to-peer learning. Regarding the "technical equipment of schools", there is room for improvement in the view of the persons questioned, for example "WLAN" and "technical devices". Media education should already be relevant at lower school levels. This study also shows, among other things, that media education needs a higher priority in the school and extra-curricular environment (Study Forschungsinstitut IFES, 2017; see also Ifes.at, Studie-meinnetz Internetnutzung Medienkompetenz Junger Menschen, p 1 ff).

Good insights were gained on "how the pupils questioned assess their digital skills, how they assess them in their social environment, what they learn in their own school on the topic of media education and what they increasingly wish for in this context". This should be discussed further and also inspire further research.

b) Individual case study: "How fit are Austrian schools for the digital world?" (OMG-Study):

Implementation:

In the course of this OMG study, 805 people were interviewed, including about 200 second secondary school students, 100 educators and 500 people from the parental sector. The study was presented by the Innovationsstiftung für Bildung

(Innovation Foundation for Education), which focuses on raising educational standards and innovation skills in education.

Results:

Seventy-six (76) per cent of Austrian pupils stated that they spend more than three hours a day in front of a computer, laptop, tablet, smartphone, etc. for school purposes. About seventy (70) per cent of all respondents said they were satisfied with the technical equipment of the hardware in the schools. However, two thirds of the teachers believe that they are not sufficiently trained for digital teaching or that they do not have sufficient basic knowledge of such learning materials. It is noteworthy that even about half of these teachers were under thirty (30) years old. Eighty-two (82) per cent of the educators called for an increased focus on digital training for educators. There were considerable differences in perception among students and educators, especially concerning the topic of new digital learning materials in the classroom. The study also demonstrates that about half of the students surveyed use free programmes from the internet for school activities - in addition to software from the school - because these are not sufficiently available at their school. Media competence - in this case learning critical media consumption for the following professional life - was essential for about ninety (90) percent of the persons questioned. However, only about fifty-three (53) per cent of the teachers, sixty-one (61) per cent of the students and twenty per cent (20) of the parents regarded the competences taught at school as essential.

Among other things, this study also reveals the lack of competence of teachers and the lack of materials that represent obstacles for digital teaching (OMG study).

Conclusions and Recommendations from Chapter III

Changes in school teaching due to digitalisation:

The complexity and speed of change processes in the global and digital world in the context of digitalisation in education also requires adaptation measures on the part of the actors. In particular, also as a result of rapid developments in the field of technology and the increasing importance of information technologies. In the field of education, the "digitalisation of educational processes", including the associated management tasks, is becoming increasingly important; "digital education" is very topical. This primarily involves the use of digital media and requires in particular a considered and critical approach to Internet sources, social media, etc. "Digital natives" are in great demand in the field of digital education, which requires both learning support and knowledge transfer by the educators, although learning support prevails once the pupils reach a certain level of proficiency. It can be stated, among other things, that digitalisation in the context of education or school was rather slow at the beginning; it must be seen as a development process. In this process, digital media are increasingly taking the place of analogue media, but they have not yet completely replaced them. The relationship between digital media and analogue media must be considered in a differentiated way - in general but also in the context of school lessons. Even though this topic is also discussed very controversially, it is necessary to discuss and develop teaching media and "school digital" constructively and discursively. If one examines previous developments in the context of digital media or computer-based media in the school sector, it can basically be stated that digitalisation here is primarily taking place through so-called driving forces or committed actors, such as educators in particular.

"Support structures" are clearly of relevance in this context. A functioning "IT support" is essential for an efficient and sustainable use of digital media. The necessary cooperation between school authorities and schools requires a clear distribution of roles and tasks and also includes a systematic organisation in order to be able to perform all tasks and measures with fundamentally increasing complexity from an economic point of view.

Education in the digital world requires concepts for action or media education

concepts for future developments and competences. The competence areas of "searching for, processing and storing information, communicating and cooperating, producing and presenting, protecting and acting safely, problem solving and acting as well as analysing and reflecting" are very essential in this context. Media education concepts are also important as instruments of school development, but this is a multi-dimensional school development process and must be understood in institutional terms. The specific school is the essential unit of design here. According to Schulz-Zander, the process of school development takes place in the context of five dimensions. These are organisational development, personnel development, teaching development, cooperation development and technology development. Cooperation between the actors is very crucial here, and can also take place within the scope of projects. The topic of "digitalisation in the education sector" should also be seen in a national, European, international and global context. This requires, among other things, quality-oriented and global learning; the potential of digital media to support learning should be exploited here, even though these are controversially discussed. When used correctly, digital media principally offer plenty of potential to support learning. However, learning guidance and knowledge transfer by educators are a necessity. "Global learning" means the attempt to respond – in accordance with pedagogical principles – to globalisation and the related increase in complexity. It aims to make this development an object of experience and learning, which also means preparing pupils and students for a life in which they can act consciously, critically and flexibly. The way in which education is performed in a networked world, which also requires a new learning culture, is very important. New knowledge is being generated every day, new insights are being gained, etc. Pupils and students need to understand global issues in their complexity and be able to reflect critically on them. In the "digital age", global learning is already a fixed component in the Austrian and worldwide education systems. Digital media are already absolutely essential in this context. Like "modern" or "virtual" learning environments, they are also changing subject-didactic approaches, contents and methods of teaching.

In addition to the topics of quality-oriented and global learning, it is also essential to point out that the learning culture is undergoing a lot of changes. This

affects the education sector in many countries and also their working lives. For example, developments in the context of digitalisation not only influence teaching/learning methods and collaboration methods, they also determine how people will learn in the future. This means new challenges and very likely less learning or training with a fundamentally high number of face-to-face events paving the way for a culture where working and learning merge into each other.

In the context of digital learning or digital education, for example, the so-called "peer learning" is of topical relevance. Social networks also play an important role in this context. The first result of any learning process is ideally the "gain of knowledge"; "experiential knowledge" is subsequently also important, which should then lead to a sustainable learning effect. In the future, "enterprise-social-network-solutions" will probably become increasingly important, because the participants can basically expect good learning results through a structured exchange between the learners and those people who have already gained experiences in the learned subject area. This is "peer learning" in an optimised form, such as "learning communities" (virtual classrooms) using virtual tools. Here, formal and informal learning processes are combined in the sense of "social learning". Learners create learning content collaboratively (user-generated content) and share insights etc. on a learning platform, but above all knowledge (content sharing). A major advantage in this context is that implemented "cloud solutions" give learners and teachers the opportunity to easily and effectively exchange content with each other and make it available at any time (Weg in die Wirtschaft, 6/2018, p 10 f).

Learning Management Systems:

Learning management systems, among other things, are helpful in achieving goals and optimising (possible) potentials in the context of digital media in the classroom. Schulmeister's definition of learning management systems is of topical relevance for the education and teaching sector. Here, "learning platforms" or "learning management systems" - in contrast to mere collections of teaching scripts or hypertext collections on web servers - are referred to as "software systems" which have specific functions. Interest in and access to learning management systems or

educational clouds vary greatly in practice. For the users it is always necessary to consider what is already available at the school and what is needed. Learning management systems (LMS) or learning platforms have existed for many years and are web-based. The actors (teachers, pupils, students) only require an internet connection and a normal web browser in order to be able to use these LMSs. In the university sector, at teacher training colleges, universities of applied sciences, etc. they are already part of the standard of teaching and learning. they are becoming increasingly important at AHS/MS and BMHS.

Legal foundations in the context of digitalisation and digital media:

Actors in the context of (digital) education in the school sector are also confronted with legal issues. In particular, the high availability of digital media and their increasing interactivity give rise to legal challenges that can also be very complex. This includes, above all, the areas of data protection, protection of minors and personal rights, copyright and licensing law. Here it is necessary to inform and support pupils, teachers, school administrators and parents. Involvement in (school) multiplier networks as well as lectures by "experts" in relevant areas of law, crime prevention etc. can be useful in this context. Relevant areas of law are also affected by the publication of subject didactic-pedagogical content. Here, for example, guidelines and recommendations in the context of teaching-related internet services and data services at schools are also essential.

The topic of "media law" is relevant in the field of education when using (digital) media. Digitalisation has already made it possible to distribute intellectual content in word, image and sound via various networks and to receive it by means of different technical devices. Technical innovations develop very quickly in this context, they also influence media law. In the legal sense, media law is not a uniform field of law but a "cross-sectional matter" that encompasses the legal fields of criminal law, civil law and public law. In Austria, the legal basis for media law is the "Media Act" (MedienG). Actors in the field of education should at least have a basic knowledge of relevant legal norms. These are in particular the copyright law, data protection law, press and personality law, broadcasting law, internet and domain law,

software law, IT intellectual property law, IT contract law, and competition law. In addition, the standards relevant to the use of digital media in the specific education system are of course essential. Data protection and copyright are of particular relevance, especially in the context of the Internet and the World Wide Web. The precise examination of a concrete problem case - especially by legal experts - is always necessary here. Internet law" or "online law" deals with legal problems related to the use of the internet. It is not a separate area of law, but the interface of all areas of law in the field of the internet. It consists of a large number of different areas of law. Examples include general and special civil law (ABGB, KSchG, UGB, Signaturgesetz), copyright law (UrhG, Musterschutzgesetz), competition law (UWG, Markenschutzgesetz 1970), criminal law (StGB, Zugangskontrollgesetz, Verbotsgesetz), data protection law (DSG, Telekommunikationsgesetz 2003, E-Commerce-Gesetz), media law, etc. The examples mentioned here should make clear that in the context of (digital) education, legal norms and their knowledge are also essential for the actors. Moreover, violence on the net is a current topic in the context of pedagogy and criminal law. Educators should address this in class and also point out possibilities for prevention.

The analysis of scientific studies:

The effectiveness or learning efficiency of "digital media" such as "computer", "internet", "smartphone" etc. is controversially discussed in science. Here, the question of digital, analogue or a combination of both is also essential. Basically, it can be stated that it does not make sense to digitalise all lessons, nor should digital media be banned from the classrooms across the board. This topic is very complex and a challenge especially for teachers in the teaching context. Finding the right balance is not so easy, but it can have positive effects. However, there are fundamentally significant differences in the field of existing information technologies and the training of educators at a specific school in the context of digitalisation and the use of digital media. The digital infrastructure and the actors are essential for success. It is assumed that the examination of meta-studies and individual findings can lead to significant insights. Meta-analyses are a part or subsection of systematic

reviews. They serve to statistically summarise individual results from several independent studies in order to increase the significance compared to individual studies. Meta-analyses calculate an overall cross-study result from the individual studies. Meta-analyses offset the results of many studies against one another; a common value can be indicated - in this case the effectiveness of the use of media, the "effect size". The meta-analyses examined in this thesis refer only to gains in subject-specific competences, the generic competences are explicitly not taken into account. However, the author assumes that generic competences are very essential in the context of digital media in school lessons. Especially computer- and information-related interdisciplinary competences.

The selected and examined meta-studies and the individual case studies are analysed within the framework of the overall research reflection (Conclusion) as the research guiding question.

CONCLUSION

Research question

What are the central areas of digital school development in the Austrian school system?

The examination of relevant research literature has revealed that the central areas of school development in the Austrian school system are personnel development, organisational development, teaching development, the development of relevant information technology as well as coordination and cooperation development.

A school development process is a multi-dimensional and institutional process. The essential design unit is the level of the specific school, which is, however, integrated into the overall system of education. These are primarily the competent Federal Ministry and the education directorates. However, the necessary development processes for digital school development are implemented at the specific school. Digitalisation in the context of schools does not only take place at the level of infrastructure and information technology; organisational, personnel and teaching development is also required in particular. The development of possible coordination and cooperation, also with private institutions, is of significant importance. School development processes can in principle also be divided into phases, which may overlap. Analogous to organisational development processes, initiation, implementation and institutionalisation are relevant here. The actors at a specific school are particularly decisive for success. This already concerns the planning and subsequent implementation and requires an understanding of structures, contexts, etc. The digital shift has already led to major changes in the education sector. Digitalisation here means much more than using digital tools in the classroom and requires school development processes. In particular, also to develop and use "media education concepts". A pedagogical concept and optimal technical equipment are required in order to acquire the necessary competences. In the context of pedagogy, information technologies, etc., it is essential to impart media education and media

literacy. Media literacy - in the context of digital school development - is an essential contribution to education here and requires well-trained, committed teachers. Digital school development does not only take place at the classroom level, it is much more comprehensive and also requires the ability to work in a team. The willingness of all actors to cooperate and coordinate as well as the demonstration of "best practice" examples are relevant for success.

Research guiding questions

Belonging to question a) Media developments, teaching media and basics on information processes in the context of school teaching

If one examines the historical development of the media, a distinction can be made between primary (human media), secondary (print media) and tertiary media (electronic and digital media). Later, the term "quaternary media" also became current. With the spread of computer-based communication, authors used this term when using networked computer technology. These are "type 4 media". Here, sender and receiver need an internet connection. There is no longer a classic sender-receiver role, but communication is interactive. Basically, and also in the field of education, a distinction is made between analogue and digital media. In this context, the terms "new media" and "interactive media" are also in use. However, there is no uniform definition of medium or media.

The digital media that are particularly relevant in actual research - in which information is conveyed via interfaces - have been around since the 1980s. These not only enable the distribution of information, but users can also become active. This is also relevant for school lessons and leads to the possibility of creating one's own (educational) content. The computer gradually became the integrating leading medium. The entire 20th century was essential for developments in the context of the computer. From about the beginning of the 1980s, the technology had already matured to such an extent that companies, educational sectors and private users were benefiting from the use of computers. Some educators had computers at school and also "home computers" already from about the mid-1980s. The "Commodore C64"

was used very often. With this computer, which did not yet have any internal mass storage devices, it was possible to write, draw, calculate and programme. In its full potential, the Commodore C64 was a programmable all-purpose computer. With the spread and further development of the computer, the spread of the Internet also began in the 1980s. From 1983, the Internet Protocol (IP) opened up a modern or new standard for data transmission in computer networks. The Internet Protocol is a network protocol; it combines the information to be transmitted into IP data packets and regulates the transmission of the data packets to the specific destination. Since the beginning of the 1990s, the development of the World Wide Web (www) has made it possible for PC users who are online to use the Internet. The World Wide Web is a system of electronic hypertext documents that can be accessed via the Internet, i.e. web pages encoded in HTML. They are linked to each other by hyperlinks and are transmitted on the internet via the https or http protocols. Web pages frequently contain texts, often with pictures, also videos, audio documents, etc. If correctly selected and well prepared, these can be useful for teaching. A high standard of care is essential here. The influence of the parental home, school and circle of friends plays a role in the personal attitude towards the mass media. The results of a study in the canton of Zurich reveal a picture of schoolchildren who use mass media in a very differentiated way and in many cases in everyday life. Each medium has its own specific significance in the overall constellation, even though the various media do not mean the same thing to all pupils. Socialisation instances have an essential significance in this context. Around the mid-1990s, computers were no longer just individual machines; they became parts of a network. Around the turn of the millennium, further significant technical developments took place, especially that of "Web 2.0", which went far beyond the logic of "Web 1.0"; it enabled diverse forms of communication and participation. In the field of science, it is assumed that in 2002, mankind was already able to store more information in digital than in analogue media. This was the beginning of the digital age with rapid, but very dynamic developments of digital media. As a result, the spectrum of "teaching media" has also expanded considerably. Consequently, a standard of teaching media developed in the school sector, both acoustically, visually and audiovisually. In many cases, pupils

already integrate digital media into their everyday life and learning processes and cover very different areas of competence. They use digital media primarily for communication, information and entertainment and are basically motivated and concentrated. However, the intensity of use depends on the age and other factors. It must be considered here how these already existing knowledge elements can be made usable for school learning processes. Decisive factors are school levels, types of school, existing technical requirements, the interest and motivation of teachers, etc.

Belonging to question b) The meaning of models (excerpt)

Models for digitalisation processes are important for a successful implementation of digital media. The development of strategies - for scientifically based digitalisation steps in the context of school development processes - is a necessary condition for success. Models are often focused on specific aspects of digitalisation - such as information technologies, etc. Concerning the models selected and examined in the present work, it can be stated that they are in any case suitable as an orientation aid. They also provide a good overview of different approaches. However, the objectives and perspectives of these models differ, is why conclusions drawn from the examination of these models also vary.

The "SAMR model" is primarily related to the development of teaching and, in the context of "using digital media in the classroom", also enables it to analyse and reflect on this and to design tasks. This model can also be used to examine learning experiences with digital media. Educators can reflect on how they integrate digital media in the classroom. This can be done either as a direct replacement for work tools without functional change, or as an extension, change or renewal by designing new educational tasks.

In the "4K model", significant competences are summarised. Communication, collaboration, critical thinking and creativity are seen as four interdisciplinary key competences. This model can be helpful to cope well with digital teaching and learning scenarios. It is a good approach for intended developments. In contrast to the SAMR model, where educators, their use and the use of learning technologies are

essential, the 4K model focuses on the question of competence acquisition in the context of new global challenges with a clear focus on pupils.

The so-called "IQES model" promotes an instruction-centred school development that empowers the educators for their tasks and sees the successful independent learning of the pupils as central. This model is a practical orientation framework whose individual elements can be well adapted to specific requirements. It is designed to focus educators' energies and work resources on their core task, i.e. effective and sustainable support of students' learning processes and outcomes. This means self-directed and cooperative learning as an essential relief factor for teachers. The eight fields of action of this model include self-directed learning, development of competences, good teaching, individual feedback, work in teaching teams, cooperative teaching development, school leadership and staff development as well as school development and internal evaluation. In the context of this model, the topic "digital education" is essential and should in practice include a comprehensive media library of teaching ideas, video tutorials, guides and annotated collections of tools, foundational texts, platforms, etc. These are important foundations for contemporary education in a digital world. It is also a major advantage of the IQES model that learning objectives can be formulated here with verbs and learning and (digital) media products can also be assigned to them.

The "ARCS model focuses" on four motivational conditions. These are Attention, Relevance, Confidence and Satisfaction. This model - which originates from Keller and Kopp (1987) and was built on the basis of the already existing motivational design by Keller (1983) - can be seen as a motivational instructional design for e-learning. The acronym ARCS stands for the four motivational conditions shown, which are to be seen as indirect motivational support areas and closely connected to self-directed learning. It is a model of motivation or a learning psychology model. In my opinion, it is essential for the teachers to apply it in their teaching practice. They should succeed in achieving and maintaining the students' joy of learning and motivation from the beginning of the lesson and for the entire duration of the lesson.

The "Dagstuhl Dreieck" and this model were developed by the Gesellschaft für

Informatik in the context of the so-called "Dagstuhl Erklärung 2016". At that time, experts from different areas of science demanded an independent learning area that should be explicitly included in curricula. This also means interdisciplinary action and subject-specific connections in the context of media education and media competence. The model includes three perspectives of digital education as well as three forms of manifestations for the school sector. These are the "technological", "socio-cultural" and "application-related perspectives", which can, however, influence each other. Educators, pupils, students, etc. must be able to deal with digital media in a self-determined way, and their possible uses should be clear. Digital systems should be investigated and understood in terms of interactions between actors, possibilities of influence, etc. Due to the rapid developments and advancements in the digital world, especially of information technologies, the Dagstuhl Erklärung can be seen as very positive, with a vision for the future.

Regarding the model of "Brandhofer and Wiesner" (2018), it can be stated that the question "which competences they should have when using digital media" is particularly essential for the digital competence of learners. Different perspectives of digital competence are demonstrated and related to each other. Central competence models and lists of competences for teachers and learners as well as their position and structure are well depicted. This model is an "integrative framework model for learners' digital competence". One of the authors' intentions was to achieve positive results in the context of Austrian educational research. An essential result of their research demonstrated that "Digi.kompP" includes the list of statements as well as a framework model. The competence catalogues "digi.komp4, digi.komp8 and digi.komp12" are a list of "can-do statements" and have no underlying competence model. The concepts "DigComp" and "DigCompEdu" are seen as digitalised lists. The concepts are taken up and combined by the integrative model. Essential for the research of Brandhofer and Wiesner were, among others, the "Grundsatzlerlass zur Medienerziehung" of the former Federal Ministry (BMBF 2014), the "Investigation of the Lists of Digital Competences" by "digi.komp4", "digi.komp8" as well as "digi.komp12" and "relevant changes in the ordinance on the curricula" or curricula on digital education. The model of "Brandhofer and Wiesner" makes a significant

contribution to the discussion and discourse regarding "digital competences of learners".

Deimann's research shows, among other things, that digital learning programmes have the potential to enable important networking. I.e. also to combine motivating aspects with each other. Digital media have a motivating effect in particular through their interactivity and adaptivity; in addition, auditory and visual impressions are essential for learners. Among other things, the essential difference between face-to-face and distance learning is pointed out. According to Deinmann, online learning offers can basically motivate learners through their possibilities. In addition, visual media in the classroom improve learning motivation; they also lead to increased joy of learning. In principle, concentration and attention are improved, which can also have a positive influence on learning perseverance.

The models selected and examined in the context of the present work provide a good overview of different approaches. However, their objectives and perspectives differ very clearly, which is why a reflective review by the actors is always necessary. In the context of application, parts of the different models could also be combined. However, this requires a thorough engagement with this topic. In any case, the models examined are open to discussion in the context of digitalisation and the use of digital media in teaching; they should also contribute to further discourses.

Belonging to question c) The essential development steps in the context of digitalisation in the Austrian school system

If one traces the development of digitalisation and digital media in the Austrian school system, it can be stated that the infrastructure, the teaching of digital competences or knowledge, skills and abilities as well as areas of law are of central importance. In this context, media education/media pedagogy and media competence are very important.

Since the establishment of a "Department for Media Education" in 1991 and subsequently a "Department for Practical Media Education" in the Federal Ministry in charge at that time, "media education" has been anchored in the Austrian education

system. A major step was taken with the introduction of the "Grundsatzrlass Medienerziehung" in 2001, an, which also established the teaching principle that is still valid today. This basic decree was updated in 2014 in the context of the increasing importance of media. It is the basis for interdisciplinary media education in Austria throughout the entire school career and obliges all educators to consider media education - a "cross-sectional matter" - in their subject. Media education is understood as comprehensive media education to promote media competence; it also means media policy education.

Another development step was the "Education Reform Act 2017", which adopted the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education". This compulsory exercise affects the curriculum of the AHS lower level and the Neue Mittelschulen. Essential contents of this new subject include digital user knowledge of operating systems, digital communication and social media, safe and critical use of the internet, aspects of media change, and above all problem-solving skills. Through independent implementation of this compulsory exercise by schools, they now have scope for design here. This concerns the time frame, school levels as well as the form of instruction. I.e. "digital basic education" as a separate subject, integrative in the subject lessons or also as a mixed form. Several accompanying measures have been planned in order to support schools in the introduction of the new subject.

With the "IKT Schulverordnung 2021" or the "Verordnung über IKT-gestützten Unterricht und Datensicherheitsmaßnahmen im Schulwesen", the competent Federal Ministry issued the necessary technical and organisational framework conditions for the use of digital forms of learning and work. This created a framework for technical and organisational measures to ensure the data security in the processing of school data, as well as for technical and organisational measures for digital end devices, and for accountability in school data processing. The Schulunterrichtsgesetz (§ 14a SchUG) also defines ICT-supported instruction - i.e. instruction supported by information and communication technology - and the use of digital end devices (laptops, tablets, etc.). Knowledge about IT security is also essential in this context and is of increasing importance.

Further significant developmental steps in the context of digitalisation and digital media in the Austrian school system:

With regard to digital school development, "eEducation Austria" pursues the formation of a national community for the development of digital and information competences as an essential task. It began in 2016 on behalf of the then BMB at the University of Education in Upper Austria, which is also the competence centre "National Center of Competence eEducation" (eEducation Austria). The promotion of these skills starts in primary schools (elementary schools) and extends to the matriculation and diploma examinations. The aim is to acquire the necessary competences to be able to use technologies for their own further development. "eEducation Austria" is a three-pillar concept with the pillars "personal digital competences, teaching development and organisational development". Personal digital competence is the foundation for the use of technology in teaching. Regarding the "development of digital competences", educators must also develop their own digital competences, especially the competence to assess the effects of media use. The didactically sensible use of digital media in all subjects and the increase of digital and informatics competences of pupils are essential for all activities in the context of "eEducation Austria". An important topic is the use of digital media scenarios that generate added value for teaching. This provides educators with good approaches, a certain degree of security for their own teaching and, in principle, opportunities to evaluate pupils' digital competences.

"Digital competences" and "computer literacy" are laid down in different legal foundations. The "digi.komp umbrella" is also essential for the implementation of the mandatory requirements from primary school to secondary level 2. Here it is shown which skills are specifically necessary with the "autonomous, reflective use of information and communication technologies" mentioned in the curriculum. Since 2006, the so-called "digi.komp initiative" has been promoted in the education sector; implementation was initially on a voluntary basis but was then integrated into curricula mandatorily. These are the different "digi.komp" models that are important for practice.

The "National Education Report 2015" then stated, among other things, "that it

is not the use of digital media per se that is problematic, but that there is a danger of not using these media optimally". In the context of media education, this must be taken into account both in the training of educators and in the teaching of pupils. In this education report, the authors also stated that initiatives to promote digital media literacy are neither effective nor efficient. This concerned both quantitative and qualitative areas. In any case, this view is open to discussion and should also encourage comparison with other research results in this field.

Concerning the period 2015 to 2018, the so-called "Grünbücher des österreichischen Bundesrates" are also of interest. In the view of the Federal Council, a space must be allowed in which innovations and new technologies can develop for the benefit of people. The framework conditions must be designed in such a way that social justice is also guaranteed in a digitalised society. The topics of work, education, data security and democracy in the context of social justice and digital transformation are to be seen as particularly important in this context.

In 2016, a joint digitalisation strategy of the then Federal Government was launched with the "Digital Roadmap Austria" - a dynamic strategy paper that is continuously adapted to current developments in the context of digitalisation. The Digital Roadmap Austria provides an up-to-date overview of the current status as well as current and planned measures and activities. In this context, twelve guiding principles are essential for shaping digitalisation in Austria. A "task force" consisting of the "Chief Digital Officer" of each ministry shall advance the work on the new digital strategy for Austria. The development steps of the "Digital Roadmap Austria" from 2020 to 2024 are also shown in the present thesis. The ongoing adaptation to current developments can be seen as very positive in this strategy paper.

In 2017, the competent Ministry of Education in Austria took another important step towards promoting digital and IT skills with the "Digitalisation Strategy School 4.0. However, the basis for promoting digital competences in the Austrian education system was already created through the "digi.komp model". The "DigComp concept" of the "Joint Research Centre of the European Commission" was also relevant. The implementation of the digitalisation strategy "School 4.0", which was elaborated and presented by the Federal Ministry, then started with the school

year 2017/2018. The strategy ranges from teaching technical skills to media education and covers the entire school career. In the context of this digitalisation strategy, "digital education" must be seen as an absolute key factor for the present and the future; "digital competences" are part of the educational standard of pupils and students. From a certain level of achievement or school types and school levels onwards, "computational thinking" is also essential. This requires a good basic digital or informatics education as an IT foundation.

This was also expected from by the "Compulsory exercise in digital basic education". In the future, graduates of secondary schools and grammar schools will be expected to be digitally literate - above all, in order to be able to cope well with political participation opportunities through the internet in the context of the education system, globalisation, etc. The implementation is the obligation of the schools themselves (independently). This basic digital education is divided into competence areas, which are "digital competence", "media competence" and "political competence". It can be assumed that the possibility of networking these competences has positive effects, especially concerning the acquisition of knowledge. In addition to the curriculum for the subject, other educational standards are also relevant for the acquisition of competences. For example, the digital competences defined by Narosy in Austria, which are also internationally comparable.

The Austrian federal government declared 2019 the "Year of Digitalisation", actively shaping a major and far-reaching change. According to the minister in charge at the time, a turnaround was necessary because a modern society needs digitally competent citizens. To develop these digital skills as the fourth basic competence, the minister supported "fit4internet" as patron and initiator. Under the umbrella brand "Digital Austria", the Austrian Federal Government presented central projects in the fields of society, economy and administration in February 2019. The "Digital Austria" initiative is significantly supported and implemented by the Digitalisation Agency (DIA). As far as "Digital Austria" is concerned, it can be stated that the increasing digital competences of citizens and the increasing demands of digitalisation by service institutions have been focused on for decades. The prioritisation in the context of "Digital Austria" can be seen as very positive; it also provides a good overview of

topics and development areas.

In the "Austrian Government Programme 2020 to 2024", major goals were also set in the field of education. The topic of education, science, research and digitalisation is one of the six major chapters.

However, digital competences and informatics education have been laid down in "curricula", "teaching principles", etc. for quite some time. The "Austrian Government Programme 2020-2024", here on the topic of digitalising Austria's school education, should also guarantee a reliable and practical implementation. "digikomp" also makes a significant contribution to this. It is essential for all actors to make optimal use of the digital potential in the Austrian school system.

After the first major lockdown in Austria in the context of Covid-19, the "Digital Action Plan Austria" was published by the Federal Ministry of Digitalisation and Economic Location (BMDW) in June 2020. This action plan primarily calls for more digital innovations. Basic digital education and training in the so-called "MINT subjects", i.e. "mathematics", "computer science", "natural science" and "technology", shall also be promoted. One of the objectives of the "Digital Action Plan" is to lead Austria in a crisis-resistant and innovative manner into the future. Austria wants to use digitalisation to further develop competitiveness, innovative strength, prosperity, climate protection, health and cultural education in a targeted manner. With the "Digital Action Plan Austria" based on the government programme, the BMDW is launching a forward-looking initiative. The Digital Action Plan for Austria also refers to the "Master Plan" for digitalisation. The essential goal here is to gradually integrate the changes as a result of digitalisation throughout the Austrian education system. This master plan also includes three major fields of action, namely the field of action "software", the field of action "hardware" and the field of action "teachers". Regarding the field of action "software", new teaching and learning content from the field of digitalisation is to be systematically integrated into the curricula in the course of a revision of existing curricula. In particular, this is intended to provide "contemporary teaching" in all subjects in a methodological and didactical manner. With regard to the field of action "hardware", the infrastructural equipment and the availability of mobile end devices are to be brought to a unified and

comparable standard. In addition, the prerequisites for the use of digital instruments and tools in schools should be created throughout Austria. With regard to the field of action "teachers", digitalisation and new possibilities of teaching content should be systematically anchored in the training and further training of teachers. Due to the specific objectives of the fields of action listed above, it can be assumed that they also contribute to the optimisation of digitalisation and educational processes, including the procurement of information and the acquisition of knowledge.

Above all, an essential step towards digitalisation shall be achieved by the "Master Plan for Digitalisation". The successive implementation of the digital school is effected through the "eight-point plan" for digital teaching. With its specific objectives, this plan specifies the next development steps for a nationwide implementation of digitally supported teaching and learning, as well as for a broad implementation of innovative teaching and learning formats. With the implementation of the eight-point plan "Digital School", digitally supported teaching and innovative teaching and learning formats will be comprehensively and sustainably anchored in the education system (in a next development step). The "Master Plan" and the "Eight Point Plan" are very important for the Austrian school system, also in terms of a far-sighted vision of the future.

Belonging to question d) Basics on media education in the digital and global world

Based on the research literature examined, "media education" in the field of science is to be seen as a lifelong education and development process aimed at a self-determined and self-responsible use of media. However, this takes place in different fields of socialisation. "Media literacy" has been an essential educational goal in the context of media education content for decades. In particular, it enables the well-founded reflection and creative design of media. School lessons as well as the family, circle of friends, etc. are essential here. This should be taken into account by educators, especially in the context of media literacy. Media literacy in the context of school does not only refer to digital media but also to analogue media such as textbooks etc. Media education, especially for the acquisition of media literacy, is

essential during school life and for the entire further life, including political participation (Zeilner, 2014). "School media education aims at media-competent pupils who are able to orient themselves in a world shaped by media and have an understanding of the basic values of democracy and freedom of opinion". Reflection, the ability to assess opportunities and risks, and knowledge of legal principles are essential. Media literacy includes the analytical examination of causes, effects and forms of media communication and the reality shaped by the media. The imparting of such competences is an essential task of educators.

If one takes a look at the research results on the topic of media education in schools, these turn out to be controversial. Moreover, they (still) show the existence of shortcomings. From the point of view of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research in Austria, media education "...is dedicated to the established media cultures and reflects the ever-changing media worlds. Media education is understood as personality development, as a process and as the result of the mediation process of world and self through media". This includes the essential areas of critical and creative thinking as well as the resulting action, an ability to use digital media, to understand their contents and to critically question them. This is necessary, among other things, to be able to make full use of the potential of the Internet and not just to accept news, but to question its origin, intention, etc. This also includes political communication and the ability to think creatively. This also includes political communication and the necessity of a basic digital education, which is already available in the Austrian school system. Receiving and evaluating media content and results quickly and efficiently is essential here.

In Professor Herzig's view, educators should be able to go beyond their own media competence and create learning conditions for pupils that promote the development and advancement of their media skills. This already requires targeted training in the context of teacher training studies at universities and teacher training colleges.

"Media literacy models" define media literacy more precisely, but above all they determine which skills and competencies are to be taught. The models by "Aufenanger" and "Baacke" are among the best known in the German-speaking

world. Aufenanger divides these skills into six dimensions ("Cognitive Dimension, Action Dimension, Moral Dimension, Social Dimension, Affective Dimension and Aesthetic Dimension"), which are equally important and easily comprehensible. For Baacke, media literacy means the ability to "use all kinds of media for people's repertoire of communication and action in a way that actively appropriates the world". His definition is based on Habermas's competence model for communicative action and is a model of communicative competence with the areas "media criticism", "media studies", "media use" and "media design". The first two areas refer to the knowledge area, while the last two refer to active application. According to Baacke, the promotion of media competence is the most important task in the field of media education. People who are media competent can use media well "actively" and "passively"; this is much more than "just" operating media and is a learning process.

The terms "media education" and "media literacy" are often used synonymously, but this is basically irrelevant. However, it is essential that two areas can be ascertained in the Austrian school system. These are the "media education perspective" and the "information technology perspective". From the media pedagogical perspective, digital education is a sub-area of a complex media education that includes all analogue and digital media. The "Grundsatzrlass Medienerziehung" - a "teaching principle" - is the basis for media education in the Austrian school system, it is to ensure the "integration of (digital) media" and "media education" in all subjects, school types and school levels. Learning informatics basics is very essential here. In this approach, media education is to be seen as digital education, with increasing importance above all due to rapid developments in the field of information technologies, changes in areas of life, etc.

Opportunities for learning in the context of education, training and further education, especially learning in one's own working environment, have changed and will continue to change. Digital learning is of great relevance in these days, even though a differentiated view is necessary. In order to understand the positive and negative effects of digitalisation on certain areas of life, it is necessary to know the basics about digitalisation. This is a process of learning and also requires adaptation on the part of educators, pupils and students.

Belonging to question e) Analysis of studies: research topics and results

The topics "digitalisation" and "use of digital media in the classroom" are controversially discussed in science. In the present work, it is assumed that the examination of meta-studies and individual findings can lead to essential insights, which is why meta-studies and individual findings on concrete topics were examined and reflected upon.

Meta study: "Invisible Learning" (John Hattie)

Numerous meta-studies were examined and compared in the study "Invisible Learning" by John Hattie, a meta-analysis. The research interest was the investigation of factors that influence the learning effectiveness of teaching, here also the investigation of the use of various digital media. Hattie took a very differentiated view of computer-aided teaching. Among the prerequisites for positive effects, he saw the need for a variety of teaching strategies, "pre-training" for the use of computers for the actors, for multiple learning opportunities, that the learners have control over learning, and that peer learning and feedback are optimised.

The analysis of meta-analyses related to the effectiveness in terms of subject-related performances. The examination was conducted using (standardised) achievement tests. The effect size (Cohen's d) as a measure of effectiveness is here independent of the sample size and independent of the unit of measurement in the original study. Hattie examined possible influences in terms of their effect size. He ranked these influences on a scale from very positive effects to negative effects on learning in school. The average effect of all influencing variables is ($d=0.40$). He evaluated the success of school interventions on learning outcomes relative to this "hinge point". A crucial question in the context of this research is, among others, "What really makes a difference in terms of learning success?". The effects of the studies used or included resulted in effect sizes between ($d=0.20$) and ($d=0.60$). The average was ($d=0.37$). In this scientific study, Hattie defined the value ($d=0.40$) as the threshold value. The value ($d=0.40$) is the mean effect size of all measures examined by Hattie. Values below ($d=0.40$) mean a below-average effect, values above

($d=0.40$) mean an above-average effect. The main finding of this research is "that digitally supported learning has a fundamentally positive effect on pupils' learning results". However, the effect sizes of digital media are not very large. The Hattie study has also been criticised, among other things, because only a few concepts of digital learning were examined and years had passed by the time the relevant studies were conducted.

Meta-Study: Extension of the study (Heike Schaumburg)

In 2018, Heike Schaumburg expanded the Hattie study with the research objective to determine whether different results can be expected when investigating further concepts of digital learning - including new research results. Concepts of digital learning (flipped classroom, game-based learning) as well as different equipment concepts such as laptops, tablets and interactive whiteboards) were added. The aim was to achieve "empirical findings on the effectiveness of different concepts of digitally supported learning". The main result here is that learning effectiveness is influenced by many factors. "Digitally supported learning has an overall positive effect on the subject-related performance of students; negative effects were not found in any meta-analysis". However, the effects are often only small - regardless of the measures or concepts. It is remarkable that the small effects were found more often in more recent studies than in older studies. This was explained, among other things, by the complexity of their use in the classroom. Well-trained and motivated teachers, the technical prerequisites (hardware and software) as well as different prerequisites of the learners are essential for exploiting the potential to support learning. It could not be clearly determined which equipment concepts are particularly effective. However, the educators and the forms of teaching play a central role. The "potential of digital media to support learning" is not as well utilised in "teacher-centred teaching" as in "pupil-centred" teaching. Here, learners basically need individual support from teachers and/or classmates.

According to Schaumburg, research on digital media suggests that educators play an absolutely decisive role. It is not (only) the media themselves that are important, but also the way in which they are integrated into the classroom. Digital

media are not good or bad per se, they have to be well selected and prepared. This requires adaptation measures or competences on the part of the actors, especially interested, motivated and well-trained teachers. I was able to see this myself during my teaching work as an educator in higher education.

Meta study: "Metastudy on the learning effectiveness of digital media in mathematics and science lessons at secondary level " (ZIB/TIM Study)"

In the context of this meta-study, it was assumed that especially science subjects such as "biology", "chemistry", "physics" as well as "mathematics" hold great potential for an effective use of digital media. Numerous studies have already investigated the conditions under which effects arise through digital media in "mathematics and science lessons". However, the results did not always provide a unified picture (Özyurt, Perry & Steck, etc.). The authors of the present study criticised the fact that in previous meta-analyses only certain subjects or types of learning programmes were of research interest and that only studies from certain countries were included in the analyses. In this meta-study, the researchers used a total of seventy-nine (79) individual studies. The primary studies relate to the subjects of mathematics, physics, biology and chemistry. The effectiveness of digital media on the achievement of secondary school students was investigated in the "intervention group" compared to the "control group", which was taught without digital media. The result shows that the use of digital media in "mathematics and science lessons" has a positive, "moderately strong effect" on the learning performance. Positive effects were found for all subjects examined and for all school levels in secondary education. In addition, a "small positive overall effect" could also be determined with regard to the attitude towards the subject. "Overall, the results of the study indicate that the use of digital media in mathematics and science subjects has a positive effect on the performance and motivation of secondary school students. However, no generally valid statement can be made. This is substantiated in particular by the numerous but differing learning programmes available. However, the results of this meta-study and the survey among educators have provided specific orientation on how the use of digital media can be a valuable support for teachers and learners. These empirically

derived findings can be beneficial for the mentioned teaching subjects and actors mentioned. This meta-study also demonstrates that digital media must above all be adapted to the individual prerequisites of the students and integrated into the lessons in accordance with the specific learning content.

Meta-Study: "How effective are digital media in the classroom?" (Bardo Herzig)

This meta-study investigated the effectiveness of digital media in the context of teaching. Digital media", "teaching processes" and "the actors involved in teaching" were assumed to be "constitutive factors". However, these factors are further differentiated in order to be able to assess direct or indirect effects on possible learning outcomes. With this study, the state of research at that time is also presented through numerous references to further literature.

An essential result of this study is that the effect of digital media is very context-dependent and therefore cannot be generalised. Discussions and debates with groups of pupils - who benefit most from the use of digital media - led to the result that this question cannot be answered in general terms with group-specific characteristics. However, the examination of individual factors enables to determine individual effects, especially on the learning success. The predictor of learning success is prior knowledge of the topic and media. Pupils who already have better prior knowledge can also benefit most from digital media offers/learning offers. This is substantiated by the fact that new knowledge meets existing prior knowledge and can be built upon. In addition, media-specific attitudes are also essential, i.e. what attitude do pupils have towards a digital medium as a learning medium. The difference between image and text media is also relevant here. "Capacities for self-direction" or "learning strategies" that students have, as well as motivation and interest, are also an influencing variable. However, prior knowledge and self-management skills are the most important factors explaining inter-individual differences in the context of learning with digital media. This also applies to socio-economic factors, etc.

"Digital media in the classroom" affect different levels. Here, a distinction is also made between the levels of organisational development, personnel development and teaching development. The "effects of digital media in teaching" are not only achieved through the technical medium, but through systemic connections. There are no generally valid statements; each individual case must be examined in detail. However, there are certain basic parameters that can be determined, especially "specific (contextual) conditions". Opportunities for the development of pedagogical concepts of action in which information technologies support the achievement of desired goals are therefore essential. This means design-oriented educational research with processes of feedback to people working in the field. Herzig's research results are of interest both to actors in the field of teaching practice and to the field of science. This should also inspire further research.

Individual case study: "Internet use and media competence of young people in Austria" (IFES)

The topics of the survey were "internet use", "media competence", "being affected by cyber-bullying" and "interest in net-political topics". The study includes essential questions for suggestions and a better anchoring and teaching of media competence in the Austrian education system.

The aim of this research was to find out how young people themselves assess their digital skills, how they evaluate them in their social environment, what they learn about media education at school and what they increasingly ask for in this context.

An essential result is that most young people consider their skills to be very good. They stated that they had taught themselves many things. From the point of view of the young people interviewed, peers are the reference group with the highest level of competences. Increased media education at school is a wish of many young people. The desire for an improvement of the corresponding competences of the educators is particularly strong. This also concerns intergenerational learning and peer-to-peer learning. From the point of view of those surveyed, there is room for

improvement in the technical equipment of schools, for example WLAN and technical devices. Since more and more young people are using digital media, such as smartphones, etc. at an early age, the researchers assume that media education should already take place at lower school levels. However, this is controversially discussed. This study also shows, among other things, that media education in Austria needs a higher priority in the school and extracurricular environment. This study provides essential insights for actors in teaching practice but also for the field of educational policy. The results are up for discussion.

Single case study: "How fit are Austrian schools for the digital world?"

Within the scope of this OMG study, a total of 805 people were interviewed, including about 200 students of the second secondary level, 100 educators and 500 people from the parents' area. Significant results of the study: Seventy-six per cent of Austrian students reported spending more than three hours a day in front of a computer, laptop, tablet, smartphone, etc. for school purposes. About seventy percent of all respondents said they were satisfied with the technical equipment of the hardware in the schools. However, it is remarkable that two thirds of the teachers stated that they were not sufficiently trained for digital teaching or did not have sufficient basic knowledge of such learning materials. It is also noteworthy that about half of these teachers were under thirty years old. Eighty-two per cent of the educators called for an increased focus on digital education. There were considerable differences in perception among students and educators, especially concerning the topic of new digital learning materials in the classroom. About half of the students surveyed said that they also use free programmes from the internet because these are not sufficiently available at their school. Media competence - in this case learning critical media consumption for the following professional life - was essential for about ninety percent of the respondents. However, only about fifty-three per cent of the teachers, sixty-one per cent of the students and twenty per cent of the parents considered the competences taught at school to be essential. This study also reveals, among other things, the lack of competence of some educators in the context of digital media, as well as the lack of digital materials relevant to teaching. This should

be discussed within the framework of an "Education Circle" and also inspire further research.

Based on the examination of relevant research literature, the analysis of scientific studies and the author's own experience as a teacher at secondary schools and as a university lecturer, it can basically be assumed that "adaptation measures" on the part of the actors are necessary with regard to the topic "Possible potentials of digital media in the context of teaching". This also includes adaptive learning, a teaching concept where the way of imparting knowledge is adapted to the level of knowledge, the learning preferences and the learning environment in order to enable a measurable and comparable learning success for all learners. Positive effects can be achieved through (possible) "multimodality". This can be substantiated in particular by the fact that information can be absorbed via different sensory channels (audio, visual, audio-visual). In principle, this can also make teaching more interesting. In some subjects, the topic of "visualisation" is also essential because it can also make process flows visible. In addition, possibilities of "simulation" are also essential for some subjects. Here, for example, experiments are not carried out in reality, but on a (digital) model. In addition to the possibilities of simulation, the possibility of "modelling" can also be of significant importance in the teaching context at certain types of schools. Here, complex processes are reduced to the essentials and presented acoustically and visually-dynamically. The fact that digital media also fundamentally promote "interactivity" should be regarded as particularly positive. This means a dialogue-oriented communication between the digital medium and the learners and basically promotes interest, motivation, creativity, etc. Interactivity has above all positive effects on communication, cooperation, etc. Joint processing of teaching tasks is supported, which basically leads to good results and also relieves the pressure on teachers. The "ability to work in a team" is also relevant here, as it is a social competence that makes it possible to communicate profitably in a team and to work constructively with other people. The ability to work in a team is becoming increasingly important, especially in working life.

Digitalisation and the use of digital media in the classroom enable, above all, quick access to information. The Internet and the World Wide Web (www) clearly

offer advantages in this respect. Information technologies and digital media in the context of teaching have advantages, but there are also disadvantages. This also affects the health of pupils and students and should be taken into account by teachers.

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